

1 **Supplementary Information for A Double-edged Sword: Evolutionary Novelty along Deep-**
2 **time Diversity Oscillation in An Iconic Group of Predatory Insects**

3
4 HONGYU LI¹, DE ZHUO², BO WANG³, HIROSHI NAKAMINE⁴, SHŪHEI YAMAMOTO⁵,
5 WEIWEI ZHANG⁶, JAMES E. JEPSON⁷, MICHAEL OHL⁸, ULRIKE ASPÖCK^{9, 10}, HORST
6 ASPÖCK¹¹, THET TIN NYUNT¹², MICHAEL S. ENGEL¹³, MICHAEL J. BENTON¹⁴, PHILIP
7 DONOGHUE¹⁴, AND XINGYUE LIU^{1*}

8
9 *¹Department of Entomology, China Agricultural University, Beijing 100193, China;*

10 *²Beijing Xiachong Amber Museum, 9 Shuanghe Middle Road, Beijing 101399, China;*

11 *³State Key Laboratory of Palaeobiology and Stratigraphy, Nanjing Institute of Geology and*
12 *Palaeontology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Nanjing 210008, China;*

13 *⁴Minoh Park Insect Museum, Minoh Park 1–18, Minoh City, Osaka 562-0002, Japan;*

14 *⁵Hokkaido University Museum, Hokkaido University, Sapporo 060-0810, Japan;*

15 *⁶Three Gorges Entomological Museum, Chongqing 400015, China;*

16 *⁷Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Manchester, Manchester M13*

17 *9PL, UK;*

18 *⁸Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin 10115, Germany;*

19 *⁹Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Zweite Zoologische Abteilung, Burgring 7, A-1010, Vienna,*
20 *Austria;*

21 *¹⁰Department of Evolutionary Biology, University of Vienna, Althanstraße 14, A-1090, Vienna,*
22 *Austria;*

23 ¹¹*Institute of Specific Prophylaxis and Tropical Medicine, Medical Parasitology, Medical*

24 *University of Vienna, Kinderspitalgasse 15, A-1090, Vienna, Austria;*

25 ¹²*Department of Geological Survey and Mineral Exploration, Ministry of Natural Resources and*

26 *Environmental Conservation, Myanmar Gems Museum, Nay Pyi Taw 15011, Myanmar;*

27 ¹³*Division of Invertebrate Zoology, American Museum of Natural History, 200 Central Park West,*

28 *New York, New York 10024-5192, USA;*

29 ¹⁴*School of Earth Sciences, University of Bristol, Bristol BS8 1RJ, UK;*

30 * *Correspondence to be sent to: Department of Entomology, China Agricultural University,*

31 *Beijing 100193, China;*

32 *E-mails: xingyue_liu@yahoo.com.*

33

34 **The PDF includes:**

35

36 Supplementary Appendices 1-5

37 REFERENCES

38 Supplementary Figures S1-121

39 Supplementary Tables S1 to S11

40

41 **Supplementary Appendix 1**

42 **METHODS**

43 *Divergence Time and Evolutionary Rate Estimations*

44 To assess the strength of evolutionary rates of different branches and trees, we categorized
45 rates into five ranks based on the distribution of unpartitioned tree rates (Supplementary Fig. S69f)
46 — low (0-1, below the median value), slightly high (1-2, approximately between the median and
47 the upper quartile value (3/4)), moderately high (2-4, over the maximum value and below the
48 boundary of the domain with dense outliers), distinctly high (4-9, the domain with dense outliers)
49 and extremely high (>9, the domain with sparse outliers).

50
51 *Measurements for Phylomorphospace and Morphospace*

52 Permutation tests with sample size corrected (two tailed) were performed for each dataset
53 across different taxonomic groups and time bins to assess whether there are significant differences
54 in morphological disparity (SOV difference as the test statistic) among them, all against the null
55 hypothesis of no difference. In detail, we first made the different sample sizes of the two
56 designated groups equalized by subsampling of the large-size group to obtain equal size of
57 samples as in the small-size group. Then the two newly obtained groups with equal sample sizes
58 were used to calculate the observed value of the test statistic and were randomly permuted into
59 two different groups once to calculate a test statistic. This procedure (subsampling and
60 permutation) was repeated 1000 times to obtain the distribution of P-values (Supplementary Fig.
61 S73, S74, S76). If the median of the P-values is smaller than 0.025, the disparity of the minuend
62 group is significantly larger than those of the subtrahend group (0.025-0.5, insignificantly larger),

63 while if the value is larger than 0.975, the disparity of the minuend group is significantly smaller
64 than those of the subtrahend group (0.5-0.975, insignificantly smaller) (Yu et al. 2021). We also
65 performed Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon tests were for morphological disparity comparison over time
66 bins subdivided in dispRity (Supplementary Table S5).

67 “ $RAB > 1$ ” indicates the two PCoA clusters are separate from each other very well; “ $RAB = 1$ ”
68 indicates the two PcoA clusters touch each other; “ $RAB < 1$ ” indicates the two PCoA clusters
69 overlap (Wang et al. 2011). The higher RAB indicates the better separation and greater distance
70 between two PCoA clusters.

71

72 *Diversification Rate Analyses*

73 The partitioned time tree (completely binary) was input in BAMM v. 2.6 (Mitchell et al.,
74 2018) to estimate diversification rates along tree branches and dynamics through time. We set the
75 global sampling fraction to 0.4121 (143 taxa / ca. 347 fossil and extant taxa of Mantispoidea in
76 this analysis) and sampling fractions respectively for different taxonomic groups edited in an
77 independent file. The numberOccurrences was set to 155 (fossil occurrences of extinct and extant
78 taxa). The initial preservation rate (preservationRateInit) was set to a neutral value of 0.5.

79 We selected nine biotic factors for correlation analyses: (i) intrinsic diversity, morphological
80 disparity and evolutionary rates of (ii-iii) HP, (iv-v) foreleg and (vi-vii) PW, (viii) diversity of
81 gymnosperms and (ix) diversity of angiosperms. The dataset of intrinsic diversity is automatically
82 given in MBD program of Pyrate (*-rmDD 0*), which can test the effect of intra-lineage interactions
83 on the diversification. We focus on the correlation tests of HP, foreleg and PW, given that these
84 anatomical regions exhibit complex and diverse morphology and significant variations across time,

85 which may be directly linked with ecological habits of different groups, such as their predation
86 abilities, flight and dispersal capabilities. The data on morphological novelties and evolutionary
87 rates were derived from the results (median or mean values) of the randomly sampled branch-
88 specific CPS in *Ancestral State Reconstruction* and the evolutionary rate estimations in
89 *Divergence Time and Evolutionary Rate Estimations*.

90 The datasets of diversity of gymnosperms and angiosperms were cited directly from those
91 included in Pyrate (Silvestro et al. 2015b, Lehtonen et al. 2017). Numerous studies have clarified
92 the close relationship between the evolution of plant and insects, either directly or indirectly
93 (Labandeira 1998, Gorden and Adler 2018, dos Santos et al. 2019, Allio et al. 2021, Ashra and
94 Nair 2022, Peris and Condamine 2024). We opted the diversity of gymnosperms and angiosperms
95 primarily considering: (i) gymnosperms and angiosperms are domestic terrestrial vegetation
96 during the 200-million-year evolutionary history of Mantispoidea (from the Late Triassic to the
97 present), with crucial Cretaceous Angiosperm Terrestrial Revolution (Benton et al. 2022, Peris and
98 Condamine 2024). (ii) adults of Mantispoidea are mainly arboreal, while the woody plants they
99 inhabited were primarily angiosperms and gymnosperms across their evolutionary history. (iii)
100 adults of Mantispoidea can directly feed on pollen or nectar, though many species are carnivorous
101 (Nakahara 1961, Batra 1972, Opler 1981, Hoffman 1992). (iv) The diversity and turnover of
102 terrestrial vegetation indirectly impact the diversification of carnivorous mantispoids by directly
103 affecting their herbivorous prey.

104 We selected six abiotic factors for correlation analyses: the level of (x) atmospheric CO₂
105 (Berner and Kothavala 2001), (xi) atmospheric O₂ (Berner 2009), (xii) magmatic activity (Gastil
106 1960, Brink 2015), (xiii) continental fragmentation (Cogné and Humler 2008), (xiv) sea level

107 (Snedden and Liu 2011) and (xv) global mean temperature (Scotese 2016). Fluctuations in
108 atmospheric CO₂ and O₂ levels are believed to be associated with the diversification of various
109 insect groups (Graham et al. 1995, Dudley 1998, Clapham and Karr 2012, Jouault et al. 2022a,
110 Jouault et al. 2022b). It is suggested that higher O₂ levels have likely promoted the diversification
111 of certain insects, while lower O₂ levels may have led to the extinction or reduction of some
112 lineages. Although certain views also suggest that the impact of O₂ concentration on insect
113 diversification may not be as pronounced as previously believed (Clapham and Karr 2012), this
114 factor still merits investigation in this study. Likewise, the alteration in CO₂ concentration,
115 particularly its elevation, is recognized to facilitate speciation in certain extant insect groups (Tang
116 et al. 2018), yet it still needs to be verified in deep timescales. We directly use the CO₂ (Berner
117 and Kothavala 2001) and O₂ data (Berner 2009) included in Pyrate.

118 Although it is uncommon for existing studies to directly explore the impact of volcanic
119 activities on insect diversity, the known positive or negative effects on biodiversity may also
120 influence insects, which account for a significant proportion of biodiversity. The immediate effects
121 of volcanic activity often include habitat destruction from lava and ash, and even direct effect on
122 climate, sharply reducing populations (Sigurdsson 1988, Bond and Wignall 2013). However, as
123 ecosystems recover and new habitats develop, biodiversity may increase due to new ecological
124 niches and resources (nutrient-rich volcanic products) (Vitousek and Chadwick 2013, Saputra et al.
125 2022). Additionally, volcanic activities are believed to be associated with the geohistorical
126 extinction events, such as the End-Permian Extinction event, End-Triassic Extinction event,
127 Cenomanian-Turonian extinction event and K-Pg extinction event (Erwin 1994, Benton and
128 Twitchett 2003, Pearce et al. 2009, Hautmann 2012, Klein et al. 2021). Therefore, it is also worthy

129 to test the impact of volcanic activities on diversification in this study. We used Phanerozoic
130 seawater sulfate $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ from (Present et al. 2020) as the proxy of volcanic activities across time,
131 considering that its significant fluctuations can more closely align with the well-known extinction
132 events aforementioned than the magmatic proxy included in Pyrate.

133 Continental fragmentation may profoundly impact terrestrial biodiversity through
134 mechanisms such as geographic isolation, formation of new habitats, climate change, and altered
135 species interactions. It promotes species divergence by geographically isolating populations in
136 different environments, thereby influencing global biodiversity (Upchurch et al. 2002, Zaffosa et
137 al. 2017, Jouault et al. 2022a). Similarly, the rise and fall of sea level may be also associated with
138 geological isolation, species migration and invasion by leading to the dispersal and connectivity of
139 continents and islands (Lambeck and Chappell 2001, Weigelt et al. 2016). Additionally, changes in
140 sea level directly impact the availability of terrestrial resources for land-based organisms—a rise
141 in sea level leads to a reduction in land resources, whereas a decline increases them (Haq et al.
142 1987, Yin et al. 2021). The datasets of continental fragments (Zaffosa et al. 2017) and sea level
143 (Snedden and Liu 2010) were acquired from those included in Pyrate.

144 Temperature fluctuations, one of the most important indicators of climate change, also
145 significantly impact insect diversity by altering their physiological processes (Condamine et al.
146 2016, Halsch et al. 2021). Temperature variations affect the geographic distribution of insects and
147 their relationships with other organisms, like plants, impacting their food sources and habitats
148 (Bale et al. 2002, Parmesan and Yohe 2003, Condamine et al. 2020). Therefore, we included the
149 global mean temperature data (Scotese 2016) sourced from Pyrate in our analyses.

150 All factor trajectories were rescaled to a range of 0 to 1 prior to analyses, and data points

151 were sampled at one-million-year intervals.

152

153

Novelty Proportion Mapping

154 To map proportion of novelties of HP, foreleg and PW along the unpartitioned time tree in
155 Fig. 2, we used the unpartitioned time tree as the reference to constrain tree topology and run
156 maximum parsimony analysis in TNT V. 1.5 (Goloboff and Catalano 2016, Fikáček et al. 2020): (1)
157 Open the data matrix (*File > Open input file*). The matrix has to be in the correct format (NONA-
158 readable or “.ss”); (2) Open the reference tree (*File > Open input file*). The tree has to have taxa as
159 numbers; (3) Force the reference tree into analysis constraints using the following command in the
160 command line of TNT: *force /&0*; (4) Run the analysis (*Analyze > Implicit Enumeration*). In the
161 analysis window, check the box *Enforce constraints*. The homoplasious and homologous character
162 states mapped by TNT along the tree branches were treated as the novelties. The proportion refers
163 to the ratio of the number of HP, foreleg, and PW novelties to their total sum.

164

165

Correlation Tests

166 We conducted three correlation tests: Pearson correlation, Kendall’s tau, and Spearman’s rank
167 correlation, using the base function “cor.test” of R, to investigate (i) potential correlations between
168 each two of the functional subdivisions in mean evolutionary rates (median values summarized
169 from 24 randomly sampled posterior trees), (ii) morphological disparity (median values of SOV
170 summarized from bootstrap simulations of disparity) and (iii) morphological state changes
171 (median values of CPS summarized from the ancestral state reconstruction of 24 randomly
172 sampled posterior trees). Prior to the tests, we detrended all time series data using the generalized

173 differencing method (Yu et al. 2023). This step was taken to address the common issue of overall
174 trend in time series data, which may lead to spurious positive or negative correlations. All tests
175 were performed under the null hypothesis of no correlation. A coefficient is statistically significant
176 if its $p < 0.05$, leading to rejection of the null hypothesis. Supplementary Table S11 contains the
177 results of all tests.

178

179 Visualization of Results

180 The phylogenetic trees were generated and visually refined using R packages, including
181 *ggtree* v. 3.0.4 (Yu et al. 2017), *phytools* v. 0.7.90 and *FigTree* v. 1.4.4. Box and bar plots were
182 constructed using *ggplot2* v. 3.3.5 (Wickham 2009) or base functions of R. Speciation, extinction
183 and net diversification rates dynamics were graphed using functions in R package *BAMMtools* v.
184 2.1.8 (Rabosky et al. 2013) and R scripts generated by the *PyRate* program (Silvestro et al. 2015a).
185 The evolutionary rate, body size, and comprehensive PCoA score curves over time were also
186 graphed using the “*plotSkylinePretty*” function. The 3D static and interactive graphics of
187 phylomorphospace and morphospace based on taxonomic groupings were generated using the first
188 three axes of PCoA score under R packages *rgl* v. 0.108.3 (Murdoch and Adler 2021) and
189 *alphashape3d* v. 1.3 (Lafarge and Pateiro-Lopez 2017). All R-package-dependent graphs were
190 created using the free software R 4.1.2. Finally, all these graphs were further polished using Adobe
191 *Illustrator* CC 2021.

192

193 **Supplementary Appendix 2. Taxon Sampling**

194

195 **Abbreviation of specimen locations**

196 AMNH American Museum of Natural History, New York

197 CAU Museum of China Agricultural University, Beijing

198 CNUB Key Laboratory of Insect Evolution & Environmental Changes, College of Life Sciences,
199 Capital Normal University, Beijing

200 NIGP Nanjing Institute of Geology and Palaeontology, Nanjing

201 PIN Borissiak Palaeontological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow

202

203 **Osmylidae**

204 **Material examined.**

205 *Osmylus biangulus* Wang & Liu, 2009: 2♂, China, Henan, Luoyang, Mt. Baiyunshan, 1500 m,
206 09.VIII.2020, leg. Wengliang Li [alcohol] (CAU).

207 *Osmylus fulvicepbalus* Scopoli, 1763: 1♂, Austria, Lower Austria, VII.2014, leg. Xingyue Liu
208 [pinned] (CAU). 1♂, Greece, Nomós Ioánnina, Kónitsa E 19km, Ármata, 40°02.10'N, 20°58.11'E,
209 1050 m, 05.XI.2007, leg. Meicai Wei [pinned] (CAU).

210 *Osmylus* sp.: 2♀, China, Shaanxi, Xian, Zhuque National Forest Park, 30.VII.2019, leg. Lu Qiu
211 [alcohol] (CAU).

212

213 **Dilaridae**

214 **Material examined.**

215 *Dilar montanus* Yang, 1992: 6♂, China, Yunnan, Ninglang, Lake Luguhu, 3012.04 m,
216 27°39'29"N, 100°48'15"E, 22.VIII.2019, leg. Di Li [alcohol] (CAU). 2♂1♀, China, Yunnan,
217 Ninglang, Yongning, Lake Luguhu, Dayuba, 2708 m, 12.VI.2009, leg. Hongliang Shi [pinned]
218 (CAU).
219 † *Dilar cretaceus* Liu & Zhang, 2017: Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU-001748, amber piece also
220 preserving a beetle, and four midges; it is polished in the form of a semiellipsoid cabochon, clear
221 and transparent, with length × width about 30.3 × 11.0 mm, height about 5.5 mm.

222

223 **Berothidae**

224 **Material examined.**

225 *Nyrma kervillea* Navás, 1933: 1♂1♀, Turkey, Anatolia, Nemru Dag, R. Dobosz, leg., coll. Horst
226 Aspöck & Ulrike Aspöck [alcohol] (personal collection of Horst Aspöck and Ulrike Aspöck).

227 *Nosybus* sp. 1♂, Kakum Nat. Park, 132 m, 5°20.288"N, 1°22.647" W, 5 April, 2007, leg., coll.
228 Horst Aspöck & Ulrike Aspöck [alcohol] (personal collection of Horst Aspöck and Ulrike Aspöck).

229 *Berotha* sp.1: 1♂, Thailand, Chiang Mai Prov., Inthakin near Mae Taeng, 19.2644°N, 98.9668°E,
230 400 m, 12.VII.2013, leg. S.L. Winterton [alcohol] (CAU).

231 *Berotha* sp.2: 1♀, Malaysia-Kuala Lumpur Selangor Ulu Gombak Forest Reserve, 20.VIII.2003,
232 leg. Svenson [alcohol] (CAU).

233 *Berotha baminana* Yang & Liu: Holotype, ♂, China: Fujian, Dehua, Shuikou, 25°70.060'N,
234 118°45.242'E, 6.XI.1974, leg. Chikun Yang [pinned] (CAU). Paratype, 1♀, same data as holotype.

235 4♂, China, Fujian, Mt. Tianbaoyan, 572.5 m, 20-22.VII.2018, leg. Xiaodong Cai [Malaise trap,
236 alcohol] (CAU). 3♂, China, Fujian, Nanping, Longhu National Forestry, 530 m, 26.VIII.2018,

237 27°32'59"N, 117°28'34"E [Malaise trap, alcohol] (CAU).

238 *Berotha bannana* (Yang, 1986): 1♀, China: Yunnan, Menghai, 18.IV.1981 21°96.343'N,
239 100°45.944'E, Chikun Yang [alcohol] (CAU).

240 *Isoscelipteron eucallum* (Yang & Liu, 1999): 1♂1♀, China, Fujian, Nanping, Longhu National
241 Forestry, 26.VIII.2018. 29°32'59", 117°28'34"E [Malaise trap, alcohol] (CAU).

242 *Lomamyia flavicornis* (Walker, 1853): 1♂7♀, USA, New Mexico, Roosevelt Co, 5 km N Portales,
243 in vegetated sand hills, 1/10.V.2004, ME Irwin, 34°12'N, 103°20'W, leg. S.L. Winterton [Malaise
244 trap, alcohol] (CAU).

245 *Lomamyia squamosa* Carpenter, 1940: 1♂3♀, USA, Arizona, Cochise Co, Bisbee, 1429 Franklin
246 Street, 1585 m, AS Menke, 07-16.VI.2013, 31°24'23"N, 109°55'57"E, leg. S.L. Winterton
247 [Malaise trap, alcohol] (CAU).

248 *Stenobiella* sp.: 1♂5♀, ChelseaRd Bushlands Res. 10.XI.2003, leg. GB Monteith. Ironbark Open
249 Forest [MV light, alcohol] (CAU).

250 *Spermophorella* sp.: 1♂1♀, Australia: QLD: 40km N Noccundra: dry creek bed, 02-09.I.1999,
251 27°29'56"S, 142°38'24"E, C. lambkin, D. Yeates, N. Power & P. Bouchard. Qld: Barakula SF, site
252 1.249m, Malasie, 1-8.Jan.2010, 26.434°S, 150.514°E, leg. Monteith & Turco (CAU).

253 †*Ansoberotha jiewenae* Yang et al., 2019: 1♀, NIGP171712, amber piece also preserving a beetle,
254 a caddis fly, and five flies; it is polished in the form of a nearly rectangular, transparent cabochon,
255 with length× width about 27.50× 23.00 mm, height about 20.80 mm (NIGP). 1ex (terminalia lost),
256 NIGP171713, amber piece also preserving a beetle; it is polished in the form of a nearly
257 rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 16.00× 14.00 mm, height about 8.90
258 mm (NIGP). 1♀, NIGP171714, amber piece also preserving a beetle; it is polished in the form of a

259 nearly ovoid, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 37.80× 30.10 mm, height about
260 14.20 mm (NIGP). 1 ♀, NIGP171715, amber piece polished in the form of a nearly ovoid,
261 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 13.00× 12.00 mm, height about 5.4 mm (NIGP).
262 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-014, amber piece also preserving a beetle; it is polished in the form of a
263 nearly round, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.78× 19.18 mm, height about 9.05
264 mm (CAU). 1ex (terminalia lost), BXAM BA-NEU-037, amber piece polished in the form of a
265 nearly round, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.78× 19.18 mm, height about 9.05
266 mm (CAU).

267 †*Cornoberotha anomala* Yang et al., 2019: Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU001249, amber piece polished
268 in the form of a nearly quadrangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.74× 15.55
269 mm, height about 6.89 mm (CAU).

270 † *Cornoberotha aspoeckae* Yang et al., 2019: Holotype, ♀, NIGP171707, amber piece also
271 preserving a leafhopper, four midges, and a parasitoid wasp; it is polished in the form of a nearly
272 elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 32.30× 23.50 mm, height about 10.00
273 mm (NIGP). Paratype, 1♂, EMTG BU001214, amber piece polished in the form of a nearly
274 elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 21.80× 22.20 mm, height about 6.20
275 mm (CAU).

276 † *Cornoberotha monogona* Yang et al., 2019: Holotype, ♀, NIGP171708, amber piece also
277 preserving five barklice; it is polished in the form of a nearly rectangular, transparent cabochon,
278 with length× width about 34.50× 10.50 mm, height about 9.00 mm (NIGP).

279 †*Dolichoberotha bifurcata* Yang et al., 2019: Holotype, ♂, NIGP171709, amber piece polished in
280 the form of a nearly round, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 21.90× 19.00 mm,

281 height about 5.4 mm (NIGP). Paratype, 1♂, NIGP171710, amber piece preserving a fly and a thrip;
282 it is polished in the form of a nearly elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about
283 26.00× 15.30 mm, height about 7.20 mm (NIGP). Paratype, 1♂, EMTG BU002117, amber piece
284 polished in the form of a nearly elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 19.30×
285 14.00 mm, height about 8.1 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♀, EMTG BU001991, amber piece polished
286 in the form of a nearly rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 31.20× 25.00
287 mm, height about 6.20 mm (CAU).

288 † *Dolichoberothes burmana* Yang et al., 2019: Holotype, ex, NIGP171711, amber piece also
289 preserving four flies, a leafhopper, a barklice and three parasitic wasps; it is polished in the form
290 of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 31.50× 31.00 mm, height about
291 11.00 mm (NIGP).

292 † *Haploberothes persephone* Engel & Grimaldi, 2008: 9♂3♀6ex, BXAM BA-NEU-015, amber
293 piece polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 23.52×
294 14.14 mm, height about 7.08 mm (CAU). 1♂, BXAM BA-NEU-016, amber piece also preserving
295 12 flies and a thrips; it is polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with length×
296 width about 21.32× 14.48 mm, height about 8.39 mm (CAU). 1♂, BXAM BA-NEU-017, amber
297 piece also preserving a barklice; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon,
298 with length× width about 18.38× 12.30 mm, height about 5.90 mm (CAU).

299 † *Iceloberothes simulatrix* Engel & Grimaldi, 2008: 1♂, BXAM BA-NEU-018, amber piece also
300 preserving a beetle and a mealybug; it is polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon,
301 with length× width about 24.81× 18.41 mm, height about 4.84 mm (CAU).

302 † *Jersiberothes tauberorum* Engel & Grimaldi, 2008: 5♂2♀6ex, NIGP171720, amber piece also

303 preserving four flies; it is polished in the form of a bar-shaped, transparent cabochon, with length×
304 width about 29.36× 8.26 mm, height about 3.34 mm (NIGP).

305 †*Osmyloberotha dispersa* Li et al., 2023: Holotype, ♂, NIGP171721, amber piece polished in the
306 form of a rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 13.95× 7.97 mm, height
307 about 4.86 mm (NIGP). Paratype, 1♂, CAM BA-0016, amber piece also preserving a specimen of
308 †*Jersiberotha* sp. three flies and a beetle; it is polished in the form of a rectangular, transparent
309 cabochon, with length× width about 34.72× 10.71 mm, height about 5.52 mm (CAU).

310 †*Osmyloberotha chenzuyini* Zhuo, Li & Liu, 2023: Holotype, ♂, BXAM-BA-NEU-38, amber
311 piece also preserving a beetle and a fly; it is polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent
312 cabochon, with length× width about 23.40× 19.72 mm, height about 5.09 mm (CAU).

313 †*Osmyloberotha magnimaculata* Li et al., 2023: Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19004, amber piece
314 also preserving a specimen of †*Haploberotha carsteni* Makarkin, 2018 and a click beetle; it is
315 polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 25.91× 10.15
316 mm, height about 4.69 mm (CAU).

317 †*Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov, 2021: 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-36, amber piece also preserving a
318 hymenopteran; it is polished in the form of a nearly rectangular, transparent cabochon, with
319 length× width about 22.49× 9.11 mm, height about 4.85 mm (CAU). 1♂, NIGP18053, amber
320 piece polished in the form of a subcircular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 16.44×
321 12.96 mm, height about 3.06 mm (NIGP). 1♂, NIGP18067, amber piece polished in the form of
322 an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 13.46×9.95 mm, height about 3.42
323 mm (NIGP). 1♀, NIGP18068, amber piece polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent
324 cabochon, with length× width about 13.48×10.34 mm, height about 4.42 mm (NIGP).

325 †*Osmyloberotha* sp.1: 1ex (abdomen broken), NIGP18069, amber piece polished in the form of a
326 subcircular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 19.60× 16.27 mm, height about 3.77
327 mm (NIGP).

328 †*Xiaoberotha bipunctata* Shi et al., 2019: Holotype, ♂, EMTG BU-001590, amber piece polished
329 in the form of a rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 27.73× 17.21 mm,
330 height about 5.38 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♀, CAM BA-0014, amber piece polished in the form of
331 a subcircular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 13.94× 10.94 mm, height about 3.87
332 mm (CAU). 1♂, NIGP171263, amber piece also preserving two beetles; it is polished in the form
333 of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 10.82× 7.62 mm, height about
334 3.25 mm (NIGP). 1♀, BXAM-BA-NEU-50, amber piece also preserving a fly, a hemipteran and a
335 caddisfly; it is polished in the form of a sub-rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width
336 about 17.96× 8.60 mm, height about 6.55 mm (CAU).

337 †*Xiaoberotha* sp.: 1ex (terminalia obscure), NIGP171262, amber piece polished in the form of an
338 elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 32.07× 16.61 mm, height about 8.85
339 mm (NIGP).

340

341 **Rhachiberothidae**

342 **Material examined.**

343 †*Acanthoberotha cuspis* Nakamine et al., 2020: 1♂, EMTG BU001992, amber piece also
344 preserving a beetle and two flies; it is polished in the form of a subtriangular, transparent
345 cabochon, with length× width about 19.87× 12.36 mm, height about 7.34 mm (CAU). 1♀, BXAM
346 BA-NEU-019, amber piece also preserving a hemipteran, a parasitic wasp; it is polished in the

347 form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 27.82× 16.37 mm, height
348 about 8.94 mm (CAU). 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-020, amber piece also preserving two flies and three
349 beetles polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about
350 27.34× 20.75 mm, height about 9.51 mm (CAU). 1♀ (terminalia cloudy and unclear), BXAM BA-
351 NEU-039, amber piece polished in form of a sub-rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length×
352 width about 37.09× 13.37 mm, height about 10.56 mm (CAU). 1ex (terminalia cloudy), BXAM
353 BA-NEU-040, amber piece also preserving three beetles; it is polished in form of an elliptical,
354 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 31.94× 19.36 mm, height about 7.08 mm (CAU).
355 1ex (terminalia unclear), EMTG BU002261, amber piece polished in form of an elliptical
356 cabochon, width about 17.43× 12.97 mm, height about 6.33 mm (CAU). 1ex, EMTG BU002285,
357 amber piece also preserving two flies; it is polished in form of a triangular, transparent cabochon,
358 width about 26.58× 16.73 mm, height about 8.64 mm (CAU).

359 †*Astioberotha coutreti* Jouault, 2021: 1♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19005, amber piece polished in the
360 form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 16.41× 14.16 mm, height
361 about 2.35 mm (CAU).

362 †*Astioberotha falcipes* Nakamine et al., 2020: 1♀, EMTG BU001993, amber piece polished in the
363 form of a round, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 15.91× 15.66 mm, height about
364 5.61 mm (CAU).

365 †*Creagroparaberotha cuneata* Nakamine et al., 2020: 1ex, EMTG BU002204, amber piece also
366 preserving a caddisfly; it is polished in the form of a bar-shaped, transparent cabochon, with
367 length× width about 32.19× 6.67 mm, height about 5.25 mm (CAU). 1♀, EMTG BU001995,
368 amber piece polished in the form of a semicircular, transparent cabochon, with length× width

369 about 17.11× 8.04 mm, height about 4.70 mm (CAU).

370 †*Creagroparaberotha* sp.1: 1♂, BXAM BA-NEU-021, amber piece also preserving eight flies, a
371 beetle a parasitic wasp and two barklice; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent
372 cabochon, with length× width about 39.82× 29.74 mm, height about 9.00 mm (CAU). 1♂, BXAM
373 BA-NEU-022, amber piece also preserving a fly and a mealybug; it is polished in the form of an
374 elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 37.31× 29.85 mm, height about 6.94
375 mm (CAU).

376 †*Creagroparaberotha* sp.2: 1ex, NIGP171722, amber piece polished in the form of a round,
377 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 13.34× 10.94 mm, height about 2.18 mm (NIGP).

378 †*Creagroparaberotha* sp.3: 1♀, EMTG BU001402, amber piece also preserving a beetle and a fly;
379 it is polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.62×
380 15.50 mm, height about 4.18 mm (CAU).

381 †*Creagroparaberotha* sp.4: 1♀, EMTG BU002282, amber piece also preserving a fly; it is
382 polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 19.94× 14.72
383 mm, height about 10.10 mm (CAU).

384 †*Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al. 2015: 1♀, EMTG BU002121, amber piece polished in the form
385 of a sub-trapezoidal, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 21.90× 11.72 mm, height
386 about 2.98 mm (CAU). 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-025, amber piece polished in the form of an
387 elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 16.09× 12.61 mm, height about 5.66
388 mm (CAU). 1♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19006, amber piece polished in the form of a subtriangular,
389 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 17.09× 13.12 mm, height about 5.93 mm (CAU).

390 †*Micromantispa galeata* Nakamine et al., 2020: 1♀, EMTG BU001234, amber piece also

391 preserving a fly; it is polished in the form of a subrectangular, transparent cabochon, with length×
392 width about 20.31× 13.07 mm, height about 8.04 mm (CAU). 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-023, amber
393 piece also preserving two flies; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon,
394 with length× width about 31.58× 14.45 mm, height about 6.82 mm (CAU). 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-
395 024, amber piece also preserving a hemipteran and two flies; it is polished in the form of a
396 subtriangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 23.64× 15.91 mm, height about
397 9.31 mm (CAU). 1♀, CAU-BA-NH-20002, amber piece also preserving a dipteran, two beetles
398 and a barklice; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width
399 about 37.50× 27.48 mm, height about 5.58 mm (CAU).

400 †*Micromantispa* sp.: 1♀, EMTG BU002143, amber piece polished in the form of a subrectangular,
401 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.69× 9.95 mm, height about 6.67 mm (CAU).
402 1♀, EMTG BU001224, amber piece polished in the form of a subtriangular, transparent cabochon,
403 with length× width about 16.02× 12.88 mm, height about 6.09 mm (CAU).

404 †*Micromantispa* spp. 1ex, BXAM BA-NEU-043, amber piece also preserving two beetles, two
405 dipteran and a snakefly larva; it is polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with
406 length× width about 34.71× 23.69 mm, height about 16.44 mm (CAU). NIGP171820, amber piece
407 polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 30.70× 19.93
408 mm, height about 5.91 mm (NIGP). 1♀, CAU-BA-HZK-20015, amber piece also preserving three
409 dipteran and a parasitic wasp; it is polished in the form of a round, transparent cabochon, with
410 length× width about 39.11× 35.67 mm, height about 9.28 mm (CAU). 1ex, NIGP171825, amber
411 piece polished in the form of a round, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 14.76×
412 14.31 mm, height about 7.11 mm (NIGP). 1ex, NIGP171826, amber piece polished in the form of

413 an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 28.39× 16.26 mm, height about 5.42
414 mm (NIGP).

415 *Paraberothoides longispina* Li, Zhang & Liu, 2023: Holotype, ♂, EMTG BU001998, amber piece
416 polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 19.22× 12.20
417 mm, height about 5.42 mm (CAU).

418 †*Dicranoberothena liumohanae* Zhuo, Li & Liu: Holotype, ♀, NIGP171723, amber piece polished
419 in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 23.56× 18.97 mm, height
420 about 3.21 mm (NIGP). Paratype, 1♀, NIGP171724, amber piece polished in the form of a sub-
421 trapezoidal, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 15.36× 13.36 mm, height about 7.12
422 mm (NIGP). Paratype, 1♀, NIGP171725, amber piece polished in the form of a subrectangular,
423 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 15.46× 9.85 mm, height about 4.87 mm (NIGP).
424 Paratype, 1♀, NIGP171726, amber piece polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent
425 cabochon, with length× width about 16.92× 11.30 mm, height about 6.66 mm (NIGP). Paratype,
426 1♀, NIGP171727, amber piece polished in the form of an ovoid, transparent cabochon, with
427 length× width about 17.52× 9.61 mm, height about 4.39 mm (NIGP). Paratype, 1♀, BXAM BA-
428 NEU-025, amber piece also preserving a hymenopteran; it is polished in the form of a sub-
429 trapezoidal, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 17.35× 12.93 mm, height about 6.75
430 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-026, amber piece polished in the form of a
431 subtriangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 31.09× 18.88 mm, height about
432 11.40 mm. 1♀, CAU-BA-NH-20002 (CAU).

433 †*Dicranoberothena zhangzhiqiae* Zhuo, Li & Liu: Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-027, amber piece
434 polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 21.55× 12.15

435 mm, height about 8.04 mm (CAU).

436 †*Paradoxoberothes chimaera* Nakamine et al., 2021: Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-NH-20001, amber
437 piece polished in the form of a semicircular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about
438 14.26× 14.02 mm, height about 5.27 mm (CAU).

439

440 †**Dipteromantispidae**

441 †*Burmodipteromantispa jiaxiaoe* Liu, Lu & Zhang, 2017: 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-028, amber
442 piece polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 15.11×
443 10.08 mm, height about 7.41 mm (CAU). 1♂, BXAM BA-NEU-003, amber piece polished in the
444 form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 19.35× 12.71 mm, height
445 about 3.94 mm (CAU).

446 †*Burmodipteromantispa* sp.: 1ex, BXAM BA-NEU-004, amber piece preserving a thrips and an
447 incomplete adult of dipteromantispid, sex unknown because of the apex of abdomen destroyed,
448 and it is polished in the form of an elliptical transparent cabochon, with length× width about 25.7×
449 16.2 mm, height about 6.3 mm (CAU).

450 †*Halteriomantispa grimaldii* Liu, Lu & Zhang, 2016: Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU001924, amber
451 polished in form of sub-rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 20.78× 15.14
452 mm, height about 6.55 mm (CAU).

453 †*Kurtodipteromantispa zhuodei* Li & Liu, 2020: Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-001, amber piece
454 also preserving a dipteran; it is polished in the form of a bar-shaped, transparent cabochon, with
455 length× width about 25.21× 8.03 mm, height about 3.94 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♂, BXAM BA-
456 NEU-002, amber piece also preserving a beetle, two dipterans, a parasitoid wasp; it is polished in

457 the form of a sub-triangle, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 13.11× 6.44 mm,
458 height about 5.76 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♂, CAM BA-0009, amber piece also preserving nine
459 dipterans, a thrips and a beetle; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon,
460 with length× width about 15.69× 9.78 mm, height about 4.73 mm (CAU). 2♂, BXAM-NEU031,
461 amber piece also preserving six dipterans, a hemipteran and a caddisfly; it is polished in the form
462 of a sub-rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 26.85 × 11.88 mm, height
463 about 5.09 mm (CAU).

464 †*Kurtodipteromantispa xiai* Li et al., 2020: Holotype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-001, amber piece also
465 preserving a caddisfly; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with
466 length× width about 20.80× 14.50 mm, height about 3.30 mm (CAU).

467 †*Kurtodipteromantispa* sp.: 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-029, amber piece polished in the form of an
468 elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 30.66× 17.98 mm, height about 7.54
469 mm (CAU). 1♀, NIGP003, amber piece also preserving a dipteran; it is polished in the form of a
470 round, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 11.46× 11.28 mm, height about 4.27 mm
471 (NIGP).

472 †*Enigmadipteromantispa dilatate* Li, Nakamine, Yamamoto & Liu, 2023: Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-
473 GYH-19007, amber piece polished in the form of a subrectangular, transparent cabochon, with
474 length× width about 7.68× 7.62 mm, height about 3.82 mm (CAU).

475 †*Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* Li, Nakamine, Yamamoto & Liu, 2023: Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-
476 GYH-19008, amber piece also preserving nine dipterans and a thrips; it is polished in the form of
477 a subtriangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 8.10× 5.92 mm, height about 2.92
478 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♂, CAU-BA-GYH-19009, amber piece polished in the form of a sub-

479 trapezoidal, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 13.22× 8.91 mm, height about 5.17
480 mm (CAU).

481 †*Kurtodipteromantispa univenula* Li et al., 2023: Holotype, ♂, NIGP173316, amber piece also
482 preserving adipteran; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length×
483 width about 20.80× 14.50 mm, height about 3.30 mm (NIGP).

484 †*Mantispidiptera enigmatica* Grimaldi, 2000: Holotype, ex, AMNH NJ-160, Keith Luzzi (KL-137),
485 White Oaks site, Sayreville, NJ (AMNH).

486 †*Jersimantispa henryi* (Grimaldi, 2000): Holotype, ex, AMNHNJ-437, Stan Klemick, White Oaks
487 site, Sayreville, NJ (AMNH).

488 †*Mantispidipterella longissima* Liu, Lu & Zhang, 2017: Holotype, ♂, EMTG BU002370, amber
489 piece polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 10.12×
490 8.27 mm, height about 5.46 mm (CAU).

491 †*Mantispidipterella* sp.: 1♀, NIGP173216, amber piece polished in the form of an elliptical,
492 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 13.51× 7.62 mm, height about 4.47 mm (NIGP).

493 †*Paradipteromantispa polyneura* Li et al., 2020: Holotype, ♀, NIGP173215, amber piece polished
494 in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 20.09× 15.93 mm,
495 height about 7.30 mm (NIGP).

496

497 **Mantispidae**

498 †*Archaeodrepanicus nuddsi* Jepson et al., 2013: Holotype, ex, CNU-NEU-LB2011001P/C, an
499 almost complete insect preserved in lateral view (CNU). Paratype, 1ex, CNU-NEU-LB2011003,
500 an almost complete insect preserved in lateral view (CNU). Preserved in compressed fossils, from

501 Yixian Formation (Lower Cretaceous, Barremian), Huangbanjigou locality, Liaoning Province,
502 northeastern China.

503 †*Archaeodrepanicus acutus* Jepson et al., 2013: Holotype, ex, CNU-NEU-LB2011004, an almost
504 complete insect preserved in lateral view, in a compressed fossil from Yixian Formation (Lower
505 Cretaceous, Barremian), Huangbanjigou locality, Liaoning Province, northeastern China (CNU).

506 †*Archaeodrepanicus* sp1.: 1♂, CNU-NEU-LB2011002, an almost complete insect preserved in
507 lateral view (CNU). (one paratype of *Archaeodrepanicus nuddsi*)

508 †*Archaeodrepanicus* sp2.: 1ex, CNU-NEU-LB2011005, an almost complete insect very poorly
509 preserved in lateral view, with wing venations invisible, in a compressed fossil from Yixian
510 Formation (Lower Cretaceous, Barremian), Huangbanjigou locality, Liaoning Province, north-
511 eastern China (CNU).

512 †*Clavifemora rotundata* Jepson et al., 2013: Holotype, ex, CNU-NEU-NN2011001, an almost
513 complete insect in lateral view, in a compressed fossil from Jiulongshan Formation (Middle
514 Jurassic, Bathonian), Daohugou, Inner Mongolia, China (CNU).

515 †*Karataumantispa carnaria* (Khramov, 2013): Holotype, ex, PIN 2239/1725, an almost complete
516 insect in lateral view, in a compressed fossil from Kazakhstan, South Kazakhstan Province,
517 Karatau locality, Upper Jurassic, Kimmeridgian-Oxfordian (PIN).

518 †*Longipronotum benmaddoxi* (Jepson, Khramov & Ohl, 2018): Holotype, ex, PIN 2784 1056, a
519 complete specimen in lateral view, with wing venations and raptorial forelegs preserved, in a
520 compressed fossil from Kazakhstan, South Kazakhstan Province, Karatau locality, Upper Jurassic,
521 Kimmeridgian-Oxfordian (PIN).

522 †*Ovalofemora abbottae* Jepson, Khramov & Ohl, 2018: Holotype, ex, PIN 2239 1727, a complete

523 specimen in lateral view, with wing venations and raptorial forelegs preserved, in a compressed
524 fossil from Kazakhstan, South Kazakhstan Province, Karatau locality, Upper Jurassic,
525 Kimmeridgian-Oxfordian (PIN).

526 †*Ovalofemora monstruosa* (Khramov, 2013): Holotype, ex, PIN 2066/1119, an incomplete insect
527 in lateral view, with wing venations and forelegs poorly preserved, in a compressed fossil from
528 Kazakhstan, South Kazakhstan Province, Karatau locality, Upper Jurassic, Kimmeridgian-
529 Oxfordian (PIN).

530 †*Sinomesomantispa microdentata* Jepson et al., 2013: Holotype, ex, CNU-NEU-2011006P/C, a
531 complete but poorly preserved specimen in lateral view, a compressed fossil from Yixian
532 Formation (Lower Cretaceous), Huangbanjigou locality, Liaoning Province, northeastern China
533 (CNU).

534 †*Mesomantispa sibirica*: Holotype, ex, No. 3064/2425 (part and counterpart) in the
535 Paleontological Institute, Moscow; basal half of a forewing; left bank of the Vitim River (9 km
536 below mouth of the River Baissa), Buryat Republic, East Siberia, Russia; Lower Cretaceous
537 (Neocomian), layer 31. 1ex, PIN 4210/5275, a well-preserved apical 2/3 of a forewing, collected
538 at Baissa, Russia (PIN).

539 †*Mesomantisporoides felixporcus* Li et al., 2023: Holotype, ♀, NIGP171728, amber piece polished
540 in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 29.02× 16.48 mm,
541 height about 6.71 mm (NIGP).

542 †*Habrosymphrosis xiai* Shi et al., 2019: 1♂, CAU-BA-WN-19002, amber piece also preserving a
543 hymenopteran and a dipteran; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with
544 length× width about 23.01× 15.05 mm, height about 7.37 mm (CAU). 1♀, NIGP171729, amber

545 piece also preserving six hymenopterans, a barklice, two dipteran and a hemipteran; it is polished
546 in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 27.51× 12.53 mm,
547 height about 4.53 mm (NIGP). 1 ex (terminalia broken), BXAM BA-NEU-0041, amber piece also
548 preserving two beetles; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with
549 length× width about 15.52× 8.56 mm, height about 2.55 mm (CAU).

550 †*Haplosymphrasites zouae* Lu et al., 2020: 1♀, NIGP171831, amber piece polished in the form of
551 an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 14.05× 9.83 mm, height about 2.97
552 mm (NIGP).

553 †*Parasymphrasites electrinus* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU002162, amber piece
554 polished in the form of a subtriangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 23.52×
555 13.68 mm, height about 5.43 mm (CAU).

556 †*Parvoasymphrasites aploneurus* Li, Lin, Liu & Wang, 2023: Holotype, ♂, NIGP171730, amber
557 piece polished in the form of a sub-rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about
558 10.67× 10.53 mm, height about 3.08 mm (NIGP).

559 †*Proplega evelynae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, 2023: Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-032, amber piece
560 polished in the form of a round, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 20.80× 17.50 mm,
561 height about 2.78 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♀, NIGP172730, amber piece polished in the form of a
562 quadrilateral, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 35.02× 27.94 mm, height about 9.28
563 mm (NIGP).

564 *Symphrasinae* sp.: 1♂, BXAM BA-NEU-033, amber piece polished in the form of an elliptical,
565 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 26.06× 16.90 mm, height about 8.18 mm (CAU).

566 *Plega dactylota* Rehn, 1939: 2♂2♀, USA, Texas, Jeff Davis Co. Davis Mountains Resort, 5800 ft,

567 30°37'42"N, 104°05'01"W, 20.V/01/13.V.2001, leg. D. G. Marqua [UV light trap, pinned] (CAU).
568 1♂, USA, Arizona, Madera Canyon, Pima County, 12.VIII.1966 [light trap, pinned] (CAU).
569 *Plega* spp.: 1♀1♂, USA, CA: Riverside Co. Corn Springs Cmpgrd 10 mi. S DesertCenter,
570 16.IX.2004, WLT, EE & KA Williams [pinned] (CAU). 2♀, USA, AZ, Santa Cruz Co., Kino
571 Springs, 30.VI.2002, leg. Kevin Williams [pinned] (CAU). 1♀, Mexico, B. Calif. Sur: 3.8 Km
572 Valle Perdido: 08.VI.1973, 23.679°N, 111.092°W, leg. E. L. Sleeper [pinned] (CAU).
573 *Trichoscelia* sp.: 1♂, Brazil, Manaus, 09.XII.2002 [Malaise trap, alcohol] (CAU).
574 †*Haplacantha robusta* Li et al., 2023: Holotype, ♂, NIGP171731, amber piece also preserving a
575 hymenopteran; it is polished in the form of rectangular, transparent cabochon, with length× width
576 about 16.70× 16.64 mm, height about 5.00 mm (NIGP).
577 †*Haplacantha tenuis* Li et al., 2023: Holotype, ♀, NIGP171732, amber piece polished in the form
578 of a semicircular, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.89× 17.83 mm, height about
579 8.02 mm (NIGP). Paratype, 1♂, NIGP171733, amber piece also preserving a dipteran and a beetle;
580 it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 23.68×
581 16.04 mm, height about 5.40 mm (NIGP).
582 †*Haplacantha* spp.: 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-0042, amber piece polished in the form of an elliptical,
583 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 16.00× 6.96 mm, height about 3.36 mm (CAU).
584 lex (terminalia broken), NIGP171734, amber piece polished in the form of a quadrilateral,
585 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 15.64× 10.36 mm, height about 6.91 mm (NIGP).
586 †*Doratomantispa arcimaculata* Li et al., 2022: Holotype, ♂, NIGP 177985, amber piece also
587 preserving a dipteran; it is polished in the form of a long ovoid transparent cabochon, with length×
588 width about 30.32× 14.53 mm, height about 6.42 mm (NIGP).

589 †*Doratomantispa ares* Li et al., 2022: Holotype, ♂, NIGP 173084, amber piece also preserving a
590 dipteran, a parasitoid wasp and two psocids; it is polished in the form of an ovoid transparent
591 cabochon, with length× width about 23.61× 16.78 mm, height about 7.44 mm (NIGP).

592 †*Doratomantispa gaoyuhe* Li et al. 2022: Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19003, amber piece
593 polished in the form of a long ovoid transparent cabochon, with length× width about 22.92× 15.20
594 mm, height about 6.26 mm (CAU).

595 †*Doratomantispa pubescens* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ex, EMTG BU001759, amber piece
596 polished in the form of an elliptical transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.48× 16.61
597 mm, height about 6.42 mm (CAU).

598 †*Doratomantispa yumeiyingae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, 2022: Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-007, amber
599 piece polished in the form of a long ovoid transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.11×
600 13.84 mm, height about 5.27 mm (CAU).

601 †*Doratomantispa zhangwenjuni* Zhuo, Li & Liu, 2022: Holotype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-005,
602 amber piece polished in the form of a subrectangular transparent cabochon, with length× width
603 about 26.60× 15.75 mm, height about 7.88 mm (CAU).

604 †*Doratomantispa zhangzhiqiae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, 2022: Holotype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-006, amber
605 piece polished in the form of a long elliptical transparent cabochon, with length× width about
606 17.44× 13.63 mm, height about 8.57 mm (CAU).

607 †*Doratomantispa zhuozhengmingi* Zhuo, Li & Liu, 2022: Holotype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-002,
608 amber piece polished in the form of a long elliptical transparent cabochon, with length× width
609 about 37.72× 10.40 mm, height about 6.40 mm (CAU).

610 †*Doratomantispa* sp.1: 1♂, NIGP18115, amber piece polished in the form of a long elliptical

611 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 43.34× 32.60 mm, height about 8.17 mm (NIGP).

612 †*Doratomantispa* sp.2: 1♀, BXAM BA-NEU-40, amber piece polished in the form of a long
613 elliptical transparent cabochon, with length× width about 26.76× 21.39 mm, height about 10.04
614 mm (CAU).

615 †*Doratomantispa* sp.3: 1♂, BXAM BA-NEU-41, amber piece polished in the form of a long
616 elliptical transparent cabochon, with length× width about 15.61× 10.20 mm, height about 3.32 mm
617 (CAU).

618 †*Paradoxomantispa jiaxiaoe* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♀, CAM BA-0015, amber piece polished
619 in the form of an elliptical transparent cabochon, with length× width about 21.30× 15.13 mm,
620 height about 6.78 mm (CAU).

621 †*Paradoxomantispa mahaiyingae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, 2022: Holotype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-008 &
622 Paratype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-009, amber piece also preserving two buprestids, ten dipterans, an
623 elaterid, a tenebrionid and four parasitoid wasps; it is polished in the form of an ovoid transparent
624 cabochon, with length× width about 45.05× 36.90 mm, height about 12.81 mm (CAU).

625 †*Acanthomantispa grandis* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ex, NIGP 173085, amber piece polished in
626 the form of a subrectangular transparent cabochon, with length× width about 18.76× 4.84 mm,
627 height about 12.81 mm (NIGP).

628 †*Acanthomantispa immaculata* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♂ EMTG BU001408, amber piece also
629 preserving a hemipteran; it is polished in the form of an elliptical transparent cabochon, with
630 length× width about 43.42× 28.80 mm, height about 7.66 mm (CAU).

631 †*Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU002131, amber piece also
632 preserving a beetle; it is polished in the form of a semicircular transparent cabochon, with length×

633 width about 28.46× 15.23 mm, height about 11.45 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♀, EMTG BU002136,
634 amber piece also preserving two dipterans; it is polished in the form of a subtriangular transparent
635 cabochon, with length× width about 33.32× 14.26 mm, height about 7.38 mm (CAU). Paratype,
636 1♀, EMTG BU002270, amber piece polished in the form of a nearly quadrangular transparent
637 cabochon, with length× width about 23.34× 21.26 mm, height about 9.11 mm (CAU). 1♂, BXAM
638 BA-NEU-034, amber piece also preserving a dipteran; it is polished in the form of a round
639 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 22.91× 22.76 mm, height about 8.82 mm (CAU).
640 1ex, EMTG BU002302, amber piece also preserving a snakefly larva, a cockroach, two beetles,
641 four ants and many dipterans; it is polished in the form of an elliptical transparent cabochon, with
642 length× width about 58.46× 41.27 mm, height about 24.36 mm (CAU).

643 †*Acanthomantispa* sp.: 1♀, NIGP171834, amber piece polished in the form of an elliptical
644 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 34.72× 19.91 mm, height about 4.31 mm (NIGP).

645 †*Dicranomantispa zhouae* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-ZM-19003, amber piece
646 polished in the form of a raindrop-like transparent cabochon, with length× width about 30.93×
647 23.28 mm, height about 7.78 mm (CAU).

648 †*Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-LX-19004, amber piece
649 polished in the form of an ovoid transparent cabochon, with length× width about 26.70× 15.21
650 mm, height about 5.17 mm (CAU). 1ex, NIGP171734, mber piece polished in the form of an
651 ovoid transparent cabochon, with length× width about 55.33× 37.04 mm, height about 19.11 mm
652 (NIGP).

653 *Allomantispa tibetana* Liu et al., 2015: Holotype, ♂, Xizang Autonomous Region, Medog County,
654 80 K, 1000 m, 08.VIII.2012, 29°39'59.7"N, 95°29'45.4"E, leg. Xiaodong Yang [pinned] (CAU).

- 655 *Allomantispa coniprocesa* Li et al., 2020: Holotype, ♂, China: Yunnan, Xishuangbanna, Mengla
656 County, 1100 m, 25–27.IX.2017, Chao Wu [pinned] (CAU). Paratype, 1♀, China: Yunnan,
657 Xishuangbanna, Mengla County, 1100 m, 25–27.IX.2017, Chao Wu [alcohol] (CAU).
- 658 *Ditaxis biseriata* (Westwood, 1852): 1♂, Australia, Eprapah Creek, Redland Bay, 22.X.1974, leg.
659 M. DeBaar & M. Hockey [pinned] (CAU). 1♂, Australia, Mt. Tamborine, 02.XI.1977, leg. R.
660 Wylie & M. DeBaar [pinned]. 1♀, Australia, Brisbane, Long Pocket, 04.IX.1980, M. DeBaar
661 [pinned] (CAU).
- 662 *Drepanicus chrysopinus* Brauer, 1867: 1♂, Chile, Nuble 5.6 km. N. Cobequecura, 21.II.1964, leg.
663 E. Krahmer [pinned] (CAU).
- 664 *Drepanicus moulti* (Navás, 1910): 1♀, Chile, Nuble 5.6 km. N. Cobequecura, 29.I.1967, leg. L.
665 Stange [pinned] (CAU).
- 666 *Gerstaeckerella chilensis* (Hagen, 1859): 1♂, Chile, 5m. NE. Papudo, P. Aconcagua, 500ft,
667 12.XI.1967 [pinned] (CAU). 1♀, Chile, Salto Valpo, leg. P. Reed [pinned] (CAU).
- 668 *Theristria basalis* Banks, 1939: 1♂, Australia, Western Australia, Golden Bay, 2.426°S, 115.771°E,
669 19.XI.2008, leg. S. L. Winterton & S. D. Gaimari [pinned] (CAU).
- 670 *Theristria cardaleae* Lambkin, 1986: 1♂, Australia, N.T., Arnhem Land, 18.VIII.2007,
671 12°25.779°S, 136°49.616°E, leg. S. L. Winterton [pinned] (CAU).
- 672 *Theristria delicatula* (Westwood, 1852): 1♂, Australia, NSW, W ambelong Ck, W arrumbungle
673 N.P., 31.323°S, 149.027°E, 21.I.2009, leg. S. L. Winterton [pinned] (CAU).
- 674 *Theristria discolor* (Westwood, 1852): 1♂, Australia, Western Australia, Golden Bay, 32.426°S,
675 115.771°E, 19.XI.2008, leg. S. L. Winterton & S. D. Gaimari [pinned] (CAU). 1♀ 1ex, Australia,
676 Danbulla, 01.XI.1976, leg. R. A. Yule & F. R. Wylie [pinned] (CAU).

677 *Theristria imperfecta* Lambkin, 1986: 1♂, Australia, NSW, Namadgi NP, Boboyan Rd, 27k S
678 Namadgi NP Visitor Center, 35°43'46"S, 148°59'47"E, 01.X.2017 leg. Xuankun Li [alcohol]
679 (CAU).

680 *Theristria pallida* Lambkin, 1986: 1♂, Australia, N.T., Arnhem Land, 18.VIII.2007, 12°25.778'S,
681 136°49.616'E, leg. S. L. Winterton [pinned] (CAU).

682 *Theristria stigma* (Esben-Petersen, 1929): 2♂3♀, Australia, NSW, Dorrigo, 23.XI.2014,
683 30°23'40"S, 152°44'45"E, 540 m, leg. Xuankun Li [alcohol] (CAU).

684 *Theristria storeyi* Lambkin, 1986: 1♂, Australia, Spear Creek, 8.5 km N of Palmer River x-ing,
685 16°03'S, 144°48'E, 26.XII.1984, G. & A. Daniels [pinned] (CAU). 6♀, Australia, McLeod River
686 x-ing, W of Mount Carbine, 16°29'S, 144°59'E, 27.XII.1984, leg. G. & A. Daniels [pinned]
687 (CAU). 1♀, Australia, Grass Tree Pocket Rd nr. Shiptons Flat, 01.I.1981, leg. G. & A. Daniels
688 [pinned] (CAU). 1♀, Australia, 10 km N Ellis Beach, 28.XII.1980, leg. G. & A. Daniels [pinned]
689 (CAU).

690 *Calomantispa venusta* Lambkin, 1986: 3♀, Australia, South Black Range 9-14.5 km, E.
691 Hoskinstown, S.E. NSW., 1130 m, 16/21/27.XI.2003, leg. D. J. Ferguson [pinned] (CAU).

692 *Campanacella javanica* (Westwood, 1852): 1♂, China, Tibet, Beibeng, Gelin, 22.VIII.2020,
693 Yuchen Zheng. [alcohol] (CAU)

694 *Campion callosus* Lambkin, 1986: 1♀, Australia, NSW, Tom Groggin Kosciuszko, 36°33'08"S,
695 148°7'31"E, 540 m, leg. Qiang Xie [alcohol] (CAU).

696 *Campion rubellus* Navás, 1914: 1♂, Australia, NSW, Ring-Gai NP, 33°34'54"S, 151°17'57"E,
697 200 m, 16.XII.2014, Qiang Xie [alcohol] (CAU). 1♀, Australia, NSW, Tom Groggin Kosciuszko,
698 36°33'08"S, 148°7'31"E, 540 m, leg. Qiang Xie [alcohol] (CAU).

699 *Campion tenuistriga* (Gerstaecker, 1885): 1♀, 35°16'28.5"S, 147°4'15.4"E, NSW, The Rock
700 Nature Reserve, 12.Feb.2016, leg. X. Li, D. Yeates & A. Landford [alcohol] (CAU). 1♂, Australia,
701 SA Witjira NP, Mt Dare Hotel, 26°4'12"S, 135°14'55"E, 19.III.2017, leg. D. Yates, A. Landford, Y.
702 Su, X. Li, J Lumbers & Irwin [alcohol] (CAU).

703 *Cercomantispa* sp.: 1♂, Madagascar, Ranomafana National Park, 24.XII.2016, Lihu [alcohol]
704 (CAU).

705 *Climaciella* sp.: 1♀, Barren county, Beaver Trail pk., VII.1976, Kentucky (CAU).

706 *Euclimacia badia* Okamoto, 1910: 1♂, China, Guangdong, Nanling, 28.IX.2017 [alcohol] (CAU).

707 *Eumantispa harmandi* Okamoto, 1910: 3♂2♀, China, Sichuan, Yaan, Baoxing County,
708 Fengtongzhai, 29.VIII.2018, leg. Yingqi Liu & Zhuo Chen [alcohol] (CAU).

709 *Eumantispa pseudoharmandi* Yang & Liu, 2010: Holotype, ♂, China, Fujian, Dazhulan,
710 22.VII.1986, leg. Jiashe Wang & Yi Jiang [pinned] (CUA).

711 *Mantispa styriaca* (Poda, 1761): 1♂1♀, China, Yanqing, Beijing, 08.VI.1960 [alcohol] (CAU).

712 *Necyla shirozui* (Nakahara, 1961): 1♂, China, Fujian, Longyan, Wan'an, Mt. Liantaishan,
713 15.V.2019, 1100 m, leg. Yuchen Zheng [alcohol] (CAU). 2♂2♀, China, Longyan, Xinluo, Gorge
714 Jiangshandaxiagu, 28.III.2019, 600-800 m, leg. Yuchen Zheng [alcohol] (CAU). 1♀, China, Fujian,
715 Longyan, Xinluo, Dachi, Jiuliyangcun Village, 800-900 m, 14.V.2019, leg. Yuchen Zheng [alcohol]
716 (CAU).

717 *Necyla flavacoxa* (Yang, 1999): 2♂2♀, China, Guangdong, Longmen, Mt. Nankunshan, 12-
718 14.VI.2018 [alcohol] (CAU).

719 *Tuberontha insignis* (Navás, 1914): 5♂6♀, China, Yunnan, Xishuangbanna, Mt Jiluoshan,
720 Bapozhai, 12.VII.2019, Xiaoxiao Yong [alcohol] (CAU).

721

722

723

724 **Supplementary Appendix 3. Characters Used for Phylogeny and Phylomorphospace**

725 **Analyses**

726

727 **Head**

728 1. Hypostomal bridge posterior to the submentum:

729 (0) absent (Supplementary Fig. S14n; Li et al. (2022): figs. 5f, 17f);

730 (1) present (Supplementary Fig. S18h-i; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 2c, d).

731 This structure is a posterior closure of the head between hypostomal sulci and below posterior

732 tentorial pits, found in all extant and fossil symphrasines.

733 2. Toruli (i.e., antennal foramens), position:

734 (0) located at the level near the top of eyes' inner margin (broad and elongated frons)

735 (Supplementary Fig. S14d-f; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 18a);

736 (1) located at the level near the middle of eyes' inner margin (narrow and short frons)

737 (Supplementary Figs. S14h, i, S20d, f, h; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 18b-e; Li et al.

738 (2022): figs. 12d, 15c).

739 3. Frontal horn:

740 (0) absent;

741 (1) present (Supplementary Fig. S15c, g).

742 The horn-like structure on frons rarely occurs in males of some neuropterans, e.g., *Neosemidalis*

743 (Meinander (1972): figs. 99-107) some species of *Meleoma* (Tauber 1969) and *Ungla bolivari*

744 (Banks) (Tauber et al. (2017): fig. 18), while it is surprisingly present in females of

745 †*Cornoberotha anomala* (double horns) and †*Cornoberotha monogona* Yang et al. (single horn)
746 (an autapomorphic character of †*Cornoberotha*).

747 4. Ocular plane in frontal view:

748 (0) not anteriorly curved inwards (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 18a-b);

749 (1) anteriorly curved inwards (Supplementary Figs. S13d, f, h, S19l, n; Ardila-Camacho et al.
750 (2021): fig. 18c-e).

751 The ocular plane is located at the compound eye base surrounding the optic neuropils and
752 ocular diaphragm (Ferris (1940); Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021)). †*Archaeodrepanicus acutus*
753 and most members the mantispid clade 2 (M2) (†*Aragomantispa*, †*Haplacantha*,
754 *Calomantispinae*, †*Doratomantispinae*, *Drepanicinae* and *Mantispinae*) share ocular plane
755 anteriorly curved inwards. In other mantispoids this plane varies from being straight to concave
756 inwards, which is difficult to be recognized especially in fossil specimens, so we do not define
757 them further to avoid ambiguity.

758 5. Mouthpart, position:

759 (0) external, with long mandible (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 18);

760 (1) sunken into concavity of head, with short mandible (Aspöck and Hynd (1995): fig. 5).

761 The former character state is very common in Neuroptera, and the latter is a specialized and
762 reduced case found in Dilaridae, *Naizema*, *Trichoberotha* and *Tanzanberotha* (Aspöck and
763 Nemeschkal 1998), (Aspöck and Randolph 2014).

764 6. Rod-like labial terminal palpi (elongated and basally slightly swollen):

765 (0) absent (Supplementary Figs. S14n, S17f);

766 (1) present (Supplementary Fig. S20d, h).

767 This character occurs in Calomantispinae, Drepanicinae and Mantispinae, while other
768 mantispoids share labial terminal palpus with base much broader than its acute apex variable to
769 different degrees, similar to a “raindrop”.

770 7. Length of antenna:

771 (0) about 0.5-1× length of forewing, but shorter than its entire length (Supplementary Figs. S9b,
772 S10b, S11c);

773 (1) shortened, shorter than 0.5× length of forewing (Supplementary Figs. S8c, e, f, h, S11i-l,
774 S13l-o); (2) elongated, longer than forewing (Yang et al. (2020): figs. 3A, 9A, 14A, 21A;
775 Supplementary Fig. S1b).

776 In Mantispoidea, the extremely long antenna (state 2) is only shared by †*Ansoberotha*,
777 †*Cornoberotha* and †*Dolichoberotha*, and the shortened antenna (state 1) is generally found in
778 Mantispidae (including Symphrasinae), but surprisingly occurs in †*Osmyloberotha* and
779 †*Xiaoberotha* as well. The moderately long antenna (state 0) in remaining taxa may be the
780 groundplan of Mantispoidea.

781 8. Male antenna type:

782 (0) filiform;

783 (1) moniliform;

784 (3) pectinate;

785 (4) clavate.

786 9. Female antenna type:

787 (0) filiform;

788 (1) moniliform;

789 (3) clavate.

790 State (0) and (1) are difficult to determine in fossil, due to the deformation possibly resulting
791 from the taphonomic processes, so evaluating the deformation degree of specimens and
792 comparing its flagellomere shape with extant and other well-preserved fossil mantispoids are
793 the means for us to make a judgment. For example, the gaps among flagellomeres of the
794 antenna in †*Osmyloberotha* are neither narrow or wide, confusing us to distinguish its definite
795 type (Supplementary Fig. S8a-h). According to the comparison that the wide gaps among
796 flagellomeres (like moniliform type) are usually found in the specimens laterally compressed
797 seriously and more easily occurs distad the antenna (Supplementary Fig. S8a, f, h), herein we
798 accept the narrow-gap antenna (filiform type) as the normal state for †*Osmyloberotha*.

799 10. Scape:

800 (0) 2× length of pedicel;

801 (1) 3× length of pedicel;

802 (2) 4-5× length of pedicel;

803 (3) over 6× length of pedicel (Supplementary Fig. S15a, e).

804 The long scape ($\geq 4\times$ length of pedicel) is found in Berothinae, †*Ansoberotha*, †*Cornoberotha*,
805 †*Dolichoberotha* and †Paraberothinae, but never occurs in all dipteromantispids and mantispids.

806 11. Scape distally:

807 (0) barely swollen, nearly as wide as its basal portion;

808 (1) swollen distinctly (Supplementary Figs. S17e, g, S19g, S20d, f, h), distinctly broader than
809 its basal portion.

810 12. Shape of basal flagellomeres pendicularly:

811 (0) barely compressed (from nearly once to 1.5 times as long as wide);

812 (1) distinctly compressed (distinctly wider than long (about 1.5 times to twice as wide as long).

813 13. Ocelli:

814 (0) present;

815 (1) absent.

816 Ocelli are common in Megloptera and Raphidioptera, but in Neuroptera, only Osmylidae bears
817 three ocelli on the supra-antennal area.

818 14. Vertex:

819 (0) domed;

820 (1) flattened (Supplementary Figs. S19o, S20a-c, h).

821 Lambkin (1986a) categorized the doming vertex into six degrees in lateral view: “strongly
822 domed”, “distinctly domed”, “moderately domed”, “slightly domed”, “very slightly domed” and
823 “not domed”. However, considering the continuous variations from “distinctly domed” to
824 “slightly domed” and the poor preservations of fossil species, their boundaries sometimes seem
825 unclear and difficult to be determined accurately. Here, to avoid ambiguity, we sort out
826 “strongly domed” to “slightly domed” as “domed vertex” (Lambkin (1986a): figs. 11-15), and
827 “very slightly domed” to “not domed” as “flattened vertex” (Lambkin (1986a): fig. 16). These
828 two states can be easily distinguished by whether the domed and rounded vertex can be detected
829 in lateral view or not (the flattened vertex always concealed by the enlarged compound eyes).

830 15. Vertexal tubercles (the small setose processes located on the medial surface of supra-antennal
831 area and posterolateral surface of vertex):

832 (0) absent;

833 (1) present.

834 16. Number of tubercles:

835 (0) three (one anteromedial tubercle and two posterolateral tubercles. Tjeder (1959): 223; Liu et
836 al. (2017): fig. 5c);

837 (1) two (the anteromedial one absent. Supplementary Figs. S19c, m, n, S20a-c); (2) reduced
838 (without distinct tubercles on vertex, but with some tufts of setae located on the same places of
839 tubercles. Aspöck and Aspöck (1997): fig. 34); (3) fused (found in *Mucroberotha* (Aspöck and
840 Mansell 1994), (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021). Some previous authors also considered the large
841 domed supra-antennal area as the anteromedial tubercle (MacLeod and Adams 1967), but in
842 some berothids, this area is domed and bears a tuft of setae anteromedially (reduced tubercle),
843 also in general equipped with two posterolateral tubercles (if present) (e.g., *Lekrugeria*; Aspöck
844 and Aspöck (1985): figs. 20, 22). Therefore, the domed supra-antennal area is not considered to
845 be homologous to the tubercle herein. Character 14 is dependent on character 13.

846 17. Coronal suture (the median longitudinal suture on vertex):

847 (0) distinct (Supplementary Fig. S20d, f; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): figs. 2a, b, 18c, d);

848 (1) indistinct (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 18a, e).

849 18. Head hair generally:

850 (0) long, not shortened (Supplementary Figs. S14a, c, S15s, S16a);

851 (1) shortened (Supplementary Figs. S17-S20).

852 Body hair is general long, soft and erected in Berothidae and Rhachiberothidae, while generally
853 shortened, sometimes thickened or flattened in †Dipteromantispidae, Mantispidae (including
854 Symphrasinae). This variation can be easily detected on the head, thorax and wing margin.

855 Notably, there is also a distinct tendency to shortening body hair further in Mantispidae, whose
856 body hair in the derived lineages is usually much shorter than in the primitive lineages, e.g., hair
857 much shorter or sometimes even nearly glabrous in †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa*,
858 †*Pectispina*, †*Psilomantispa*, Drepanicinae, Calomantispinae and Mantispinae. In the present
859 study, we focus the length of hair on head, prothorax, pterothorax and wing margin respectively,
860 regarding them as four independent characters.

861

862 **Thorax**

863 19. Pronotal scales (scale-like setae):

864 (0) absent;

865 (1) present (Aspöck and Randolph 2014).

866 The absence of scales is plesiomorphic in Neuroptera, and the scales (single, tufts, or brush-like)
867 occur in *Spiroberotha* (scales on the meso- and metathorax, *Podallea* (scale brush on the on the
868 pronotum of the male of several species), or *Spermophorella* (scale brush on the pronotum of
869 the female of some species) (Aspöck and Nemeschkal 1998), and it is common to observe wing
870 scales in Berothinae. Herein we focus scales on prothorax, pterothorax and wings respectively,
871 regarding them as three independent characters.

872 20. Pronotum shape:

873 (0) shield-shaped, posteroventrally not fused (Supplementary Figs. S14k-m, S15m, S16e, f,
874 S17k, o, p, S18h-o; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 20a-d);

875 (1) tubular, posteroventrally fused (Supplementary Figs. S19d, e, m, S20m; Ardila-Camacho et
876 al. (2021): fig. 20e-j).

877 Shield-shaped pronotum should be the groundplan of all neuropterans, ventrally open, bearing
878 several sclerites (e.g., posterior cervical sclerite, episternum, epimeron, postfurcasternum etc.)
879 and inserted by procoxae. In †*Archaeodrepanicus acutus*, †*Aragomantispa*, †*Haplacantha*,
880 †*Doratomantispinae*, *Drepanicinae*, *Calomantispinae* and *Mantispinae*, pronotum fused
881 ventrally posteriorly the insertion of procoxae as a tube-like structure, mostly strongly elongated.

882 21. Ratio length/width of prothorax (pronotum):

- 883 (0) short, at most twice as long as wide;
- 884 (1) compressed, nearly two times as long as wide;
- 885 (2) 1.5 times as long as wide;
- 886 (3) 2-2.5 times as long as wide;
- 887 (4) moderately long, about 3-4 times as long as wide;
- 888 (5) extremely long, over 4.5 times as long as wide.

889 All shield-shaped and certain tubular pronotum (e.g., those in †*Archaeodrepanicus acutus*,
890 †*Haplacantha*, *Drepanicus*) are short, nearly 1-1.5 times as long as wide, but it is very common
891 in Mantispidae to observe very long pronotum, e.g., over pronotum over three times as long as
892 wide occurring in *Doratomantispinae*, *Drepanicinae* and *Calomantispinae* and *Mantispinae*,
893 which is mainly caused by elongating the tubular portion of pronotum.

894 22. Maculae:

- 895 (0) absent;
- 896 (1) present (Li et al. (2020b): fig. 4I-L; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 19c-e).

897 Maculae are always present as a pair of shagreened or smooth and glossy spots or small humps
898 on the base of pronotal swollen portion (Lambkin 1986a), found in *Calomantispinae*,

899 Drepanicinae and Mantispinae.

900 23. A pair of setose patches on male pronotum:

901 (0) absent;

902 (1) present (Li et al. (2020b): figs. 4I-J, 4L).

903 This patches usually bear dense, long and thickened setae anteriorly maculae, occurring in males
904 of *Allomantispa* and representing an autapomorphic character of this genus.

905 24. Pronotal furrows:

906 (0) present;

907 (1) absent.

908 25. Number of furrows:

909 (0) two (Supplementary Fig. S14j, k, p);

910 (1) one.

911 This character is dependent on character 24.

912 Pronotal furrows refer to the transverse narrow grooves on the smooth pronotum, bilaterally
913 deeply depressed in general, commonly found in Dilaridae, Berothidae, Rhachiberothidae and
914 †*Mesomantispoides*. In some members of Mantispidae (including Symphrasinae), the dorsum of
915 pronotum is unevenly raised, leading to two or more broad grooves (Supplementary Figs. S18h,
916 l, S20l, m), which is different from the pronotal furrows.

917 26. Prothorax:

918 (0) not elongate posteriorly insertion of procoxa (Supplementary Figs. S14m, s, S16f, k, S17c, k;
919 Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 20a, b);

920 (1) slightly elongate posteriorly insertion of procoxa (making procoxa insert near middle of

921 prothorax) (Supplementary Figs. S18f, h-m, S19d, e; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 20c, d);
922 (2) strongly elongate posteriad insertion of procoxa (making procoxa inserting at anterior apex
923 of prothorax) (Supplementary Figs. S19j, m, o, 20m; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 20e-j).

924 The procoxae generally located near the posterior end of the prothorax in Neuroptera (prothorax
925 not elongate posteriad) represents a plesiomorphic state, shared by Berothidae,
926 Rhachiberothidae and †Dipteromantispidae in Mantispoidea. Prothorax in some
927 mesomantispinaes (e.g., †*Clavifemora*, †*Longipronotum*, †*Ovalofemora* etc.), Symphrasinae
928 and †*Mesomantispoides* has shield-shaped pronotum, but slightly elongates posteriad the
929 insertion of procoxa (large distance between postfurcasternum and the procoxal insertion; the
930 reason why the coxal insertion approximately at the middle of prothorax). This slightly
931 elongated prothorax also occurs in †*Archaeodrepanicus acutus* and †*Haplacantha*, however
932 with a tubular pronotum. †*Argaomantispa*, Calomantispinae, †Doratomantispinae, Drepanicinae
933 and Mantispinae share the strongly elongated prothorax mainly by elongating the tubular
934 portion of pronotum, making the procoxa insert at anterior apex of prothorax. It is noteworthy
935 that the elongated prothorax also makes the postfurcasternum far away from epimeron and
936 episternum (Supplementary Figs. S18h-m, S19e, S20m). The strongly elongated prothorax of
937 †*Longipronotum* is the shield-shaped pronotum. Considering the position of the procoxal
938 insertion and the poor preservation of the type specimen, herein we interpret the prothorax in
939 this genus is slightly elongated posteriad, as seen in other mesomantispines (Supplementary Fig.
940 S12i; Jepson et al. (2018): fig. 1C).

941 27. Elongated portion of tubular pronotum:

942 (0) smooth;

- 943 (1) rugose (usually occurring on lateral and ventral surfaces of the pronotal tubular portion);
944 (2) with many deep circular grooves (e.g., *Austroclimaciella*, *Campanacella*, *Eumantispa* etc.).

945 28. Elongated portion of tubular pronotum dorsally:

- 946 (0) nearly flattened;
947 (1) raised strongly (e.g., *Climaciella*, *Euclimacia*, *Tuberontha* etc.).

948 Characters 27-28 are dependent on character 26. The highly morphological variations of surface
949 of elongate pronotal tubular portion, such as rugose, unevenly raised surface, circular grooves
950 etc., having important taxonomic and phylogenetic values.

951 29. Area of procoxal insertion:

- 952 (0) barely expanded;
953 (1) distinctly expanded (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 19c-e). The narrow procoxal
954 insertion area is usually observed in the taxa with the cursorial foreleg or weakly incrassate
955 raptorial appendage, such as Berothidae, Rhachiberothidae and †Dipteromantispidae. In
956 †Mesomantispinae, Symphrasinae and †*Haplacantha*, this area is still narrow but broader than
957 the former three families, with the presence of very stout raptorial forelegs. The distinctly
958 expanded procoxal insertion area develops very well in most mantispids with the long tubular
959 pronotum (distinctly more than twice as long as wide) possibly evolving together with their
960 more strengthened raptorial forelegs, but in †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa*, †*Pectispina*
961 and †*Psilomantispa*, it turns narrow as in †Mesomantispinae and Symphrasinae, with the
962 reduction of their raptorial forelegs to different degrees.

963 30. Precoxal bridge:

964 (0) absent (Supplementary Figs. S14k-m, S16f, S18j, k, n-o; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig.
965 5d);

966 (1) present (Supplementary Figs. S17n, p, S19e, k, S20i, j; Li et al. (2022): fig. 13b).

967 This structure refers to the sclerite connecting the basisternum and the episternum on the
968 anteroventral portion of prothorax, close to the anterior margin of procoxal insertions, generally
969 observed in †*Mesomantispoidea*s and tubular-pronotum mantispids, which may assist in
970 strengthening the raptorial system.

971 31. Postfurcasternum (the prothoracic sclerite located between the posterolateral corners of the
972 pronotum and the mesothoracic spiracle):

973 (0) absent;

974 (1) present.

975 32. Development degree of postfurcasternum:

976 (0) well-developed (Supplementary Figs. S11f, i-o, S16j, k, S17c, k, S19e; Ardila-Camacho et
977 al. (2021): fig. 20a-d);

978 (1) reduced, narrow (Supplementary Fig. S20k, m; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 20e, g, j;
979 Li et al. (2022): fig. 17c).

980 33. Fusing condition of postfurcasternum:

981 (0) separate (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 20a, b);

982 (1) fused (Supplementary Fig. S18n, o; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 5c, d).

983 Characters 32, 33 are dependent on character 31.

984 The postfurcasternum was interpreted as “posterior piece of the pronotum” by Ferris (1940) and

985 Lambkin (1986a) or “heminota” by Lu et al. (2020), and then was interpreted as homology to

986 the homonymous sclerites of *Raphidia* sp. in the sense of Crampton (1928) by Ardila-Camacho
987 et al. (2021). It seems to represent an autapomorphy of raptorial Mantispoidea (Ardila-Camacho
988 et al. 2021), while all berothids lack this structure. The presence of postfurcasterum should be
989 associated with the strength of the raptorial system but unrelated to the elongation of prothorax,
990 because it also occurred in Rhachiberothidae and †Dipteromantispidae whose prothorax not
991 elongated posteriad. The elongated pronotum is strengthened in *Plega* by the enlargement and
992 fusion of the postfurcasternum, while in tubular-pronotum mantispids usually by the pronotal
993 posteroventrally fusing portion with paired reduced and narrow postfurcasterna.

994 34. Prothorax bearing setae generally:

995 (0) long, not shortened;

996 (1) shortened.

997 35. Prothoracic setae:

998 (0) inserted on a smooth base;

999 (1) inserted on a prominent base (sensu “pedicellate” in Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021)).

1000 36. Fluffy membranous sac anteriorly mesothorax:

1001 (0) absent;

1002 (1) present (Supplementary Fig. S16q-s).

1003 The possible autapomorphic character of †*Dicranoberothena*

1004 37. Meso- and metathoracic scales:

1005 (0) absent;

1006 (1) present.

1007 38. Anterolateral processes on mesoscutum (i.e., the acutely produced anterolateral corners of the

- 1008 mesoscutum in Lambkin (1986a));
- 1009 (0) absent;
- 1010 (1) present (an autapomorphy of Mantispinae, see Lambkin (1986a): fig. 19, 20).
- 1011 39. Metathorax:
- 1012 (0) developed as mesothorax;
- 1013 (1) strongly reduced (namely much narrower than mesothorax, with reduced nota and pleura; an
- 1014 autapomorphy of in †Dipteromantispidae).
- 1015 40. Pterothoracic hair generally:
- 1016 (0) long, not shortened;
- 1017 (1) shortened.
- 1018
- 1019 **Legs**
- 1020 41. Foreleg:
- 1021 (0) cursorial;
- 1022 (1) raptorial.
- 1023 42. Procoxa:
- 1024 (0) not elongated;
- 1025 (1) elongated. Actually, the procoxa of Neuropterida is more or less elongated, compared with
- 1026 meso- and metacoxa, while the elongating degree in raptorial Mantispoidea is much more than
- 1027 in others.
- 1028 43. Procoxal proximal surface:
- 1029 (0) without;

1030 (1) with an annular groove (Supplementary Fig. S29s). The annular groove, or the ring-shaped
1031 groove ((Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021)) or transverse sulcus (Lambkin 1986a), is located at the
1032 proximal 1/3 or 1/4 of coxa length, only occurring in Mantispinae.

1033 44. Procoxal posterodistal surface:

1034 (0) smooth;

1035 (1) with a longitudinal groove (sensu “longitudinally impressed distally” in Lambkin (1986a),
1036 found in Drepanicinae. Supplementary Figs. S28a, g, m, S29a, g);

1037 (2) flattened (shared by Mantispinae and some species of *Theristria*. Supplementary Fig. S29s).

1038 45. Length of procoxal distal longitudinal groove on its posterior surface:

1039 (0) along 1/3 length of procoxa (Supplementary Fig. S29a, g);

1040 (1) along 1/2-2/3 length of procoxa (Supplementary Fig. S28a, g, m).

1041 This character is dependent on character 44.

1042 46. Procoxal specialized setae:

1043 (0) absent;

1044 (1) present (an autapomorphic character of †*Enigmadipteromantispa*, see Azar et al. (2020): figs.
1045 2D, 4C).

1046 47. Profemur:

1047 (0) not incrassate;

1048 (1) incrassate.

1049 The degree of incrassation reflects the strength, thickness (in ventral view) and width (in lateral
1050 view) of profemur. For all berotherids and †*Psilomantispa*, profemur is tubular as all other
1051 cursorial neuropterans; the feeble and slender profemur is commonly found in rhachiberotherids,

1052 some dipteromantispids and those mantispids with reduced raptorial appendages, e.g.,
1053 †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa* and †*Pectispina*. most mantispids (including
1054 Symphrasinae) share the strong, thickened and broader profemur.

1055 48. Incrassate profemur in lateral view:

1056 (0) broadened near base (apex narrower than base; Supplementary Figs. S22d, S23n, S24h,
1057 S26g, j);

1058 (1) broadened near proximal 1/3-1/2 length of profemur (apex nearly as broad as base;
1059 Supplementary Fig. S25a-n);

1060 (2) concave medially (an autapomorphy of †*Dicranoberotha*; Supplementary Figs. S23h).

1061 49. Ventral margin proximad broadening point:

1062 (0) curved (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 22a-e);

1063 (1) straight (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 22f-h).

1064 The ventral margin of profemur in lateral view curved distally and abruptly turning straight
1065 towards the base at the broadening point in Mantispinae, while in other raptorial mantispoids,
1066 this margin generally curves more smoothly proximad the profemoral broadening point.

1067 Characters 48, 49 are dependent on character 47.

1068 50. Base of profemur in lateral view:

1069 (1) truncate;

1070 (2) acute (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 22f-h).

1071 51. Protochanteral blunt process:

1072 (0) absent;

1073 (1) present (an autapomorphic character of *Anchieta*. (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 25a).

1074 52. Trochanter-femur complex:

1075 (0) absent (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 21a-f);

1076 (1) present.

1077 53. Development degree of trochanter-femur complex:

1078 (0) not very strong (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): 22a-e);

1079 (1) very strong (Supplementary Fig. S29t; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 22f-h).

1080 The typical trochanter-femur complex found in Mantispinae represent that the trochanter
1081 appears to be almost completely fused with the femur, restricting any movement between those
1082 two parts to a minimum (Büsse et al. 2021), while in †*Haplacantha tenuis*, Calomantispinae,
1083 †*Doratomantispinae*, Drepanicinae, this complex is weak, and the remaining mantispoids lack
1084 this association, with a higher degree of freedom in the movement between trochanter and
1085 profemur ((Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021)). Character 53 is dependent on character 52.

1086 54. Profemoral ventral integumentary specializations (ISs, i.e., integumentary processes (IPs) in
1087 Pérez-de la Fuente and Peñalver (2019a)):

1088 (0) absent;

1089 (1) present.

1090 Considering the limitation of the previous terms (“spine”, “teeth”, “denticle”, “spine-like seta”,
1091 “cuticular spines”) to describe the profemoral structures comprising an elevated integumentary
1092 process and apical variably elongate specialized seta (Tjeder 1959, Poivre 1978, Lambkin
1093 1986a),(Grimaldi 2000), Pérez-de la Fuente and Peñalver (2019a) proposed the descriptive term,
1094 “integumentary process (=IP) bearing a modified seta”. The classification of ISs is based on
1095 their relative process/seta proportion, their general appearance, and occurrence through the

1096 different raptorial mantispoid subfamilies(Pérez-de la Fuente and Peñalver 2019b, Ardila-
1097 Camacho et al. 2021). Herein, we separated the profemoral ISs into six basic types — “stinger-
1098 shaped”, “thorn-shaped”, “saber-shaped”, “tubercle-shaped”, “large pedicellate, thickened setae”
1099 and “spine-shaped” according to Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021). These ISs are arranged into two
1100 rows, namely the anteroventral row (internal row) and the posteroventral row (external
1101 row)(Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021). Major process herein includes “branched specializations” in
1102 †*Dicranoberothesa*, †*Doratomantispinae*, †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa* and †*Pectispina*
1103 and sub-basal process in some symphrasines, defined as a longest and stoutest ISs located at the
1104 most base of the profemoral anteroventral row, which may promote the preying efficiency by
1105 preventing the tibia from moving anteriorly in combination with a notch located anteroventrally
1106 at the distal end of the profemur (Büsse et al. 2021).

1107 55. Stinger-shaped ISs on profemur:

1108 (0) absent;

1109 (1) present.

1110 Pedicellate, short to remarkably elongate, thin, and tapering setae (Supplementary Fig. S2a;
1111 Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 29h).

1112 56. Thorn-shaped ISs on profemur:

1113 (0) absent;

1114 (1) present.

1115 Elongate and narrow especializations, consisting of narrow processes bearing long and tapering
1116 Stitz organs, process/seta ratio = 1-2.5 (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 29g).

1117 57. Saber-shaped ISs on profemur:

1118 (0) absent;

1119 (1) present.

1120 Long, and often curved, narrow processes, bearing a well-developed, conical Stitz organ

1121 (Supplementary Figs. S23e, S26g; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 29c). The process is

1122 always longer than the seta.

1123 58. Tubercle-shaped ISs on profemur:

1124 (0) absent;

1125 (1) present.

1126 Tiny to enlarged, short and thick processes equipped with, short and thick conical setae

1127 (Supplementary Fig. S24o; (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021): fig. 29f).

1128 59. Large pedicellate, thickened setae on profemur (unique of Symphrasinae. Supplementary Fig.

1129 S24o; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 29e):

1130 (0) absent;

1131 (1) present.

1132 60. Spine-shaped ISs on profemur:

1133 (0) absent;

1134 (1) present.

1135 Increasingly larger processes equipped with minute, plug-shaped Stitz organs (Supplementary

1136 Fig. S28n; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 29b).

1137 61. Development condition of profemoral anteroventral row:

1138 (0) fully developed, similar to posteroventral row (Supplementary Fig. S22d; Ardila-Camacho

1139 et al. (2021): fig. 24a);

1140 (1) reduced and incomplete (usually discontinuously arranged with large gaps) (Supplementary
1141 Fig. S23a, d; Aspöck and Mansell (1994): fig. 11; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 6c);
1142 (2) only one major process remained (Supplementary Fig. S1s, w; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021):
1143 fig. 22f-h).
1144 Characters 55-61 are dependent on character 54.

1145 62. Profemoral anteroventral row:
1146 (0) straight;
1147 (1) curved outwards near middle of profemur (and an autapomorphy of †*Haplacantha*;
1148 Supplementary Fig. S11, p).
1149 This character is dependent on character 60.

1150 63. Gradually shortened (from the base to apex of profemur) processes row of profemoral
1151 anteroventral row:
1152 (0) absent;
1153 (1) present (Supplementary Figs. S23e, S26a, j; Li et al. (2022): fig. 11a, c, d).
1154 Except †*Dicranoberotha*, †*Paradoxoberotha*, †*Haplacantha*, †*Psilomantispa*,
1155 †*Doratomantispa* and those with anteroventral row reduced to only one process (usually the
1156 major process), raptorial mantispoids generally bear these processes with similar length (Ardila-
1157 Camacho et al. (2021): figs. 6c, 24a) or long and short processes arranged irregularly or
1158 alternately.
1159 Characters 62, 63 is dependent on character 61.

1160 64. Major process:
1161 (0) absent;

1162 (1) present.

1163 This character is dependent on character 54.

1164 65. Major process type:

1165 (0) simple (Supplementary Figs. S21r, S28, S29);

1166 (1) branched. The branched major process sensu “branched specialization” in Ardila-Camacho

1167 et al. (2021), occurring in Doratomantiapinae, †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa*,

1168 †*Pectispina*, and independently evolving in †*Dicranoberothesa*.

1169 The branch number of this IS varies from two to five, primarily diverged from the base or the

1170 middle of its length.

1171 66. Position of major process:

1172 (0) near base of profemur (Supplementary Fig. S2l, p; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): 21d, e);

1173 (1) at proximal 1/5-1/4 length of profemur (Supplementary Fig. S28h; Ardila-Camacho et al.

1174 (2021): fig. 22b, c);

1175 (2) at proximal 1/3 length of profemur (Supplementary Figs. S23d, l, 29n, t; Ardila-Camacho et

1176 al. (2021): fig. 22d, e);

1177 (3) near middle of profemur (Supplementary Fig. S2g, S29h; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig.

1178 22f, g).

1179 67. Length of major process:

1180 (0) very short, distinctly less than 1/8 length of protibia (Supplementary Fig. S2l, p);

1181 (1) nearly 1/5 length of profemur (Supplementary Fig. S2g, S28h);

1182 (2) nearly 1/4 length of profemur (Supplementary Figs. S21r, S22q, S23l);

1183 (3) nearly 1/3 length of profemur (Supplementary Fig. S23n);

1184 (4) over 1/2 length of profemur (Supplementary Figs. S2s, S26g, j; Li et al. (2022): fig. 8d-e).

1185 68. Branches of major process (simple major process regarded as having one branch):

1186 (0) thorn-shaped (Supplementary Fig. S21r);

1187 (1) saber-shaped (Supplementary Figs. S25w, S26g);

1188 (2) spine-shaped (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): figs. 26a, 27a, 28b).

1189 The branch type of the major process is variable but seems to have phylogenetic or taxonomic
1190 values, such as thorn-shaped branch in all rhachiberothids, saber-shaped branch in
1191 †*Archaeodrepanicus* sp. (one paratype of †*Archaeodrepanicus nuddsi* possesses the profemoral
1192 major process, different from other type specimens, possibly representing a new species, so we
1193 isolated it from †*A. nuddsi* and used it for all analyses herein), †*Haplacantha*,
1194 †*Mesomantispoides*, †*Doratomantispinae* etc., spine-shaped branch in Drepanicinae,
1195 Calomantispinae and Mantispinae.

1196 Characters 65-68 are dependent on character 64.

1197 69. Primarily branching position of major process:

1198 (0) at base (Supplementary Fig. S26g, j; Li et al. (2022): figs. 15f, 22f);

1199 (1) near 1/5-1/4 length of major process (Supplementary Fig. S2s);

1200 (2) near middle (Supplementary Fig. S23d, e). This character is dependent on character 57.

1201 70. Number of branches:

1202 (0) two (Supplementary Fig. S2c; Li et al. (2022): fig. 15f);

1203 (1) three (Supplementary Fig. S2s);

1204 (2) four (Shi et al. (2020): fig. 3D; Li et al. (2022): fig. 24c, d);

1205 (3) five (Supplementary Fig. S22f).

1206 This character is dependent on character 57.

1207 71. Anterior branch of major process (i.e., the branch anterior to the primary branch (Li et al.
1208 2022)):

1209 (1) absent;

1210 (2) present (an autapomorphic character of †*Paradoxomantispa*; Li et al. (2022): fig. 22k).

1211 Characters 69-71 are dependent on character 65.

1212 72. Development condition of profemoral posteroventral row:

1213 (0) well-developed, dense (gaps among processes very narrow) (Supplementary Fig. S22a-d);

1214 (1) reduced, sparse (gaps among processes broad) (Supplementary Figs. S23e, S24f, S26j);

1215 (2) reduced into only one process (Supplementary Fig. S2s, w).

1216 This character is dependent on character 54.

1217 73. Profemoral posteroventral row:

1218 (0) straight;

1219 (1) curved outwards (an autapomorphic character of †*Haplacantha*. Supplementary Fig. S21).

1220 This character is dependent on character 72.

1221 74. Profemoral posteroventral row proximally commencing:

1222 (0) near base of profemur;

1223 (1) at proximal 1/4-1/3 length of profemur (Supplementary Fig. S26g; Ardila-Camacho et al.
1224 (2021): fig. 22e, Li et al. (2022): fig. 9a);

1225 (2) near middle of profemur (Supplementary Figs. S2c, l; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig.
1226 22f).

1227 This character is dependent on character 53.

- 1228 75. Processes of profemoral posteroventral row:
- 1229 (0) not gradually shortened;
- 1230 (1) gradually shortened.
- 1231 Except †*Dicranoberothes*, †*Paradoxoberothes*, †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa*,
- 1232 †*Haplacantha*, †*Pectispina*, †*Psilomantispa*, †*Doratomantispinae*, raptorial mantispoids
- 1233 generally bear posteroventral processes with similar length (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): figs.
- 1234 6c, 24a) or long and short processes arranged irregularly or alternately (Ardila-Camacho et al.
- 1235 (2021): fig. 22).
- 1236 Character 75 is dependent on character 72.
- 1237 76. Profemoral posteroventral carina (laterally compressed and raised area along and under the
- 1238 entire posteroventral ISs row (Lambkin 1986a, Büsse et al. 2021):
- 1239 (0) absent;
- 1240 (1) present.
- 1241 This character is dependent on character 54.
- 1242 77. Profemoral posteroventral carina:
- 1243 (0) narrow (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 27a, b);
- 1244 (1) broad (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 28a).
- 1245 This character is dependent on character 76.
- 1246 78. Extra and independent ISs scattered between antero- and posteroventral rows:
- 1247 (0) absent;
- 1248 (1) present (an autapomorphy of †*Haplacantha*. Supplementary Fig. S21, p).
- 1249 This character is dependent on character 54.

- 1250 79. Closed protibia:
- 1251 (0) longer to slightly shorter than profemur;
- 1252 (1) about $\times 4/5$ length of profemur;
- 1253 (2) $\times 3/4$ - $2/3$ length of profemur;
- 1254 (3) $\times 1/2$ length of profemur.
- 1255 Closed tibia in cursorial Mantispoidea are usually slightly to distinctly longer than profemur,
- 1256 while in raptorial Mantispoidea, it is shorter than profemur to different degrees.
- 1257 80. Protibia plus protarsus:
- 1258 (0) longer than profemur;
- 1259 (1) as long as profemur (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 21c-f);
- 1260 (2) shorter than profemur.
- 1261 State 2 is only shared by Calomantispinae and Mantispinae, and state 1 seems a synapomorphy
- 1262 of Symphrasinae, while state 0 is very common, might be the groundplan in raptorial
- 1263 Mantispoidea. Character is dependent on character 79.
- 1264 81. Protibia near joint with profemur:
- 1265 (0) not curved;
- 1266 (1) curved (Supplementary Fig. S2j).
- 1267 This character may be a synapomorphy of raptorial Mantispoidea.
- 1268 82. Protibia medially:
- 1269 (0) straight (Supplementary Fig. S2s);
- 1270 (1) curved (Supplementary Fig. S2l).
- 1271 83. Protibial ventral keel (or “ridge” (Lambkin 1986a)):

1272 (0) absent;

1273 (1) present (Supplementary Fig. S2d).

1274 This character should be the synapomorphy of raptorial Mantispoidea (Ardila-Camacho et al.
1275 2021).

1276 84. Protibial specialized setae:

1277 (0) absent (Supplementary Figs. S23n, S29v; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): figs. 23c, 28g);

1278 (1) present.

1279 The protibial specialized setae, if present, are thickened, continuously or discontinuously
1280 arranged in a row on the ventral keel, with each two separated by a wide or narrow gap. They
1281 can be categorized into two types — “erected” and “flattened” by the degree of touching ventral
1282 keel, and also can be separated into three types — “straight, not curved”, “smoothly curved”
1283 and “angularly curved” by their own curving degree. Generally, the type of these specialized
1284 setae is monotonous and uniform on the same protibia, but sometimes two types can occur
1285 simultaneously in some rhachiberothids.

1286 85. Protibial specialized setae arranged:

1287 (0) continuously (Supplementary Figs. S22k, S23h, q);

1288 (1) discontinuously. (Supplementary Figs. S21r, S22o)

1289 86. Shape of protibial specialized setae:

1290 (0) homogeneous;

1291 (1) heterogeneous (Supplementary Fig. S22o).

1292 87. Protibial specialized setae:

1293 (0) erected (Supplementary Fig. S22k);

- 1294 (1) flattened (Supplementary Fig. S24q).
- 1295 88. Curving degree of protibial specialized setae:
- 1296 (0) straight, not curved (Supplementary Fig. S22e);
- 1297 (1) smoothly curved (Supplementary Figs. S21o, S26g);
- 1298 (2) angularly curved (Supplementary Figs. S2t, S26k, m; Li et al. (2022): figs. 13f, 20f).
- 1299 89. Protibial specialized setae most:
- 1300 (0) nearly as long as width of protibia (Supplementary Fig. S22e);
- 1301 (1) distinctly longer than width of protibia (over twice) (Supplementary Fig. S2a);
- 1302 (2) shorter than 1/2 width of protibia (Supplementary Fig. S2m, q).
- 1303 Characters 85-89 are dependent on character 84.
- 1304 90. Male protarsus:
- 1305 (0) 5-segmented;
- 1306 (1) 4-segmented (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): 23e, 24g, 25e; Aspöck and Mansell (1994): fig.
- 1307 21).
- 1308 91. Female protarsus:
- 1309 (0) 5-segmented;
- 1310 (1) 4-segmented.
- 1311 92. Male probasitarsus distally:
- 1312 (0) not produced;
- 1313 (1) slightly produced (Supplementary Fig. S22f);
- 1314 (2) strongly produced (i.e., spinous probasitarsus. Supplementary Fig. S24q).
- 1315 93. Female probasitarsus distally:

- 1316 (0) not produced;
- 1317 (1) slightly produced;
- 1318 (2) strongly produced .
- 1319 94. Male probasitarsus:
- 1320 (0) at most as long as remaining protarsomeres except terminal one combined;
- 1321 (1) nearly as long as remaining protarsomeres combined (Supplementary Figs. S21e, s, S23d, h);
- 1322 (2) distinctly longer than remaining protarsomeres combined (Supplementary Fig. S25c, k, l).
- 1323 95. Female probasitarsus:
- 1324 (0) at most as long as remaining protarsomeres except terminal one combined;
- 1325 (1) nearly as long as remaining protarsomeres combined;
- 1326 (2) distinctly longer than remaining protarsomeres combined.
- 1327 96. Male distodorsal specialized setae of probasitarsus:
- 1328 (0) absent; (1) long and thickened;
- 1329 (2) minute, present as “Stitz organ” (Supplementary Fig. S25k; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021):
- 1330 fig. 24h).
- 1331 97. Female distodorsal specialized setae of probasitarsus:
- 1332 (0) absent;
- 1333 (1) long and thickened (Supplementary Fig. S22f);
- 1334 (2) minute, present as “Stitz organ” (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 24h).
- 1335 The presence of characters 95, 96 is shared by some species of Rhachiberothidae, Symphrasinae
- 1336 and †*Sinomesomantispa*. Characters 89-96 in Rhachiberothinae present sexual dimorphism that
- 1337 female rhachiberothines possess the 5-segmented protarsus showing many plesiomorphic

1338 characters of Mantispoidea, such as the absence of the distal process and the specialized setae of
1339 probasitarsus, the probasitarsus at most as long as the following three protarsomeres combined,
1340 while males show more specialized characters, such as 4-segmented protarsus, the presence of
1341 distally produced probasitarsus with apical specialized setae and the probasitarsus as long as the
1342 remaining protarsomeres combined. In Symphrasinae, both male and female share the same
1343 specialized characters including 4-segmented protarsus, probasitarsus distally strongly produced
1344 with minute “Stitz organ” and distinctly longer than the remaining protarsomeres combined.

1345 98. Probasitarsal ventral specialized setae:

1346 (0) absent;

1347 (1) present.

1348 The classification of these specialized setae is similar to that of protibial specialized setae,
1349 except the conical setae and the angularly curved setae with two different states (closely pressed
1350 to the tarsal venter or not). These specialized setae were arranged in one (e.g., †*Micromantispa*,
1351 †*Paraberothoides*, Symphrasinae) or two rows (†*Acanthoberothena*, †*Creagroparaberothena*,
1352 †*Uranoberothena* and most mantispids), sometimes reduced into only one (†*Astioberothena*,
1353 †*Creagroparaberothena cuneata*, †*Paradoxoberothena chimaera*). The ventral specialized setae on
1354 the probasitarsus of †*Creagroparaberothena groehni* Makarkin should be arranged in two rows
1355 according to our present study (Supplementary Fig. S22f) and the figs. 2B, 6A in Makarkin and
1356 Ohl (2015), rather than “arrange in one row” interpreted in Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021).

1357 99. Probasitarsal ventral specialized setae:

1358 (0) erected (Supplementary Fig. S22f);

1359 (1) flattened (Supplementary Figs. S24q, S25k).

- 1360 100. Curving degree of probasitarsal ventral specialized setae:
- 1361 (0) smoothly curved, long (Supplementary Fig. S22f);
- 1362 (1) angularly curved, apically not touching tarsal venter (Supplementary Fig. S2n, r; Pérez-de la
- 1363 Fuente and Peñalver (2019a): fig. 4c);
- 1364 (2) angularly curved, apically touching tarsal venter (Supplementary Fig. S29i, k; Pérez-de la
- 1365 Fuente and Peñalver (2019a): fig. 6d);
- 1366 (3) straight, conical (Supplementary Fig. S26l-m, o; Li et al. (2022): figs. 8g, 11e, 23g).
- 1367 101. Probasitarsal ventral specialized setae arranged as:
- 1368 (0) two rows;
- 1369 (1) one row;
- 1370 (2) only one setae.
- 1371 Characters 99-101 are dependent on character 98.
- 1372 102. Protarsal segment 2 distodorsally:
- 1373 (0) without;
- 1374 (1) with a long, specialized seta (only found in †Paraberothinae. Supplementary Fig. S22f).
- 1375 103. Protarsal segment 2 ventrally:
- 1376 (0) without;
- 1377 (1) with specialized setae.
- 1378 104. Curving degree of protarsomere 2 ventral specialized setae:
- 1379 (0) straight to smoothly curved, long;
- 1380 (1) angularly curved, apically not touching tarsal venter;
- 1381 (2) angularly curved, apically touching tarsal venter;

- 1382 (3) straight, conical. This character is dependent on character 103.
- 1383 105. Protarsomeres 3-4 ventrally:
- 1384 (0) without;
- 1385 (1) with specialized setae.
- 1386 106. Curving degree of protarsomeres 3-4 ventral specialized setae:
- 1387 (0) angularly curved, apically not touching tarsal venter;
- 1388 (1) angularly curved, touching tarsal venter;
- 1389 (2) straight, conical.
- 1390 This character is dependent on character 105.
- 1391 107. Pretarsal claw:
- 1392 (0) paired;
- 1393 (1) single (Supplementary Fig. S29w; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 28h).
- 1394 The single pretarsal claw is the origin synapomorphy of Mantispinae (Lambkin 1986a, Lambkin
- 1395 1986b)
- 1396 108. Pretarsal claw each:
- 1397 (0) simple (groundplan in Mantispoidea);
- 1398 (1) bifurcate (found in *Allomantispa* and Calomantispinae; Liu et al. (2015): fig. 3G; (Li et al.
- 1399 2020b): fig. 5C, J);
- 1400 (2) multiforked (found in Osmylidae and Mantispinae except *Campion*; Supplementary Fig.
- 1401 S29x).
- 1402 109. Arolium of protarsus:
- 1403 (0) large, sac-like;

1404 (1) small, triangular and acutely tapering distad (only found in †Doratomantispinae,
1405 †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa*, †*Pectispina* and †*Psilomantispa*. Supplementary Figs.
1406 S2u, S26l).

1407 This character is dependent on character 107.

1408 110. Distal thickened setae (spurs) of protarsus:

1409 (0) present;

1410 (1) absent.

1411 111. Segments 3-4 of meso- and metatarsi ventroapically:

1412 (0) with one pair of thickened setae (suprs) (Supplementary Fig. S21d-e);

1413 (1) with two pairs of thickened setae (spurs) (Supplementary Figs. S21b, h, S23m, S25f, r-s,
1414 S26d-f);

1415 (2) with at least three pairs of thickened setae (Supplementary Figs. S25q, r, S26p-s); (3)
1416 without thickened setae (spurs).

1417 The tarsal spurs sensu the bristles in Willmann (1990) and thickened setae in Ardila-Camacho et
1418 al. (2021) are distoventrally arranged on two sides of tarsomeres 2-4. Cursorial mantispoids
1419 always bear one or more pairs of distal spurs respectively on protarsomeres 1-4, the same as on
1420 meso- and metatarsomeres 1-4, while this structure is generally absent in raptorial mantispoids
1421 except some rhachiberothids, e.g., †*Astioberotha* (Nakamine et al. (2020): Fig. S5h, i). On
1422 meso- and metatarsomeres 1-4, there are only one pair of spurs in most berothids except
1423 †*Osmyloberotha* and Cretaceous long-antenna berothid genera (two pairs of spurs); two pairs of
1424 spurs possibly represent the groundplan of raptorial mantispoids, occurring in Rhachiberothidae,
1425 †Dipteromantispidae and basal mantispids, e.g., †Mesomantispinae, †*Mesomantispoides*,

1426 †*Haplacantha* and †*Aragomantispa*; over three pairs of spurs may evolve independently in
1427 Symphrasinae, †Doratomantispinae and DCM clade.

1428 112. Each pretarsal claw of mid and hind legs:

1429 (0) multifurcate (in Mantispoidea, it only occurs in Mantispinae (Lambkin 1986a, Snyman et al.
1430 2017, Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021));

1431 (1) simple;

1432 (2) bifurcate (split into two equal teeth or a developed tooth with a small accessory one, found
1433 in Drepanicinae (*Allomantispa*, *Gerstaeckerella* and *Theristria*) and Calomantispinae (Liu et al.
1434 (2015): fig. 3H, I; Li et al. (2020b): fig. 5D, E, H, I).

1435 113. Hind legs:

1436 (0) not shortened;

1437 (1) shortened (the autapomorphy of *Theristria* (Lambkin 1986a, Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021)).

1438 114. Metatibia swollen basally:

1439 (0) absent;

1440 (1) present (the autapomorphy of *Nolima* (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021)).

1441 115. Metatibia enlarged, making hind legs superficially similar to pollen-carrying legs:

1442 (0) absent;

1443 (1) present (the autapomorphy of *Anchieta* (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021)).

1444

1445 **Wings**

1446 116. Trichosors (short thickened veinlets without tracheation on the wing margin between each
1447 two apical veinlets of longitudinal veins (Breitkreuz et al. 2017), (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021):

1448 (0) well-developed, almost around entire wing margin;

1449 (1) moderately developed, present on the entire wing margin except large part of anterior base;

1450 (2) reduced, present only along wing apex;

1451 (3) absent.

1452 117. Number of trichosors between each two adjacent veinlets generally:

1453 (0) only one;

1454 (1) more than two (Supplementary Figs. S11k, S37f).

1455 This character is dependent on character 116.

1456 The presence of trichosors is considered as a plesiomorphic condition in Neuroptera, well-

1457 developed in Berothidae and Rhachiberothidae, but variously modified or reduced in

1458 †Dipteromantispidae, Symphrasinae and Mantispidae. All berothids, rhachiberothids, most

1459 fossil symphrasines, †*Aragomantispa*, †*Haplacantha*, †Mesomantispinae and

1460 †Doratomantispinae, there is only one trichosor between each two adjacent veinlets surrounding

1461 almost entire wing margin. In †*Haplosymphrasites* and extant genera of Symphrasinae, the one

1462 trichosor between each two adjacent veinlets, if present, is restricted on the wing apex, and most

1463 part of the wing margin except the base bears 2-9 trichosors between the adjacent veinlets. In

1464 †*Paradipteromantispa*, †*Enigmadipteromantispa dilatata*, †*Kurtodipteromantispa relictata*,

1465 †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa*, †*Pectispina* and †*Psilomantispa*, *Gerstaeckerella*, the

1466 trichosors are reduced and only restricted on the wing apex, usually present as only one between

1467 each two adjacent veinlets (2-3 present in *Gerstaeckerella*), while in remaining members of

1468 †Dipteromantispidae, Drepanicinae, Calomantispinae and Mantispinae, trichosors are

1469 completely absent.

1470 118. Vesicae (i.e., lens-shaped vesicular structures covered with sensory pits (Tjeder 1968)):
1471 (0) absent;
1472 (1) present (Aspöck and Aspöck (1997): figs. 18, 19).
1473 Vesicae is a common character for Rhachiberothinae, currently present in all known males, but
1474 only in the female of one species, which is a unique evolutionary novelty of unknown
1475 function(Aspöck and Mansell 1994).

1476 119. Nygmata:
1477 (0) present;
1478 (1) absent.
1479 The membrane of many neuropteran families includes one or two nygmata, small spots in well-
1480 defined consistent positions and of some taxonomic value (New 1989). Nygmata are usually
1481 slightly domed and devoid of setae except around the periphery, and are of similar appearance
1482 from either wing surface (New 1989), absent in all mantispoids.

1483 120. Female wing scales (scale-like setae on wings):
1484 (0) absent;
1485 (1) present.
1486 Lack of scales is plesiomorphic in Neuroptera, and the presence of scales is apomorphic. Wing
1487 scales are restricted to the female berothines and occur in all genera (though not all species)
1488 except *Berlekrumyia*, *Lekrugeria* and *Berotha* (Aspöck and Nemeschkal 1998).

1489 121. Wing margin hair:
1490 (0) long, not shortened;
1491 (1) shortened.

1492 122. Pterostigma:

1493 (0) distinct;

1494 (1) indistinct (Supplementary Figs. S2b, S8e, S11b).

1495 The distinct pterostigma is generally thickened, opaque to translucent and colorful, with

1496 incorporated veins distinct to obscure, while the indistinct pterostigma region is thin,

1497 transparent and usually immaculate, with quite distinct incorporated veins.

1498 123. Pterostigma shape:

1499 (0) long, distinctly longer than wide;

1500 (1) short, nearly as long as wide. This character is dependent on character 121, possibly as an

1501 apomorphy for Calomantispinae (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021). This character is dependent on

1502 character 122.

1503 124. Incorporated veins in pterostigma:

1504 (0) present;

1505 (1) absent.

1506 This character is dependent on character 122.

1507 125. ScP distally:

1508 (0) fused with RA;

1509 (1) separate from RA (generally, one or more short crossveins connecting ScP and RA distally

1510 (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021)).

1511 126. Crossveins under pterostigma or the same position:

1512 (0) only one;

1513 (1) more than one.

1514 This character is dependent on character 125.

1515 127. Subcostal area distinctly enlarged distally with ScP abruptly curved towards RA:

1516 (0) absent;

1517 (1) present (Supplementary Fig. S35a).

1518 This character occurs in †*Enigmadipteromantispa*, †*Kurtodipteromantispa*,
1519 †*Paradipteromantispa*, †Doratomantispinae, Drepanicinae and Calomantispinae, and in
1520 remaining mantispoids, the subcostal area is nearly uniformly broadened along its entire length
1521 with ScP from smooth to curved towards RA. The straight ScP is observed in most genera of
1522 †Dipteromantispidae (Liu et al. (2017): fig. 5), possibly representing a derived character in this
1523 family.

1524 128. RA distally:

1525 (0) separate from RP;

1526 (1) fused with RP for a short distance (an original synapomorphy of Mantispinae. Ardila-
1527 Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 30e).

1528 129. RP main branches:

1529 (0) smooth;

1530 (1) sinuous (Supplementary Fig. S40d-g. Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 39g-j).

1531 RP branches are commonly smooth and at most only slightly displaced at the gradate series in
1532 most mantispoids, while strongly sinuous (S-shaped) proximad the gradate series in some
1533 *Theristria*, Calomantispinae and Mantispinae.

1534 130. RP branches:

1535 (0) with small apical twigging (very small and shallowly bifurcate or multifurcate branches of

1536 each primary branch. Supplementary Fig. S30a);

1537 (1) without small apical twiggings (each primary branch simple or only deeply forked.

1538 Supplementary Fig. S35b; Liu et al. (2017): fig. 5; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 32g-j).

1539 This is character to measure the complexity and density of wing venations. In most mantispoids,

1540 RP branches more or less bear dense to sparse apical twiggings (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021),

1541 while in *Anchieta*, †*Haplosymphrasites*, *Theristria*, †Dipteromantispidae except

1542 †*Paradipteromantispa*, Calomantispinae and Mantispinae, RP branches are almost to all simple

1543 or deeply simply bifurcate.

1544 131. Humeral recurrent vein (i.e., first costal crossvein, which is curved toward the wing base and

1545 often pectinately forked (Breitkreuz et al. 2017)):

1546 (0) branched;

1547 (1) simple, possibly lost.

1548 132. Branching condition of humeral recurrent vein:

1549 (0) complicatedly, at least one branch diverging secondarily (Supplementary Fig. S36a-i; Jepson

1550 et al. (2013): fig. 1C);

1551 (1) simply multifurcate, more than three branches (Supplementary Figs. S36j, S37d-f; Ardila-

1552 Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 10a; Nakamine et al. (2022): fig. 3a);

1553 (2) trifurcate;

1554 (3) bifurcate.

1555 This character is dependent on character 131.

1556 In Mantispoidea, the complicatedly branched humeral recurrent vein is found in some extinct

1557 taxa (possibly representing the basal lineages), such as †Mesithoninae, †Mesomantispinae,

1558 †*Archaeosymphrasis*, †*Mesomantispoidea*, †*Oloberotha*, †*Parasymphrasites*, etc., while this
1559 vein of all extant and remaining fossil taxa has a tendency to reduction, in which the simple
1560 (possibly lost) and bifurcate ones are much commoner.

1561 133. Forewing apex:

1562 (0) rounded;

1563 (1) acute, subfalcate (Supplementary Fig. S30d);

1564 (2) acute, falcate (Supplementary Fig. S31g, h; Li et al. (2018): figs. 1-11).

1565 A rounded wing apex is plesiomorphic in the Neuroptera, an acute (subfalcate or falcate) wing
1566 apex is apomorphic and has certainly evolved several times independently (Aspöck and
1567 Nemeschkal 1998), e.g., also in the Osmylidae, Hemerobiidae. The acute (subfalcate or falcate)
1568 wing in Mantispoidea is mainly converged on Berothidae, e.g., †*Ansoberotha*, †*Cornoberotha*,
1569 †*Dolichoberotha* (hind wing), †*Osmyloberotha*, *Spiroberotha*, †*Xenoberotha*, Trichomatinae
1570 and Berothinae, etc., while in raptorial Mantispoidea, only *Hoezelliella* shares this character
1571 state.

1572 134. Forewing length/width ratio:

1573 (0) about 2.5 times as long as wide;

1574 (1) over 3 times as long as wide (Supplementary Fig. S30d-l);

1575 (2) over 3.5 times as long as wide (Supplementary Fig. S40g);

1576 (3) over 4 times as long as wide (Supplementary Fig. S40f).

1577 135. Forewing costal space:

1578 (0) directly extending to pterostigma or same position;

1579 (1) with costal vein fused with ScP for a distance (see in *Austromantispa*, *Nolima*, *Xaviera*, etc.;

1580 Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 32h).

1581 136. Forewing costal crossveins proximad pterostigma or the same position (proximad position
1582 that ScP is distally curved toward RA (or their fusion point)):

1583 (0) branched;

1584 (1) simple (sometimes one or two bifurcate, which is unstable and belongs to the individual
1585 variation).

1586 137. Forewing dense costal crossveins (over 10 costal crossveins proximad the level of primary
1587 branching point of M, with gap less than 1/2 length of costal crossvein):

1588 (0) present (Supplementary Fig. S30a; Makarkin et al. (2011): fig. 3B);

1589 (1) absent.

1590 138. Forewing subcostal space proximad pterostigma or the same position (not taking those under
1591 pterostigma or the same position into consideration):

1592 (0) with only one crossvein near base;

1593 (1) with 2-3 crossveins;

1594 (2) more than 4;

1595 (3) veinless.

1596 The single crossvein (1scp-r) proximad the pterostigma or the same position may represent the
1597 groundplan for Mantispoidea, only members in †*Sinosmylites*, Rhachiberothinae, Nyrminae,
1598 some mesomantispines and Mantispinae bear over two scp-r crossveins proximad the
1599 pterostigma or the same position. These crossvein can be also completely lost in
1600 †Dipteromantispidae, some berothids, and †*Dicranomantispa*.

1601 139. Forewing most proximal scp-r (i.e., 1scp-r, the crossvein between Sc and R closest to the

- 1602 wing base):
- 1603 (0) proximad original point of RP (Supplementary Fig. S30d);
- 1604 (1) distad original point of RP (Supplementary Fig. S39a).
- 1605 This character is dependent on character 136. The most proximal scp-r distad the original point
- 1606 of RP is mainly observed in †*Magniberothera*, Symphrasinae (at the original point of RP in some
- 1607 genera), †Doratomantispinae, some species of †*Acanthomantispa* and †*Psilomantispa*. This
- 1608 character is dependent on character 138.
- 1609 140. Forewing RA branches:
- 1610 (0) branched;
- 1611 (1) simple.
- 1612 141. Number of forewing ra-rp:
- 1613 (0) three;
- 1614 (1) two;
- 1615 (2) one;
- 1616 (3) absent;
- 1617 (4) more than three.
- 1618 142. Forewing ra-rp (referring to the most distal one) distad pterostigma or the same position
- 1619 (proximad position that ScP is distally curved toward RA (or their fusion point)):
- 1620 (0) absent (Supplementary Fig. S31h);
- 1621 (1) present (Supplementary Fig. S31g).
- 1622 143. Two regular forewing gradate series:
- 1623 (0) absent;

1624 (1) present (Supplementary Figs. S30h, S40c).

1625 144. Forewing RP:

1626 (0) smooth at proximal 1ra-rp;

1627 (1) angularly curved at proximal 1ra-rp (an autapomorphy of dipteromantispids except

1628 †*Enigmadipteromantispa* and †*Mantispidipterella*. Liu et al. (2017): fig. 5).

1629 145. Independent RP on forewing (sensu MA in Liu et al. (2017): fig. 9E, found in Dilaridae and

1630 Hemerobiidae (Breitkreuz et al. (2017): fig. 14)):

1631 (0) absent;

1632 (1) present.

1633 146. Forewing 1rp-m (sensu the stem of MA (“b”) in Aspöck (1983)):

1634 (0) proximad original point of RP;

1635 (1) distad original point of RP.

1636 147. Forewing 1rp-m (sensu the stem of MA (“b”) in Aspöck (1983)):

1637 (0) proximad primary branching point of M;

1638 (1) distad primary branching point of M.

1639 The 1rp-m crossvein located distad both the original point of RP and the primary branching

1640 point of M are commoner than other states. There could be another extremely short crossvein

1641 named “1r-m” very close to the wing base in Lu et al. (2020), proximad both the original point

1642 of RP and the primary branching point of M, which occurs in †*Doratomantispinae*,

1643 †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa* and †*Psilomantispa*. This short crossvein should not be

1644 homologous to “1rp-m” mentioned above, since the latter is usually longer and more distal to

1645 the wing base, and there are generally no crossvein between it and the last 1rp-m crossvein (Li

1646 et al. (2018): figs. 1-11; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 32). Although “1rp-m” has similar
1647 position to “1r-m” in most genera of Berothinae, it still shares the same traits of “1rp-m”
1648 aforementioned, and furthermore there are some possible transitional states observed in some
1649 genera in Berothidae, such as distinctly distad both the original point of RP and the primary
1650 branching point of M as in many other mantispoids in *Austroberothella*, *Nyrma*, *Spiroberotha*
1651 (Aspöck and Aspöck (1979): fig. 7; Aspöck and Aspöck (1984): fig. 25; (Ardila-Camacho et al.
1652 2021): fig. 1e), slightly distad both the original point of RP and the primary branching point of
1653 M in *Lomamyia* (Faulkner (1992): figs. 33, 34). Here we name the “1r-m” in
1654 †*Doratomantispinae*, †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa* and †*Psilomantispa* as “accessory
1655 r-m”.

1656 148. Forewing venations:

1657 (0) not reticular;

1658 (1) reticular (with many irregularly arranged crossveins on wings. Monserrat (2006): fig. 7b, c).

1659 149. Forewing MA (sensu the anterior branch of MP in Lambkin (1986a), Liu et al. (2015)):

1660 (0) not approaching or fused with RP;

1661 (1) approaching or fused with RP (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): figs. 32g, j; Lambkin (1986b):

1662 figs. 404, 419; observed in *Calomantispa*, *Climaciella*, *Euclimacia*, etc.).

1663 150. Forewing MA:

1664 (0) multibranching;

1665 (1) simply bifurcate (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 32i, j);

1666 (2) simple.

1667 151. Forewing MP (sensu the posterior branch of MP in Lambkin (1986a), Liu et al. (2015)):

- 1668 (0) multibranched;
- 1669 (1) simply bifurcate;
- 1670 (2) simple.
- 1671 152. Forewing 1m-cu:
- 1672 (0) present;
- 1673 (1) absent.
- 1674 153. Forewing 1m-cu:
- 1675 (0) distad primary branching point of Cu;
- 1676 (1) proximad primary branching point of Cu;
- 1677 (2) at primary branching point of Cu. This character is dependent on character 152.
- 1678 154. Forewing M distad 1m-cu:
- 1679 (0) separate from R;
- 1680 (1) fused with R for a short distance (possibly the synapomorphy for †Dipteromantispidae,
- 1681 distinctly shorter than m-cu. Supplementary Fig. S35);
- 1682 (2) fused with R for a long distance (found in †*Protoberotha*, extant and some fossil
- 1683 symphrasines, equal to or longer than m-cu. Supplementary Figs. S37d, f, S40e); (3) fused with
- 1684 R for a long distance with a small cell above m-cu (the autapomorphy of Mantispinae.
- 1685 Supplementary Fig. S40f, g; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 32i, j). This character is
- 1686 dependent on character 152.
- 1687 155. Forewing M stem proximally:
- 1688 (0) smoothly curved;
- 1689 (1) strongly curved (an autapomorphy of †Dipteromantispidae. Supplementary Fig. S35).

- 1690 156. Forewing CuA stem:
- 1691 (0) not approaching to MP;
- 1692 (1) approaching to MP (an autapomorphy of *Gerstaeckerella*; Figs. 32e).
- 1693 157. Forewing CuA:
- 1694 (0) multibranched;
- 1695 (1) simply bifurcate;
- 1696 (2) simple.
- 1697 158. Completely branched forewing CuA (with over seven dense main branches):
- 1698 (0) absent;
- 1699 (1) present.
- 1700 This character is dependent on character 157.
- 1701 159. Forewing CuP distally:
- 1702 (0) free;
- 1703 (1) fused with A1 (an autapomorphy of *Nolima*).
- 1704 160. Forewing CuP proximally:
- 1705 (0) not approaching A1;
- 1706 (1) approaching A1 (cup-a1 barely detected, an autapomorphy of Symphrasinae; Supplementary
- 1707 Figs. S36j, S37d, f).
- 1708 161. Forewing CuP:
- 1709 (0) multibranched;
- 1710 (1) simply bifurcate;
- 1711 (2) simple.

- 1712 This character is dependent on character 155.
- 1713 162. Hind wing:
- 1714 (0) well-developed, similar to forewing;
- 1715 (1) strongly reduced, haltere-like (the autapomorphy of †Dipteromantispidae; Supplementary
- 1716 Fig. S11b).
- 1717 163. Hind wing apex:
- 1718 (0) rounded;
- 1719 (1) acute, subfalcate;
- 1720 (2) acute, falcate (Li et al., 2018: figs. 1-11).
- 1721 This character is dependent on character 162.
- 1722 164. Hind wing costal space:
- 1723 (0) directly extending to pterostigma or same position;
- 1724 (1) with costal vein fused with ScP for a distance (found in †*Haplosymphrasites*,
- 1725 †*Parvosymphrasites*, †*Proplega*, *Anchieta*, *Plega*, *Trichoscelia*, *Nolima*, and some genera of
- 1726 Mantispinae. Supplementary Figs. S36j, S37; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 32b-d, h);
- 1727 (2) unclear (this area is reduced and unclear in †Dipteromantispidae).
- 1728 165. Hind wing venations:
- 1729 (0) not reticular;
- 1730 (1) reticular.
- 1731 166. Hind wing gradates nearly throughout the last RP branch (well complete gradates series):
- 1732 (0) absent (i.e., the outer crossvein row arranged posteriad the longitudinal axis of wing.
- 1733 Supplementary Fig. S30a);

1734 (1) present (i.e., the outer crossvein row arranged anterior to the longitudinal axis of wing, usually
1735 directly extending under the distal ra-rp. Supplementary Fig. S31c).

1736 167. Number of hind wing ra-rp:

1737 (0) three;

1738 (1) one;

1739 (2) two;

1740 (3) absent;

1741 (4) more than three.

1742 168. Hind wing ra-rp (referring to the most distal one) distad pterostigma or the same position
1743 (proximal position that ScP is distally curved toward RA (or their fusion point)):

1744 (0) absent;

1745 (1) present.

1746 This character is dependent on character 167.

1747 169. Two regular hind wing gradate series:

1748 (0) absent;

1749 (1) present.

1750 170. Hind wing 1rp-m (sensu the stem of MA ("b") in Aspöck (1983), Liu et al. (2015), Lu et al.
1751 (2020)):

1752 (0) present;

1753 (1) absent.

1754 171. Hind wing 1rp-m:

1755 (0) sigmoid (Supplementary Fig. S411-o);

- 1756 (1) upright;
- 1757 (2) absent (Makarkin (2018): fig. 3B; Huang et al. (2019): fig. 2C, D).
- 1758 The sigmoid 1rp-m may evolve or reverse independently multiple times in Mantispoidea,
- 1759 observed in †*Osmyloberotha*, Rhachiberothinae, †*Paradoxoberotha*, †*Dicranoberotha*,
- 1760 †*Mesomantispoidea* and Symphrasinae. The hind wing sigmoid 1rp-m is also observed in
- 1761 †*Khasurtoberotha bellissima*, albeit weakly visible, according to the fig. 39h of Kopylov et al.
- 1762 (2021).
- 1763 172. Hind wing 1rp-m:
- 1764 (0) proximad original point of RP;
- 1765 (1) distad original point of RP.
- 1766 173. Hind wing 1rp-m:
- 1767 (0) proximad primary branching point of M;
- 1768 (1) distad primary branching point of M.
- 1769 174. Additional short crossvein connecting 1rp-m and M stem in hind wing:
- 1770 (0) absent;
- 1771 (1) present (present in †*Paradoxoberotha* and *Trichoscelia*. Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig.
- 1772 32c).
- 1773 Characters 171-174 are dependent on character 170.
- 1774 175. Hind wing CuA:
- 1775 (0) long, terminating at or distad the midpoint of wing posterior margin (Supplementary Fig.
- 1776 S30);
- 1777 (1) shortened, terminating distinctly proximad the midpoint of wing posterior margin (only

- 1778 observed in Drepanicinae, Calomantispinae and Mantispinae. Supplementary Fig. S40);
- 1779 (2) undetected (observed in †Dipteromantispidae).
- 1780 176. Hind wing CuA:
- 1781 (0) not creeping, multibranched;
- 1782 (1) creeping (i.e., pectinate, with only short veinlets along wing margin (Aspöck and Randolph
- 1783 2014));
- 1784 (2) simply bifurcate;
- 1785 (3) simple.
- 1786 This character is dependent on character 175.
- 1787 177. Hind wing CuP:
- 1788 (0) detected;
- 1789 (1) undetected, possibly absent.
- 1790 178. Hind wing CuP stem:
- 1791 (0) long and deep (original point near 1m-cu);
- 1792 (1) very short (original point far away from 1m-cu. Breitkreuz et al. (2017): fig. 11B; Ardila-
- 1793 Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 31d);
- 1794 (2) reduced (Li et al. (2022): fig. 6c).
- 1795 179. Fusing condition of Hind wing CuP:
- 1796 (0) free;
- 1797 (1) only fused with CuA;
- 1798 (2) only fused with A1 (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 31a-f);
- 1799 (3) fused both with CuA and A1 (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 30a).

1800 Breitkreuz et al. (2017) presented an alternative interpretation on the homology of wing
1801 venation in Neuropterida based on vein tracheation, and then Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021)
1802 employed this method to analysis the homology of venations of Mantispoidea, in which there
1803 are four fusing states of hind wing CuP. State 1, the common state in Neuroptera, might be the
1804 groundplan in Mantispoidea, occurring in most species of Berothidae, Symphrasinae, fossil
1805 Rhachiberothidae and Mantispidae. In the few extant berothids (e.g., Speleoberotha), extant
1806 Rhachiberothidae and extant crown Mantispidae, the hind wing CuP is more or less fused with
1807 A1 anterior branches or CuA or both. In Speleoberotha paloma Machado, there is a very feeble
1808 CuP vein beneath the CuA stem (Machado et al. (2022): fig.4B), indicating the former seems
1809 not completely fused with the latter in this species, and the proximal 5-6 branches of CuA
1810 should belong to the creeping CuP. Due to the poorly preserved and indistinguishable tracheae
1811 in fossil specimens, their wing venations are interpreted using comparative morphology with
1812 extant mantispoids to coincide with the homology hypotheses in Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021).

1813 180. Hind wing CuP distally:

1814 (0) not creeping, multibranching;

1815 (1) creeping (i.e., pectinate, with only short veinlets along wing margin (Aspöck and Randolph
1816 2014));

1817 (2) simply bifurcate;

1818 (3) simple.

1819 Characters 178-180 are dependent on character 177.

1820 181. Hind wing CuP distally with creeping and simplified tendency (a tendency to having short

1821 branches and extending along wing posterior margin approximate to “hind wing with tendency to

1822 a reduction of the CuP” in Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021) who recovered it as a homologous
1823 character state for Mantispoidea):

1824 (0) absent;

1825 (1) present.

1826 Herein, this character includes creeping ((Aspöck and Randolph 2014)) and simply bifurcate CuP
1827 (distally not completely fused with A1 anterior branch) in Mantispoidea, indicating this
1828 longitudinal vein distally having a tendency to reduction (with less and very short branches),
1829 extending closely along the hind wing posterior margin. Character 181 is dependent on
1830 character 180.

1831

1832 **Abdomen**

1833 182. Male abdominal Eltringham’s extrusible glands on terga 4-5:

1834 (0) absent;

1835 (1) developed (Hoffman (1992): fig. 3.4A; Machado and Rafael (2010): figs. 24a, 28a);

1836 (2) reduced as a sclerotized and thickened line on each side.

1837 The Eltringham’s extrusible glands, initially described by Eltringham (1932), refer to the pores
1838 and marks, sometimes plus enlarged intersegmental membranes forming one or two pockets
1839 which may also be equipped with pores, arranged on terga 3-6 in Mantispinae (Ardila-Camacho
1840 et al. 2021), with important taxonomic and phylogenetic values. Among the mantispine genera
1841 examined currently, the pores and marks on male terga 4-5 are reduced as a sclerotized and
1842 thickened line on each side in *Mantispa*, *Mantispilla*, *Necyla* and *Euclimacia*, while the former
1843 three genera all bear a large “pocket” between terga 5 and 6.

- 1844 183. Male sternum 8 posteriorly with two projections:
- 1845 (0) absent;
- 1846 (1) present (an autapomorphy of *Spiroberotha*, each projection distally with a very thick seta.
- 1847 Machado and Krolow (2016): fig. 4).
- 1848 184. Male tergum 9 ventrally:
- 1849 (0) not fused with sternum 9;
- 1850 (1) fused with sternum 9 (the autapomorphy of *Nolima*. Reynoso-Velasco and Contreras-
- 1851 Ramose (2019): fig. 5a)
- 1852 *Nolima* has a tergum 9 either dorsally very thin and lateroventrally expanded (e.g., *N. pinal*
- 1853 Rehn, 1939) or completely paired and lateroventrally situated (Acker 1960), where it is partially
- 1854 fused with sternum 9 (Reynoso-Velasco and Contreras-Ramose 2019).
- 1855 185. Male tergum 9:
- 1856 (0) not fused with ectoprocts;
- 1857 (1) fused with ectoprocts (the fusion of tergum 9 and ectoprocts might be apomorphic, very
- 1858 common in extant Berothidae (Supplementary Fig. S42g-q).
- 1859 186. Male sternum 9:
- 1860 (0) unpaired;
- 1861 (1) paired (Supplementary Fig. S42k; Aspöck and Hynd (1995): fig. 9).
- 1862 187. Size of male sternum 9 compared with sternum 8:
- 1863 (0) developed, $\geq 1 \times$ length of sternum 8;
- 1864 (1) reduced, $< 1 \times$ length of sternum 8 (making the internal genital sclerites directly exposed
- 1865 ventrally; Supplementary Fig. S42n-q; Li et al. (2018): figs. 12, 13);

1866 (2) absent, possibly fused with sternum 8 (an autapomorphic character of †*Osmyloberotha*;
1867 Supplementary Fig. S42a-f).

1868 By contrast to state 1 common in Mantispoidea, the reduced sternum 9 is the specialized state,
1869 and apparently evolve independently in *Nallachus*, many genera of Berothidae, and some
1870 genera of †Paraberothinae. The sternum 9 may be lost or completely fused with sternum 9,
1871 leading to the large, paired, setose gonocoxites 9 exposed totally in †*Osmyloberotha*.

1872 188. Male gonocoxites 9:

1873 (0) not fused with gonocoxites 11;

1874 (1) fused with gonocoxites 11 (Supplementary Fig. S43i, j; occurring in Rhachiberothidae.
1875 Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 34a, b).

1876 189. Male gonocoxites 9:

1877 (0) bearing setae (Supplementary Fig. S42a-q);

1878 (1) glabrous (Supplementary Figs. S42r, S43-S46).

1879 The setose gonocoxites 9 generally occur in basal groups of Neuroptera, such as Nevrothidae,
1880 Osmylidae, Sisyridae, possibly representing the plesiomorphic state (Aspöck and Aspöck 2008).

1881 190. Male gonocoxites 9:

1882 (0) with sparse and long setae (Supplementary Fig. S42a-f; Li et al. (2020b): figs. 17-19);

1883 (1) without sparse and long setae (Supplementary Fig. S42g-k; Aspöck (1989): fig. 5; Monserrat
1884 (2006): fig. 12f).

1885 Character 190 is dependent on character 189.

1886 191. Male gonocoxites 9:

1887 (0) entirely well-sclerotized (Supplementary Figs. S42r, S43-S46);

1888 (1) partly membranous (Supplementary Fig. S42a-q; Monserrat (2006): fig. 12f; Li et al. (2018):
1889 figs. 35-37).

1890 192. Partly membranous male gonocoxites 9:

1891 (0) without;

1892 (1) with anterior sclerotized apodeme. The apodeme, a handle-like sclerite, is an autapomorphy
1893 of the Trichomatinae + Nosybinae + Berothinae (with a reversal in *Naizema*) (Aspöck and
1894 Nemeschkal 1998).

1895 This character is dependent on character 191.

1896 Male gonocoxites 9 in †*Osmyloberotha* and extant berothids except Cyrenoberothinae are
1897 enlarged, membranous and setose and in basal extant berothid groups, such as Nyrrminae,
1898 Protobiellinae and *Naizema* lack the sclerotized apodeme anterior to the membranous part of
1899 gonocoxites 9. Male gonocoxites 9 in remaining mantispoids are entirely sclerotized and
1900 glabrous in various shape (e.g., rod-shaped (Symphrasinae, †*Haploberotha*, †*Iceloberotha*,
1901 †*Jersiberotha*, etc.), bar-shaped (Drepanicinae, Calomantispinae, Mantispinae), T-shaped
1902 (*Cyrenoberotha*, *Nolima*), etc.). The well-sclerotized, setose male gonocoxites nine may
1903 represent a plesiomorphic state in Neuroptera, which is commonly found in Osmylidae,
1904 Nevrothidae and Sisyridae.

1905 193. Male gonocoxites 9 rod-like (slender, not broadened in any view):

1906 (0) absent;

1907 (1) present (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 34c, d).

1908 This character is dependent on character 184.

1909 194. Male gonocoxites 9 distally:

1910 (0) simple;

1911 (1) with hook-like processes (MacLeod and Adams (1967): fig. 8; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021):

1912 fig. 34e-h);

1913 (2) with digitiform processes (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 34c, d);

1914 (3) fused with each other (found in *Speleoberotha*; Machado et al. (2022): figs. 5D, E; 9D, E);

1915 (4) with many tiny processes (found in *Nolima*; Reynoso-Velasco and Contreras-Ramose (2019):

1916 fig. 8I).

1917 195. Male gonocoxites 10 (mediuncus):

1918 (0) present;

1919 (1) absent.

1920 196. Male gonocoxites 10 (mediuncus):

1921 (0) paired (Aspöck and Aspöck (2008): fig. 24);

1922 (1) unpaired.

1923 This character is dependent on character 190.

1924 197. Male gonostyli 10 (pseudopenis):

1925 (0) with slender and well-sclerotized base (observed in *Osmylus*; Aspöck and Aspöck (2008):

1926 fig. 24);

1927 (1) with thickened and well-sclerotized base (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 34c, d);

1928 (2) with membranous base (found in extant crown Mantispidae. Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021):

1929 fig. 34e-j);

1930 (3) possibly fused with gonocoxites 10 (Li et al. (2020b): figs. 28, 29).

1931 Male 10th sclerites in Mantispidae can be clearly divided into three separate portions associated

1932 by the broad to narrow membrane — “gonocoxites 10” (mediuncus), “gonapophyses 10”
1933 (hypomeres) and “gonostyli 10” (pseudopenis), while in Rhachiberothidae, there are only two
1934 10 sclerites retained. In Berothidae, these sclerites might be fused together as the
1935 gonocoxites+gonapophyses+gonostyli 10 complex (sensu indistinct base in Ardila-Camacho et
1936 al. (2021)), i.e., paramere-mediuncus complex (Aspöck and Nemeschkal 1998), but it can be
1937 also hypothesized that only gonostyli 10 left with thickened and well-sclerotized base similar to
1938 that of *Mucroberotha*, *Rhachiella*, Symphrasinae, †Doratomantispinae (such as in
1939 *Cyrenoberotha*, †*Dolichoberotha*, †*Iceloberotha*, †*Jersiberotha*, etc.).

1940 198. Male gonostyli 10 (pseudopenis):

1941 (0) present;

1942 (1) absent.

1943 199. Male gonostyli 10 (pseudopenis):

1944 (0) paired (Aspöck and Aspöck (2008): fig. 24);

1945 (1) unpaired.

1946 This character is dependent on character 198.

1947 200. Shape of male gonostyli 10:

1948 (0) bar-like (short, broad and not elongated; Aspöck (1989): fig. 6);

1949 (1) whip-like (long, slender and elongated, distally generally very acute; Supplementary Figs.

1950 S42r,

1951 S43a-f, S44g, k-m);

1952 (2) bristle-like (distally with a bunch of short to very long and thin bristle, commonly found in

1953 many extant berothids; Li et al. (2020b): fig. 28);

- 1954 (3) spinous (much shorter than the bar-like gonostyli 10, tapering distally to an acute point.
1955 Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 34e-j);
- 1956 (4) deeply bifurcate (Supplementary Fig. S43k-n; Aspöck and Aspöck (2008): fig. 32).
1957 This character is dependent on character 199.
- 1958 201. Bristle-like male gonostyli 10:
1959 (0) short and scattered (Wise (1992): figs. 4, 6; Aspöck and Aspöck (1984): figs. 2-4);
1960 (1) long and bundled (Aspöck (1983): figs. 23, 32, 34; Li et al. (2020b): fig. 28).
1961 The bristles at the distal end of the gonocoxites+gonapophyses+gonostyli 10 (paramere-
1962 mediuncus) complex are a synapomorphy of the Protobiellinae + Trichomatinae + Nosybinae +
1963 Berothinae.
- 1964 202. Formations of bristles:
1965 (0) straight (Wise (1992): figs. 4, 6; Aspöck and Aspöck (1985): figs. 2-4);
1966 (1) thread-like (Aspöck and Aspöck (1982): figs. 23, 32, 34); (2) simple bow (Li et al. (2020b):
1967 fig. 28);
1968 (3) looped (Aspöck and Aspöck (1996): figs. 7, 23).
- 1969 203. Whip-like male gonostyli 10 (i.e., penisfilum) basally:
1970 (0) curved dorsad (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 34a; (Li et al. 2022): fig. 6d-e);
1971 (1) curved ventrad (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 34c).
1972 Characters 201-203 are dependent on character 200.
- 1973 204. Male gonapophyses 10 (hypomeres):
1974 (0) absent;
1975 (1) present.

1976 205. Male gonapophyses 10 (hypomeres):

1977 (0) long, developed (Supplementary Figs. S44k-p, S45a-e; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig.

1978 34c, d; Li et al. (2022): figs. 6d, e, 25a);

1979 (1) shortened, sometimes reduced (Supplementary Fig. S46e-g, i, k, l-m; Ardila-Camacho et al.

1980 (2021): fig. 34e-h).

1981 This character is dependent on character 204.

1982 Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021) only interpreted hypomeres in Symphrasinae as gonapophyses 10

1983 in Mantispoidea, while compared their position (located at the membranous part distolateral to

1984 mediuncus) with that of the hypomeres in other mantispids, we consider the latter are

1985 homologous to the former and can be also termed “gonapophyses 10”. The gonapophyses 10

1986 are generally long and developed in Symphrasinae (rod-like) and †Doratomantispinae (long and

1987 broadened in †*Doratomantispa*, rod-like in †*Paradoxomantispa*), while reduced into short,

1988 small processes in various shapes (ball-like, strip-like, horn-like etc.) and or as setose

1989 membrane (possibly absent) in Drepanicinae, Calomantispinae and Mantispinae. This structure

1990 is absent or possibly fused with other 10th sclerites in Berothidae, †Dipteromantispidae and

1991 Rhachiberothidae.

1992 206. Male callus cerci:

1993 (0) present;

1994 (1) absent.

1995 207. Ventromedial lobe of male ectoprocts:

1996 (0) absent;

1997 (1) present (Supplementary Fig. S46m; Machado and Rafael (2010): fig. 4d).

- 1998 This structure is observed in most mantispine genera (absent in *Campion*), usually bearing
1999 many thickened, spinous setae.
- 2000 208. Male gonocoxites 11:
2001 (0) present;
2002 (1) absent.
- 2003 209. Male gonocoxites 11:
2004 (0) paired (the autapomorphy of *Cyrenoberotha* MacLeod and Adams (1967): figs. 8, 9);
2005 (1) unpaired.
- 2006 This character is dependent on character 208.
- 2007 210. Male gonocoxites 11 posteromedially:
2008 (0) without processes (Machado et al. (2022): figs. 5E, 6D);
2009 (1) with processes (one or two posteromedial processes usually present in Mantispidae and
2010 Symphrasinae, sometimes also found in some berothids, e.g., †*Cornoberotha*, *Nosybus* and
2011 *Tanzanberotha*).
- 2012 This character is dependent on character 209.
- 2013 211. Crumena on female sternum 7 (the small or enlarged pouch-like cavity located medially on
2014 the female sternum 7, only found in *Drepanicus*, *Gerstaeckerella* and *Theristria* (Lambkin
2015 (1986a): fig. 252; Liu et al. (2015): fig. 10B, E)):
2016 (0) absent;
2017 (1) present.
- 2018 212. Crumena:
2019 (0) unpaired;

- 2020 (1) paired.
- 2021 This character is dependent on character 211.
- 2022 213. Female sternum 7:
- 2023 (0) unpaired, semiannular;
- 2024 (1) bilobed, but posterior margin distinctly fused;
- 2025 (2) divided into a pair of lateral sclerites (gonocoxites 7?).
- 2026 The semiannular sternum 7 is plesiomorphic, and the sagittally divided sternum 7 consisting of a
- 2027 pair of lateral sclerites is apomorphic and evolved independently in *Hozelella*, *Rhachiberotha*,
- 2028 *Spiroberotha* and *Lomamyia*+ *Lekrugeria*-group. with a reversal to state (1) in. The intermediate
- 2029 step with a posteriorly bilobed seventh sternum occurs in *Austroberothella*, *Nodalla*, *Nosybus*
- 2030 and *Mucroberotha* (Aspöck and Nemeschkal 1998), (Aspöck and Aspöck 2008), (Ardila-
- 2031 Camacho et al. 2021).
- 2032 214. Posterior region of female sternum 7, a pair of sclerite disks (gonapophyses 7?):
- 2033 (0) absent;
- 2034 (1) present.
- 2035 The paired, hairless sclerite disks are apomorphic, occurring in *Spiroberotha*, *Lomamyia*,
- 2036 *Berotha*, and the *Isoscelipteron*-group (Aspöck and Nemeschkal 1998), (Aspöck and Randolph
- 2037 2014).
- 2038 215. Female gonocoxites 8:
- 2039 (0) paired;
- 2040 (1) unpaired;
- 2041 (2) absent.

- 2042 216. Female gonapophyses 8:
- 2043 (0) not fused with gonocoxites 8;
- 2044 (1) fused with gonocoxites 8;
- 2045 (2) absent.
- 2046 217. Female gonapophyses 8:
- 2047 (0) paired;
- 2048 (1) unpaired.
- 2049 This character is dependent on character 216.
- 2050 218. Female tergum 9 and ectoprocts:
- 2051 (0) separate;
- 2052 (1) fused (The fusion of tergum 9 and ectoprocts possibly evolving independently in
- 2053 Mantispoidea; Supplementary Fig. S51a-h, n, o).
- 2054 219. Female pseudohypocaudae:
- 2055 (0) absent;
- 2056 (1) present.
- 2057 The pseudohypocaudae appear to be a ventral modification of the female tergum 9, i.e., the
- 2058 tergum 9 with ventral region detached/separated in Lambkin (1986a).
- 2059 220. Female pseudohypocaudae:
- 2060 (0) not produced ventrad (Lambkin (1986a): fig. 237);
- 2061 (1) shortly produced ventrad (Aspöck and Mansell (1994): figs. 14, 33, 44);
- 2062 (2) strongly produced ventrad (Supplementary Fig. S52i-p; Nakamine et al. (2022): fig. 4).
- 2063 This character is dependent on character 219.

- 2064 221. Branched female pseudohypocaudae:
- 2065 (0) absent;
- 2066 (1) present (found in *Rhachiella* Aspöck et al. (2020): figs. 8, 9).
- 2067 This character is dependent on character 220.
- 2068 222. Female gonocoxites 9:
- 2069 (0) loose, not adjoining closely (there are a broad space between gonocoxites 9; Ardila-
- 2070 Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 35b, f, h, j);
- 2071 (1) adjoining closely (the space between gonocoxites 9 in ventral view is extremely narrow or
- 2072 undetectable. Supplementary Figs. S51g-m, S53e, g-i, k; Tjeder (1959): figs. 265-267; Ardila-
- 2073 Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 35d).
- 2074 223. Female gonocoxites 9:
- 2075 (0) not entirely elongated;
- 2076 (1) entirely elongated anteriorly (Supplementary Fig. S51g-m; Aspöck and Aspöck (1982): figs. 2,
- 2077 5, 14);
- 2078 (2) entirely elongated posteriorly, not long ovipositor-like (Supplementary Fig. S53e, g);
- 2079 (3) entirely elongated posteriorly, not long ovipositor-like (Supplementary Fig. S53h, i, k; Ardila-
- 2080 Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 12b).
- 2081 224. Female gonocoxites 9:
- 2082 (0) not produced;
- 2083 (1) anteroventrally produced as hypocaudae.
- 2084 225. Length of hypocaudae:
- 2085 (0) short (distinctly shorter than the main portion of gonocoxites 9. [Aspöck and Aspöck

2086 (1984)]: figs. 6, 7);

2087 (1) long (nearly as long as the main portion of gonocoxites 9. Supplementary Fig. S51a, e;

2088 Faulkner (1992): figs. 14-26);

2089 (2) extremely long (over twice as long as the main portion of gonocoxites 9. Supplementary Fig.

2090 S52i-p).

2091 This character is dependent on character 224.

2092 The hypocausta refers to the slender process anteroventrally on each female gonocoxite 9,

2093 varying from being very short to extremely long. The long (nearly as long as the main portion

2094 of gonocoxites 9) and extremely long (over twice as long as main portion of gonocoxites 9)

2095 hypocaustae are only observed in †*Osmyloberotha*, †*Elektroberotha*, Berothinae and two extinct

2096 rhachiberothid genera †*Dicranoberotha* and †*Paradoxoberotha*, while in other mantispoids, if

2097 present, this process is distinctly shorter than the main portion of gonocoxites 9. According to

2098 our present study, the gonocoxites 9 of †*Ansoberotha*, †*Cantabroberotha*, †*Cornoberotha*,

2099 †*Dolichoberotha* and †*Magniberotha* should be entirely elongated anteriorly and adjoined closely

2100 as those in *Nosybus*, rather than produced anteroventrally as the paired hypocaustae as

2101 interpreted in the previous study (Yuan et al. 2016), (Yang et al. 2020).

2102 226. Female gonapophyses 9:

2103 (0) paired (Supplementary Figs. S57c, f, n, S58a, b, e, g, j, S59b, d, f, i, n);

2104 (1) unpaired (Supplementary Figs. S56c, S58o);

2105 (2) absent.

2106 227. Ventral projection of female ectoprocts:

2107 (0) absent;

2108 (1) present.

2109 228. Length of ventral projection of female ectoprocts:

2110 (0) short (Supplementary Fig. S54i, j; Lambkin (1986a): fig. 268; Li et al. (2022): figs. 10c, d,
2111 14e, f);

2112 (1) long (Supplementary Fig. S54l, m; a possible autapomorphic character of
2113 †*Acanthomantispa*). This character is dependent on character 227.

2114 229. Female callus cerci:

2115 (0) present (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 35a, e, g);

2116 (1) absent.

2117 230. Female spermatheca coiled and tubular shape:

2118 (0) absent;

2119 (1) present (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 36a-e).

2120 231. Ball-like accessory gland of spermatheca (an enlarged accessory portion of spermatheca,
2121 possibly independently evolving in Berothidae, Rhachiberothidae and Calomantispinae):

2122 (0) absent;

2123 (1) present (Aspöck and Aspöck (1984): figs. 24, 25; Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 36a, d).

2124 232. Female fertilization canal (a much broader, usually opaque structure surrounded by a halo of
2125 minute strands (fine cuticular ducts from a glandular epithelium) and distally with a knob-like
2126 projection, connecting the termination of spermatheca with a very narrow duct (Lambkin 1986a),
2127 observed in Mantispoidea):

2128 (0) absent;

2129 (1) present (Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): fig. 36a-e).

2130

2131

2132 **Supplementary Appendix4. Mantispoidea Phylogeny**

2133

2134 The present phylogenetic analysis aims to reconstruct the phylogenetic relationship among
2135 all families of Mantispoidea and that among subfamilies within Berothidae, Rhachiberothidae, and
2136 Mantispidae based on large-scale morphological data. Our data matrix was established according
2137 to direction examination of the specimens we examined, with a few data obtained from other
2138 literatures (see Supplementary Appendix 3).

2139 An increasing number of studies have advocated for the direct incorporation of fossil records
2140 into traditional phylogenetic approaches, alongside extant taxa, to better understand the process of
2141 macroevolution(Quental and Marshall 2010, Hunt and Slater 2016, Louca and Pennell 2020, Koch
2142 et al. 2021). This strategy can enhance the accuracy of phylogenetic inferences and topological
2143 resolution, increase the reliability of estimating of divergence time and other macroevolutionary
2144 parameters, and ultimately help to faithfully reconstruct evolutionary history over long geological
2145 time scales, even when highly fragmentary. We conducted a total of 15 phylogenetic analyses
2146 using three distinct morphological matrices. Each matrix consisted of 232 morphological
2147 characters but was combined with different taxa counts: 146, 132 (after removing three dubious
2148 fossil taxa and all heavily fragmented fossils described only by isolated wings), and 143 (only
2149 removing the three dubious taxa). Our analyses included: (i) six maximum parsimony analyses,
2150 conducted under both traditional and new technology search methods (labelled MP1-3T/N), (ii)
2151 six maximum likelihood analyses using the models “MK+FQ+ASC+R3” and “MK+FQ+ASC+G4”
2152 (labelled ML1-3R3/G4), (iii) three Bayesian inferences (labelled BI1-3). The parsimony analyses
2153 generated ten most-parsimonious trees under the traditional search, and five or six most-

2154 parsimonious trees under the new technology search (MP1-3T/N: tree length = 964, 941, 948 steps,
2155 consistency index CI = 0.350, 0.358, 0.355 and retention index RI = 0.856, 0.856, 0.859). Under
2156 the traditional search method, the tree resolution is better.

2157 In this study, the adoption of different methods, as well as the inclusion of dubious taxa and
2158 those described only by forewing, have little impact on the family- and higher-level phylogenetic
2159 topology, while the subfamilial and generic relationships may be unstable to different degrees,
2160 even resulting in the paraphyly of Rhachiberothidae (BI3). The dubious taxa and those described
2161 only by isolated wings impact the maximum parsimony analysis more seriously than statistics-
2162 based methods, inevitably leading to a significant decrease in both bootstrap and Bremer values,
2163 and negatively altering the topological resolution of the MP consensus tree in general. The
2164 increase in missing data is an important contributor to these changes.

2165 Berothidae is known for some members with scale-like setae caused by secretion on the
2166 female wings (the origin of the term “beaded”). This family presently comprises 119 extant
2167 species in 26 genera distributed worldwide plus 67 extinct species in 39 genera from Middle-Late
2168 Triassic to Eocene. It includes six valid extant subfamilies, i.e., Nyrminae, Cyrenoberothinae,
2169 Protobiellinae, Nosybinae, Trichomatinae and Berothinae, and one extinct subfamily
2170 †Mesithoninae from Upper Jurassic to Lower Cretaceous (Aspöck and Randolph 2014),(Li et al.
2171 2020a, Machado et al. 2022, Oswald 2022, Khramov 2023), with most fossil taxa lacking
2172 definitive subfamilial placement.

2173 The current comprehensive morphology-based phylogeny is the first attempt to investigate
2174 the intrarelations of Berothidae by incorporating a diverse range of fossil taxa, calling into the
2175 question about the monophyly of this family, along with the lack of supported reliable family-level

2176 synapomorphies (Supplementary Figs. S3-S5, S60, S61). Previous studies have reached an
2177 implicit agreement on including all cursorial mantispoids and the majority of those described
2178 solely from compressed wing fossils into this family (Engel and Grimaldi 2008, Makarkin et al.
2179 2011, Aspöck and Randolph 2014, Engel et al. 2018, Yang et al. 2020, Lu and Liu 2021, Machado et
2180 al. 2022). However, despite performing simple morphological comparisons, none of them have
2181 rigorously tested this hypothesis under a comprehensive phylogeny of the entire superfamily.
2182 Interestingly, the recent morphological phylogenetic work (Machado et al. 2022) mentioned that
2183 the raptorial mantispoids (*Mantispa* or *Rhachiberothera* + (*Trichoscelia* + *Mucroberothera*)) as the
2184 outgroup can be deeply nested within Berothidae when analyzed with fossil berothid genera.
2185 However, the authors eventually removed *Mantispa* from the analysis and accepted the result with
2186 high constant k values, which supported the monophyly of Berothidae. Our study demonstrates
2187 that the characters which were previously used to classify species as Berothidae are recognized as
2188 either plesiomorphies of Mantispoidea, such as the long creeping CuA and CuP veins (char. 176:1,
2189 180:1, 181:1), or the synapomorphies of specific clades, such as the paired large hairy tubercles
2190 (char. 15: 1, 16:1), scale-like setae (char. 19:1, 37:1, 120:1) and female hypocaustae (char. 224: 1)
2191 (mainly found in BM1). Most of these characters can be inherited by or evolved independently in
2192 raptorial mantispoids (e.g., Rhachiberotheridae, Symphrasinae and many other extinct mantispids).

2193 †*Nascimberothera* has unstable placement, either assigned as the sister to †*Osmyloberothera* or to
2194 †*Banoherothera*+ †Berothidae indeterminate² in BM2. However, we still question the supra-family
2195 level placement of †*Nascimberothera*, because this genus has two R sectors which is never found in
2196 all other mantispoids (only one R sectors) (Grimaldi (2000): Fig. 21), but commonly observed in
2197 Dilaridae and Hemerobiidae (Liu et al. 2016, Breitzkreuz et al. 2017).

2198 Nyrminae was identified as the most basal extant group of Mantispoidea, rather than being
2199 basal to BM1 or a sister group to Cyrenoberothinae, as suggested in previous studies (Aspöck and
2200 Randolph 2014, Machado et al. 2022). Currently, we struggled to find convincing synapomorphies
2201 to support these previously proposed relationships, when examining the phylogeny in terms of the
2202 entire superfamily. This subfamily is distinctive within Mantispoidea, particularly due to its more
2203 jagged, and even reticular forewing venations (Supplementary Fig. S31a, b), with some members
2204 originally assigned in Hemerobiidae. Its male genitalia with large setose membranous gonocoxites
2205 9, as that in BM1, may represent a plesiomorphic character of Mantispoidea, which is also
2206 definitively observed in †*Osmyloberotha* (Supplementary Fig. S42a-f). The phylogeny of BM1
2207 were not well-resolved on the relationships of Nosybinae and Trichomatinae, as well as the
2208 placement of *Naizema* and †*Xenoberotha*. It is unexpected and controversial that the Berothinae
2209 affinity of †*Elektroberotha* and †*Xenoberotha* was rejected herein, which was mainly supported by
2210 the presence of scale-like setae and their female genitalia structure resembling Berothinae in the
2211 previous studies (Makarkin and Ohl 2015, Makarkin 2017). The unstable placement of
2212 †*Xenoberotha* is highly likely to result from the limited morphological information, requiring
2213 additional materials for further clarification, but †*Elektroberotha* were stably recovered as the
2214 basal most lineage of BM1, on which one homoplasious character state, the very short hind wing
2215 CuP stem (char. 178:1), was identified to support the separation of remaining BM1 genera from
2216 †*Elektroberotha* (long and deep hind wing CuP, char. 178:0). Additionally, all analyses recovered
2217 *Spiroberotha* as the basalmost group to Berothinae, consistent with the treatment in Adams (1989)
2218 and Makarkin and Ohl (2015), and the elongated scape (4-5× length of pedicel, char. 10:2) were
2219 identified to support this relationship, although it can be reshortened within Berothinae.

2220 Our results have ignited the debate on the placement of †*Berotherone*, †*Khasurtoberotha* and
2221 †*Mesithone*, suggesting their assignment to Mantispidae. This issue has consistently been debated
2222 due to these taxa being typically described from incomplete compressed forewing fossils.
2223 Although their berotherid affinity has been widely accepted, some authors have indeed recognized
2224 the forewing venation of †Mesithoninae as being similar to that of †Mesomantispinae, such as the
2225 long and complexly branched recurrent humeral crossvein, general structure of Rs and M, etc.
2226 (Makarkin et al. 2012, Jepson 2015). Some authors have even synonymized †Mesomantispinae
2227 with †Mesithoninae (Khramov 2013). Additionally, two other pieces of evidence further supported
2228 the mantispid affinity of these three genera in the present study. The discovery of
2229 †*Mesomantispoides* (Supplementary Figs. S1f, S2f, g, S11g, S36g, h) and the undescribed species
2230 that was recorded as a berotherid in Kopylov et al. (2021): fig. 39g directly indicate the existence of
2231 a phenotype that combined mesithone-like wings, mantispid-like prothorax, and raptorial forelegs.
2232 Moreover, the PERMANOVA and GDEM analyses showed that the PW morphospace between
2233 these three taxa and Mantispidae was insignificantly different, and had more overlap than with
2234 Berotheridae (Supplementary Tables 6, 7).

2235 The identification of the closest berotherid relative to raptorial Mantispoidea, i.e.,
2236 Cyrenoberothinae together with the majority of fossil berotherids (C+BM2), is a completely new
2237 and unexpected result that has never been mentioned or focused on before, as all previous studies
2238 tended to investigate the status of these berotherids under the assumption of a monophyletic
2239 Berotheridae. This finding inspires us to detect some essential differences in their genitalia structure
2240 from that of other berotherids with known genitalia, involving male gonocoxites 9 glabrous (char.
2241 189:1) and entirely well-sclerotized (char. 191:0, a reversal) (setose (char. 189:0) and membranous

2242 (char. 191:0), sometimes with the anterior sclerotized apodeme (char. 192:1, in derived clades of
2243 BM1), in other berothids); frequent presence of whip-like male gonostyli 10 (char. 200: 2),
2244 especially in extinct taxa (bristle-like (char. 200:1) or bar-like (char. 200:0), absolutely not whip-
2245 like in other berothids) and the presence of paired female gonapophyses 9 (char. 226:0, a reversal)
2246 (unpaired or absent (char. 226:1, 2) in other berothids). Interestingly, all of these features are also
2247 commonly found in raptorial Mantispoidea. Additionally, the parsimony analyses also indicates
2248 that the stable presence of two ra-rp crossveins in the forewing (char. 141:1) and the distal ra-rp
2249 positioned proximad to the distal fusion point of ScP and RA (char. 142:1), might be another two
2250 homoplasious character states supporting this unexpected relationship as well, which commonly
2251 occurs in C+BM2 and Rhachiberothidae (the basal lineage of raptorial Mantispoidea), but very
2252 rare in other berothids (three or more, and usually with distal one distad the fusion point of ScP
2253 and RA). Moreover, it is noteworthy that †*Archarhachiberotha* exactly exhibits the intermediate
2254 phenotype between C+BM2 berothids and raptorial Mantispoidea (namely combining the general
2255 C+BM2 berothid or Rhachiberothidea appearance with a primitive raptorial foreleg (slightly
2256 incrassated profemur bearing extremely tiny ISSs) representing the transition from cursorial to
2257 typical raptorial forms) (Wang et al. 2024). This finding provides the direct evidence for
2258 understanding the newly identified evolutionary pathway from berothids to raptorial Mantispoidea.

2259 †*Araripeberotha* and †*Caririberotha* were clustered with *Cyrenoberotha* and *Mansellibertha*
2260 by most analyses if well-resolved, while *Speleoberotha* sometimes could be grouped with
2261 †*Microberotha* and †*Sibelliberotha* within BM2 (Fig. 2; Supplementary Figs. S3c, S4c, S5c). The
2262 relationship between Cyrenoberothinae and BM2 is still unstable (unresolved in MP, paraphyletic
2263 in ML and MB, forming a monophyly in time-calibrated tree), requiring further clarification.

2264 Notably, the Cretaceous long-antenna berothids (†*Ansoberotha*, †*Cornoberotha* and
2265 †*Dolichoberotha*, ACD) were recovered as a high monophyletic lineage of BM2, and therefore,
2266 their apomorphic characters shared with higher subfamilies of BM1 (e.g., Nosybinae and
2267 Berothinae) resulted from convergent evolution, which includes slightly falcate wing apex (char.
2268 133: 1) and the entirely anteriorly elongated (char. 223:1), tight-closed (char. 222:1) gonocoxites 9
2269 (always misinterpreted as hypocaustae and also occurring in their related lineages, see details in
2270 Supplementary Appendix 3). Additionally, the male genitalia structure of ACD obviously belongs
2271 to the type in BM2 rather than in BM1 (Supplementary Figs. S42r, S43a-h, S48c-g).

2272 Although all our phylogenetic analyses and some morphological evidence support the
2273 paraphyly of Berothidae, we still retain the original taxonomic status of this family and do not
2274 conduct any formal treatments. This is due to the relationships among key berothid lineages being
2275 either not or weakly supported by different analyses and the limited morphological information of
2276 berothids used for the present analyses: (i) systematically valuable characters fewer (mainly from
2277 wings and genitalia) than those of raptorial Mantispoidea, (ii) incomplete preservation of type
2278 specimens of some genera (usually only with forewings well-preserved or even worse), (iii) the
2279 shortage of specimen examinations (a lot of berothid morphological data extracted directly from
2280 brief and inaccurate original descriptions and drawings, and most fossil genera described only
2281 from a single type specimen). Also due to (i)-(iii), the key to fossil berothid genera here was
2282 tentatively compiled mainly in light of limited forewing characters, needing more revisions. In the
2283 future, additional materials and examinations for revision and extending the current morphological
2284 dataset, necessarily integrating large molecular data, would hopefully reconstruct a more
2285 convincing phylogenetic framework for berothids, powerfully determine the placement of the

2286 questionable genera and improve the key in this study.

2287 Raptorial Mantispoidea was recovered as a monophyletic group by all analyses, resolved as
2288 †*Archarhachiberotha*+ (Rhachiberothidae+ (†Dipteromantispidae+ Mantispidae)). Five characters
2289 were identified as possible synapomorphies (all homologous) supporting this relationship: (i) the
2290 presence of raptorial foreleg (41:1), (ii) the elongation of procoxa (42:1), (iii) incrassate profemur
2291 (47:1), (iv) the presence of profemoral ventral integumentary specializations (54:1), (v) protibia
2292 curved near the joint with profemur (81:1). The monophyly of the clade Rhachiberothidae+
2293 (†Dipteromantispidae+ Mantispidae) is supported by following homologous and homoplasious
2294 character states: (i-ii) filiform antenna (8:0, 9:0, homoplasious), (iii) scape distally swollen (11:0,
2295 homoplasious), (iv) shortened protibia ($3/4-2/3 \times$ length of profemur, 79:2, homoplasious), (v)
2296 protibia medially curved (82:1, homologous), (vi) the presence of profemoral ventral keel (83:1,
2297 homologous), (vii) hind wing 1rp-m sigmoid (171:0, homoplasious). Meanwhile, maximum
2298 parsimony analyses display inconsistencies in identifying characters (iii) and (vii) as
2299 synapomorphies.

2300 The modern fauna of Rhachiberothidae is relict and restricted to Sub-Saharan Africa, with 14
2301 species in four genera, all of which belong to the subfamily Rhachiberothinae (Aspöck et al. 2020).
2302 However, the abundant fossil records, particularly from various Cretaceous amber deposits,
2303 suggests a once high diversity for this family, in which there are 23 species in 18 genera from
2304 Cretaceous period classified into †Paraberothinae, two species in the genus †*Whalfera* Makarkin
2305 & Kupryjanowicz assigned to Rhachiberothinae and three genera with four species without
2306 subfamilial determination. Herein, we tentatively accept the monophyly of this family which was
2307 recovered as a basal lineage of Mantispoidea second to †*Archarhachiberotha*, based on our most

2308 phylogenetic analyses, although weakly or moderately supported (only the MB analysis based on
2309 143×232 matrix recovered the paraphyletic Rhachiberothidae) (Supplementary Figs. S3-5, S60,
2310 S61).

2311 Our study suggests that the similarities between Berothidae and Rhachiberothidae represent
2312 the plesiomorphies of Neuroptera or synapomorphies of Mantispoidea, which are inappropriate to
2313 be treated as synapomorphies to support the close relationship of the two families in the previous
2314 research (Aspöck and Mansell 1994), (Makarkin and Kupryjanowicz 2010). For example, the
2315 pronotum prolonged anteriorly on forelegs also occurs in †Dipteromantispidae and is not a distinctive
2316 character of Mantispoidea. This character is commonly observed in the lower to the higher
2317 lacewing lineages to various degree in fact, representing a plesiomorphic state of Neuroptera. The
2318 presence of female pseudohypocaudae has been clarified to evolve independently multiple times
2319 across Berothidae, Rhachiberothidae, †Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae, indicating the
2320 convergent evolution under the similar reproductive pressure.

2321 Other characters, including the elongation of larval postlabium, cylindrical larval antenna and
2322 long tubular spermatophores, although not included in the present study, may also represent the
2323 synapomorphic state of Mantispoidea. Previous studies that predominantly compared these
2324 characters in the highly derived Mantispinae with Berothidae and Rhachiberothidae may lead to
2325 less complete and convincing results. Actually, some of these characters or their intermediate
2326 types have been observed in lower extant mantispids, such as, subcylindrical larval antenna in
2327 *Ditaxis biseriata* (Westwood) and long tubular spermatophores in symphrasines (Dorey and
2328 Merritt 2017), (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021), let alone there are a great many extinct and extant
2329 taxa with these characters unknown.

2330 Unfortunately, the subfamily-level relationships within this family were failed to resolve
2331 presently, with two completely different results interpreted by different datasets and methods,
2332 which should be ascribed to the limited morphological information (specimen examinations only
2333 for the species from Myanmar amber, as well as brief or inaccurate original descriptions and
2334 drawings), and therefore, we do not perform any taxonomic treatments at the subfamily level here.
2335 Apart from the MP2-3 and ML1R3 recovering monophyletic †Paraberothinae plus PD clade as the
2336 sister to †*Oisea* plus Rhachiberothinae, most results recovered the paraphyletic †Paraberothinae,
2337 which was dissolved into a large monophyletic clade generally containing those genera with adult
2338 protarsomeres 1-2 distodorsally and ventrally bearing specialized setae (R1), †*Astioberotha* and
2339 †*Chimerhaberotha* clustered with the PD clade (R2), as well as †*Raptorapax* and †*Spinoberotha*
2340 grouped with †*Oisea*+Rhachiberothinae (R3). Notably, †*Alboberotha* could be resolved as the
2341 basal group of either R1 clade or R3 clade, and only ML3G4 assigned †*Micromantispa* as the
2342 sister to †*Astioberotha* in R3 clade.

2343 These two results lead to two suites of possible synapomorphies that were identified to
2344 support the monophyly of Rhachiberothidae. Both are supported by two homoplasious character
2345 states: char. 15: 1, the presence of vertexal tubercles and char. 56:1, the presence of thorn-shape
2346 ISs on profemur. The result supporting monophyletic †Paraberothinae detected another three
2347 homologous character states: char. 92:1, male probasitarsus distally slightly produced, bearing a
2348 long, specialized setae (char. 96:1), and char. 188:1, male gonocoxites 9 fused with gonocoxites 11.
2349 The result supporting paraphyletic †Paraberothinae detected another three homoplasious character
2350 states: char. 57:1, the presence of saber-shaped ISs on profemur, char. 101:2, probasitarsus
2351 ventrally with only one specialized seta and char. 141:1, forewing with two ra-rp crossveins.

2352 Future comprehensive revision on the species from non-Burmese amber will be the key to address
2353 the intrarelationships of Rhachiberothidae thoroughly.

2354 The enigmatic Cretaceous raptorial family †Dipteromantispidae can be easily characterized
2355 by its strikingly dipteran-like appearance, with highly reduced forewing venation and haltere-like
2356 hind wings. It now includes 13 species in nine genera (Azar et al. 2020, Li et al. 2020c). The
2357 forewing CuA, CuP and A1 originating from R stem in †*Jersimantispa* is weird and completely
2358 different from all other dipteromantispids, even never found in other mantispoids, and therefore
2359 may be a misinterpretation. In addition to †*Mantispidiptera*, after examining the holotype of †*M.*
2360 *enigmatica*, the forewing RP drawn in Grimaldi (2000) has its base separate from RA, and this is
2361 now confirmed as a misinterpretation, whose case is the same as other dipteromantispids (MA
2362 described in Grimaldi (2000) is here interpreted as the primary branch of RP based on Breitkreuz
2363 et al. (2017)). We described two new genera and three species in this study based on their several
2364 morphological differences and our phylogenetic results (Supplementary Figs. S3-S5, S60, S61):
2365 †*Enigmadipteromantispa dilatata* and †*Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* represent the intermediate
2366 lineages with unstable phylogenetic placement, and thus we cannot definitely combine them as
2367 one genus or into other known genera currently, awaiting further investigations and confirmations;
2368 †*Kurtodipteromantispa univenula* together with †*K. xiai* and †*K. zhuodei* as a monophyletic group
2369 was supported by most analyses, though weakly. Only MP analyses cannot successfully resolve
2370 their relationships, recovering them in a polytomy with a monophyletic group including
2371 †*Burmodipteromantispa*, †*Dipteromantispa*, †*Halteriomantispa*, †*Mantispidiptera* and
2372 †*Mantispidipterella*.

2373 Obviously, the high specialization of this family is the main source of difficulty in

2374 understanding the systematic position of this family. Similar to the case in Berothidae, our study
2375 indicates that all characters supporting †Dipteromantispidae to be either allied with
2376 Rhachiberothidae or be a more basal group were identified as plesiomorphies of Mantispoidea or
2377 raptorial Mantispoidea, such as, shield-shaped pronotum, prothorax not elongated posteriorly, the
2378 procoxal insertion, broad postfurcasternum, and keeled protibia with a row of specialized setae,
2379 etc., or convergent synapomorphies that evolved multiple times independently in Mantispoidea,
2380 such as female pseudohypocaudae (e.g., †*Elektroberotha*, †*Spiroberotha*, †*Aggregataberotha*,
2381 *Cyrenoberotha*, †*Haploberotha*, †*Cornoberotha*, Rhachiberothidae, †Dipteromantispidae,
2382 *Theristria*) and hypocaudae (†*Osmyloberotha*, BM1 except *Nosybus*, Rhachiberothinae, PD clade,
2383 †*Dipteromantispa*, †*Halteriomantispa*) (Makarkin et al. 2013, Li et al. 2020c, Ardila-Camacho et
2384 al. 2021). Although all the results are congruent with †Dipteromantispidae sister to Mantispidae,
2385 there are only a few synapomorphies identified that weakly or moderately support this relationship:
2386 distally swollen scape (11:1), reduced and shortened body hair (head and thorax) (24:1, 40:1), the
2387 absence of prothoracic furrows (18:1) as seen in Berothidae and Rhachiberothidae. The lowest
2388 lineage, †*Paradipteromantispa*, exhibits more plesiomorphic character states in its forewing,
2389 which is similar to basal mantispid genera, such as the shape, strongly dilated costal space, more
2390 complex venations, and more developed trichosors, seemingly indicating that this genus represents
2391 a remnant during the process towards morphological specialization of †Dipteromantispidae. We
2392 believe the discovery of additional fossil materials, particularly more intermediate lineages
2393 between this family and the most recent common ancestor of it and Mantispidae, would eventually
2394 span this confounding morphological gap.

2395 Although the monophyly of this genus is weakly supported by all ML and MB analyses, there

2396 is no synapomorphies found to further support this relationship currently, and all known key
2397 diagnostic characters of this genus have been clarified to be shared with either lower lineages (e.g.,
2398 ScP distally abruptly curved toward proximad scp-r) or higher lineages (e.g., the absence of
2399 forewing trichosors), being a mosaic state. Future deeper and more comprehensive morphological
2400 study for this genus should be concentrated on this problem to further confirm its monophyly and
2401 placement.

2402 Mantispidae resembles praying mantises more closely than other raptorial Mantispoidea with
2403 their prothorax elongated posterior to the insertion of the procoxa (to varying degrees), highly
2404 mobile. It represents the largest mantispoid family including about 395 extant species in 44 genera
2405 distributed worldwide and 50 extinct species in 34 genera from Lower Jurassic to Miocene,
2406 traditionally divided into two extinct subfamilies: †Mesomantispinae from Upper Jurassic to
2407 Lower Cretaceous and †Doratomantispinae solely from mid-Cretaceous Myanmar amber, and four
2408 extant subfamilies: Symphrasinae, Drepanicinae, Calomantispinae and Mantispinae (the former
2409 three with relict distribution, and the latter one cosmopolitan with the highest extant diversity in
2410 Mantispoidea) (Snyman et al. 2017, Lu et al. 2020, Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021, Li et al. 2022,
2411 Oswald 2022).

2412 Our present study recovered the monophyly of Mantispidae, mostly with moderate to strong
2413 support. At most ten possible synapomorphies were identified to support this relationship: (i) toruli
2414 located at the level near middle of the inner margin of eyes (2:1), (ii) shortened antenna (shorter
2415 than half length of forewing) (7:1), (iii) distinct coronal suture (17:0), (iv) prothorax slightly
2416 elongated posterior to the procoxal insertion (namely large distance between postfurcasternum and
2417 the procoxal insertion) (26:1), (v) the presence of probasitarsal ventral specialized setae (98:1), (vi)

2418 complicatedly branched humeral recurrent vein (132:0), (vii) the presence of male gonapophyses
2419 10 (hypomeres) (204:0), (viii) the presence of posteromedial process of male gonocoxites 11
2420 (210:1), (ix) female ectoprocts separate from tergum 9 (218:0), (x) the absence of female
2421 pseudohypocaudae (219:0). When considering more taxa described only from isolated wings, the
2422 number of these possible synapomorphies decreases, and there are another two detected: three ra-
2423 rp crossveins in the forewing, with the distal one distad the fusion point of ScP and RA (or the
2424 position that ScP is distally curved toward RA). Only character (iv) is homologous and others
2425 have evolved independently multiple times in Mantispoidea. Mantispidae herein consists of the
2426 basal lineages which comprise mesomantipine genera, †*Berotherone*, †*Khasurtoberotha* and
2427 †*Mesithone*, Symphrasinae including †*Sinomesomantispa*, †Doratomantispinae, Drepanicinae,
2428 Calomantispinae, Mantispinae and three important intermediate lineages: †*Mesomantispoides*,
2429 †*Haplacantha* and †*Aragomantispa* (Supplementary Figs. S3-S5, S60, S61).

2430 We support the hypothesis of paraphyletic †Mesomantispinae proposed by Jepson et al.
2431 (2013), which was defined by plesiomorphic characters of Mantispidae, which can be retained to
2432 different degrees by Symphrasinae, †*Mesomantispoides*, †*Haplacantha*, †Doratomantispinae and
2433 †*Aragomantispa*. The complicated pectinate forewing CuA (over seven branches) proposed as the
2434 synapomorphy of †Mesomantispinae by Lu et al. (2020) is supported as the specialized character
2435 of certain mesomantispines, such as †*Archaeodrepanicus* and †*Mesomantispa*. Therefore, there is
2436 justification to suggest that Symphrasinae and derived extant mantispids (DCM clade) might
2437 respectively or commonly stem from a mesomantipine ancestor. The presence of a protarsal
2438 distodorsal specialized seta (long thickened setae (char. 96:1, char. 97:1) or Stitz organ (char. 96:2,
2439 char. 97:2)) was supported to independently evolve in Symphrasinae, Rhachiberotherinae and R1

2440 clade of †Paraberothinae. Notably, this seta can be observed in both sexes in Symphrasinae and
2441 †Paraberothinae (at least in †*Acanthoberotha* and †*Creagroparaberotha*) but only in male in
2442 Rhachiberothinae. Additionally, the number of protarsal segments is four in both sexes in
2443 Symphrasinae, five in both sexes in †Paraberothinae (at least in †*Acanthoberotha* and
2444 †*Creagroparaberotha*), and four in male while five in female in Rhachiberothinae. These findings
2445 indicate the complex evolutionary history of the protarsus in these subfamilies, with multiple
2446 origins and various combinations, which is not as simple as previously understood. The presence
2447 of a single row of probasitarsal specialized setae, forewing with trapezoidal pterostigma and Sc
2448 fused with RA distally, which were regarded as unique synapomorphies to support the close
2449 relationship between †Paraberothinae and Symphrasinae (Ardila-Camacho et al. 2021), were
2450 recognized either as the independent evolution in †Paraberothinae and Mantispidae (the first two),
2451 or as the plesiomorphic character of Mantispoidea (the last one).

2452 †*Mesomantispoides* and †*Haplacantha* were resolved as intermediate lineages between basal
2453 mantispids and derived mantispids with long tubular pronotum, which clarifies the gradual
2454 evolution of specialized prothorax in Mantispidae: (i) shield-shaped pronotum, prothorax not
2455 elongated posteriad and apically not expanded, broad postfurcasternum, the absence of precoxal
2456 bridge (plesiomorphic state) — (ii) shield-shaped pronotum, prothorax slightly elongated
2457 posteriad and apically not expanded, broad postfurcasternum, the absence of precoxal bridge
2458 (basal mantispids and Symphrasinae) — (iii) shield-shaped pronotum, prothorax slightly
2459 elongated posteriad and apically not expanded, broad postfurcasternum, the presence of precoxal
2460 bridge (†*Mesomantispoides*) — (iv) tubular pronotum, prothorax slightly elongated posteriad and
2461 apically not expanded, broad or narrow postfurcasternum, the presence of precoxal bridge

2462 (†*Haplacantha*) — (v) tubular pronotum, prothorax strongly elongated posteriad to various
2463 degrees and apically expanded, narrow postfurcasternum, the presence of precoxal bridge (most
2464 mantispids in the TPM clade).

2465 All analyses reach a consensus on the paraphyly of Drepanicinae which was originally
2466 hypothesized to contain five extant and eight extinct genera. †*Sinuijumantispa* was grouped in
2467 mantispid basal lineages. †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa* and †*Psilomantispa*, together
2468 with †*Pectispina* (originally subfamily incertae sedis) consist of a derived lineage in
2469 †Doratomantispinae. †*Liassochrysta* plus †*Promantispa* were recovered as either the sister group
2470 either to Calomantispinae+Mantispinae or to Mantispinae. *Aragomantispa* is supported to be
2471 closely allied with the DCM clade. The results even question the monophyly of extant
2472 drepanicines which comprise five genera *Allomantispa*, *Ditaxis*, *Drepanicus*, *Gerstaeckerella*
2473 (including extinct †*G. asiatica*) and *Theristria*. The DCM were well-supported by the
2474 synapomorphies as follows: (i) the absence of saber-shaped profemoral ISs (57:0), (ii) the
2475 presence of spine-shaped of ISs (60:1), (iii) spine-shaped major process (68:2); (iv-vi) protarsal
2476 ventral specialized setae angularly curved and apically touching the tarsal ventral surface (100:2,
2477 104:2, 106:2, homologous), (vii) trichosors reduced, present only on wing apex (116:3), (viii) ScP
2478 distally separate from RA (125:1); (ix) hind wing 1rp-m distad the primary branching point of M
2479 (173:1); (x) hind wing CuA shortened, terminating proximad the midpoint of wing posterior
2480 margin (175:1, homologous). Three possible character states supporting the monophyly of
2481 Drepanicinae were detected in MP1-2: (i) procoxal posterior surface distally with a longitudinal
2482 groove (44:1, homologous), (ii) major process located at proximal 1/5-1/4 length of profemur
2483 (66:1, homoplasious) and (iii) female gonocoxites 8 paired (215:0, homoplasious). Some fossil

2484 drepanicine genera exhibit more plesiomorphic characters, while some were recovered as the
2485 specialized group in another subfamily which underwent convergent evolution.

2486 Placing †*Sinuijumantispa* to Drepanicinae is obviously caused by the inaccurate or
2487 superficial recognition of characters (So and Won 2022), which displays a series of traits as seen
2488 in mesomantispines and symphrasines, indicating its lower placement, such as the prothorax
2489 slightly elongated posteriad, well-developed trichosors nearly along entirely wing margin, short
2490 wing length, recurrent humeral crossvein, as well as ScP and RA distally fused in fact, rather than
2491 as separate as in Drepanicinae. The seemingly highly developed character, the presence of major
2492 process and other more secondarily long processes on profemoral ventral surface, is also observed
2493 in mesomantispines and symphrasines. This genus now was reconstructed to be related to
2494 mesomantispine lineages by most results (Supplementary Figs. S3-S5, S60b, S61), and we
2495 tentatively placed it into the paraphyletic †Mesomantispinae, awaiting additional materials for in-
2496 depth investigations.

2497 †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa* and †*Psilomantispa* were originally assigned in
2498 Drepanicinae, mainly relying on similar wing and male genital characters (elongated ectoprocts)
2499 with extant Drepanicinae, although they do not cluster together with the other drepanicine genera
2500 together to form a monophyletic group (Lu et al. 2020). However, our analyses suggest that these
2501 genera, together with †*Pectispina*, form a derived clade in †Doratomantispinae, mostly positioning
2502 them in close relation to †*Doratomantispa*. This relationship is supported by the presence of
2503 erected (87:0), angularly curved protibial ventral specialized setae (88:2, homologous), and female
2504 ectoprocts each with a ventral projection (227:1, homologous), indicating that the previously
2505 recognized similarities are somewhat superficial and represent convergent evolution.

2506 †*Aragomantispa* was also unanimously ousted from Drepanicinae, instead forming the stem group
2507 to the DCM clade. All characters applied to classify this genus into Drepanicinae should be
2508 plesiomorphic, occurring in many basal mantispid lineages, such as the presence of major process,
2509 protarsal prostrate setae arranged in transverse pairs (two rows) and protibial and protarsal
2510 prostrate setae having a different shape, with the latter being thicker, more raised and angulated
2511 (Pérez-de la Fuente and Peñalver 2019a). Notably, the angularly curved protarsal ventral
2512 specialized setae in †*Aragomantispa* do not touch the ventral surface (100:1, 104:1, 106:1), which
2513 is identical to the case in †*Haplacantha* (the homologous character state of TPM clade) but
2514 different from those (touching the surface, the homologous character state of DCM clade) in
2515 Drepanicinae.

2516 Despite the forewing venations of the two Jurassic genera, †*Liassochrysa* and †*Promantispa*,
2517 more similar to extant drepanicines superficially (Lambkin 1986a, Lambkin 1986b, Wedmann and
2518 Makarkin 2007, Liu et al. 2015, Lu et al. 2020), and even recovered as the sister to
2519 Calomantispinae+Mantispinae or to Mantispinae in this study, the question on their placement of
2520 family or even super family is still posed here. Such specialized forewing type of DCM clade
2521 surprisingly occurred in this early period in fact, because we have noticed that mantispids from the
2522 same or adjacent geological period, or even throughout the period from Jurassic to mid-Cretaceous,
2523 possess the forewing morphology more plesiomorphic and more complex. The simplified
2524 forewing (simpler venation, trichosors reduced or absent) was present possibly until the origin of
2525 derived doratomantispines and the DCM clade, which is still more complex than that of
2526 †*Liassochrysa* and †*Promantispa*. Notably, during this early period, such a similar simplified wing
2527 structure is commonly observed in some chrysopid-like species (e.g., †*Aristenymphes perfecta*

2528 Panfilov in Dolin et al., †*Mesypochrysa reducta* Panfilov in Dolin et al., and †*Mesypochrysa*
2529 *minuta* Jepson et al., although there are some differences (e.g., thickened and rounded pterostigma,
2530 only three forewing ra-rp crossveins in †*Liassochrysa* and †*Promantispa*), and †*Liassochrysa* was
2531 originally assigned in †Mesochrysopinae, or alternatively treated as a monotypic family as
2532 †*Promantispa* (Panfilov 1980, Ansorge and Schlüter 1990, Nel et al. 2005). With the systematic
2533 changes in †*Berothone*, †*Khasurtoberotha*, and †*Mesithone*, as well as the common occurrence of
2534 convergent evolution in wings, we consider that simply determining the systematic position of
2535 fossils based solely on wing morphology comparisons may carry significant risks. Therefore, the
2536 family or supra-family identity of these two genera requires further clarification when more
2537 complete materials are found.

2538 Calomantispinae were recovered as the sister group to Mantisppinae as proposed in Lambkin
2539 (1986a), Lambkin (1986b), rejecting the hypothesis of drepanicine affinity in Winterton et al.
2540 (2018) and Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021). At most nine possible synapomorphies were identified
2541 to support this relationships: (i) major process nearly 1/4× length of profemur (67:2), (ii) the
2542 presence of profemoral posteroventral carina (namely, profemur lateroventrally compressed, 76:1,
2543 homologous), (iii) protibia plus protarsus shorter than profemur (80:2, homologous), (iv) the
2544 absence of incorporated veins in pterostigma (124:1), (v) two or more crossveins under
2545 pterostigma (126:1), (vi) RP main branches sinuous (129:1), (vii) RP branches without small
2546 apical twigging (130:1), (viii) forewing MP simply bifurcate (151:1) and (ix) the absence of male
2547 callus cerci (206:1).

2548

2549 According to above results from the phylogenetic analysis, systematic revision on the

2550 mantispid subfamilies Symphrasinae and †Doratomantispinae as well as some of their affiliated
2551 genera should be made and presented below.

2552

2553 **Systematic palaeontology**

2554 **Class Insecta Linnaeus, 1758**

2555 **Order Neuroptera Linnaeus, 1758**

2556 **Superfamily Mantispoidea Leach, 1815**

2557 **Family Mantispidae Leach, 1815**

2558 **Subfamily Symphrasinae (including †*Sinomesomantispa*)**

2559 Supplementary Figs. S1g, S2j, k, S11h-k, S12h, S17q, S18, S24o-s, S25a-s, S27f, S36i-k, S37,
2560 S44k-p, S48n-p, S53c-m, S58g-j.

2561 Symphrasini Navas, 1909: 484; Lambkin, 1986a: 28. Type genus: *Symphrasis* Hagen, 1877,
2562 synonymized with *Trichoscelia* Westwood, 1852 by Parker and Stange, 1965

2563 **Revised diagnosis.** Tubercles absent; coronal suture distinct. Antenna short, less than half length
2564 of forewing. Pronotum short, shield-shaped, posteroventrally not fused, slightly elongated
2565 posteriad insertion of procoxa (making procoxa insert near middle of prothorax); postfurcasternum
2566 paired or fused, broad. Profemur stout, broadened near middle; profemoral ventral ISs arranged in
2567 two or four rows, two large pedicellate, thickened ISs rows (absent in †*Sinomesomantispa*), and
2568 two very short ISs rows (namely antero- and posteroventral rows, stinger-, thorn-, tubercle- and
2569 spine-shaped), both fully developed or with posteroventral row reduced; major process present or
2570 absent; protibial ventrally with short, continuous, homogeneous, flattened and smoothly curved
2571 specialized setae with narrow gaps; protarsus 4-segmented in both sex, tarsomere 1 spinous,

2572 apically strongly produced, longer than remaining ones combined, ventrally bearing specialized
2573 setae the same as those on protibia; tarsomeres 2-4 ventrally without specialized setae; two
2574 pretarsal claws, each simple; arolium sac-like, with rounded apex. Wing not elongated, generally
2575 about 2.5 times as long as wide; trichosors almost along entire wing margin (only one between
2576 each adjacent veinlets, sometimes with two or more between each adjacent veinlets). Forewing
2577 recurrent humeral crossvein simple, bifurcate, simply or complicatedly multifurcate, ScP distally
2578 fused with RA, subcostal space proximad pterostigma with only one scp-r crossvein; one to three
2579 ra-rp crossveins, distal one proximad or distad fusion point of ScP and RA; M separate from or
2580 fused with R for a long distance distad 1m-cu. Hind wing costal veins distally fused with ScP or
2581 not; one to three ra-rp crossveins, distal one proximad or distad fusion point of ScP and RA; 1rp-m
2582 sigmoid; CuP free, creeping, with stem long and deep. Male tergum 9 separate from ectoprocts;
2583 gonocoxites 9 rod-like, slender, simple or distally bearing digitiform processes; gonapophyses 9
2584 long, rod-like; gonostyli 10 whip-like, with a broadened and thickened base. Female tergum 9
2585 fused with ectoprocts or not; gonocoxites 9 adjoined loosely or closely, rounded or entirely
2586 elongated posteriad, sometimes as a long ovipositor.

2587 **Remarks.** †*Sinomesomantispa* is assigned into Symphrasinae as its basal lineage, based on almost
2588 all phylogenetic results (only MP1T and MP3T not or weakly supported, obviously affecting by
2589 the increase in missing data of the matrix), and the presence of a unique synapomorphy of
2590 Symphrasinae — probasitarsus spinous (92:2, 93:2), distally with minute conical Stitz organ (96:2,
2591 97:2), ventrally bearing flattened, smoothly curved specialized setae (100:0) in a row (101:1). The
2592 female ovipositor-like gonocoxites 9 (223:3) is a specialized character present in higher clades,
2593 such as †*Habrosymphrasis*, †*Haplosymphrasites* (highly possible) and three extant genera. The

2594 entirely elongated posteriad but not ovipositor-like gonocoxites 9 (223:2) of †*Proplega* may
2595 represent a transitional phenotype.

2596

2597 **Genus** †*Habrosymphrasis* Shi et al., 2019

2598 Supplementary Figs. S11h, S17q, S24r, s, S37e, S53h, i, S58g.

2599 Shi et al., 2019: 5. **Type species:** *Habrosymphrasis xiai* Shi et al., 2019, by original designation
2600 and monotypy.

2601 **Revised diagnosis.** Postfurcasternum paired, broad. Profemoral antero- and posteroventral rows
2602 fully developed, with ISs stinger-, thorn- and tubercle-shaped; major process simple, saber-shaped.
2603 Trichosors almost along entire wing margin except large part of anterior base (only one between
2604 each adjacent veinlets). Forewing humeral crossvein recurrent, with four simple branches; costal
2605 crossveins along ScP all simple; three ra-rp crossveins, distal one distad fusion point of ScP and
2606 RA; M diverging from R proximad lm-cu. Hind wing costal vein distally fused with ScP for a long
2607 distance; two ra-rp crossveins, distal one proximad fusion point of ScP and RA. Male sternum 9
2608 plate-like, shallow; gonocoxite 9 distally bifurcated. Female tergum 9 separate from ectoprocts;
2609 gonocoxite 9 elongated to a long ovipositor.

2610 **Material examined.** 1♂, CAU-BA-WN-19002, amber piece also preserving a hymenopteran and
2611 a dipteran; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width
2612 about 23.01× 15.05 mm, height about 7.37 mm (CAU). 1♀, NIGP171729, amber piece also
2613 preserving six hymenopterans, a barklice, two dipteran and a hemipteran; it is polished in the form
2614 of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width about 27.51× 12.53 mm, height about
2615 4.53 mm (CAU). 1ex (terminalia broken), BXAM BA-NEU-0041, amber piece also preserving

2616 two beetles; it is polished in the form of an elliptical, transparent cabochon, with length× width
2617 about 15.52× 8.56 mm, height about 2.55 mm (CAU).

2618 **Locality.** Hukwang Valley in Tanai Township, Myitkyina District of Kachin State, Myanmar,
2619 Lowermost Cenomanian.

2620

2621 **Genus** †*Haplosymphrasites* Liu et al., 2020

2622 Supplementary Figs. S11k, S37f, S53l, m.

2623 Lu et al, 2020: 2. **Type species:** *Haplosymphrasites zouae* Lu et al., 2020, by original designation
2624 and monotypy.

2625 **Revised diagnosis.** Postfurcasternum paired, broad. Profemoral posteroventral rows fully
2626 developed, with ISs stinger-, thorn- and tubercle-shaped; major process simple, saber-shaped.
2627 Trichosors almost along entire wing margin except large part of anterior base (over two between
2628 each adjacent veinlets). RA branches all simple; RP branches only simply bifurcate, without apical
2629 twigging. Forewing humeral crossvein recurrent, with three to six simple branches; costal
2630 crossveins along ScP all simple; only one ra-rp crossvein, proximad fusion point of ScP and RA;
2631 M fused with R distad lm-cu for a long distance. Hind wing costal vein distally fused with ScP for
2632 a long distance; only one ra-rp crossvein, proximad fusion point of ScP and RA. Female
2633 gonocoxites 8 fused with gonapophyses 8; tergum 9 separate from ectoprocts; gonocoxite 9 highly
2634 likely elongated to a long ovipositor (broken in specimen NIGP171831).

2635 **Material examined.** 1♀, NIGP171831, amber piece polished in the form of an elliptical,
2636 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 14.05× 9.83 mm, height about 2.97 mm (NIGP).

2637 **Locality.** Hukwang Valley in Tanai Township, Myitkyina District of Kachin State, Myanmar,

2638 Lowermost Cenomanian.

2639

2640 **Subfamily †Doratomantispinae Lu et al., 2020**

2641 Supplementary Figs. S2s-z, S13b-o, S19j-p, S20a-c, S26g-s, S39, S45, S49b-h, S54i-n, S58k-m.

2642 Lu et al., 2020: 2; Li et al., 2022: 638. Type genus: *Doratomantispa* Poinar in Poinar & Buckley,

2643 2011

2644 **Revised diagnosis.** Vertex domed or flattened, posteriorly with two large lateral tubercles.

2645 Pronotum tubular, posteroventrally fused; maculae absent; postfurcasternum paired and narrow.

2646 Profemur distinctly shorter than protibia plus protarsi, without posteroventral carina, broadened

2647 near base or middle, ventrally with two ISs rows: ISs stout, saber-shaped, rarely spine-shaped;

2648 anteroventral row consisting of a branched major process with two-five branches, and several

2649 short processes or not; posteroventral row sparse, with only one or several short processes;

2650 sometimes all profemoral ISs absent (†*Psilomantispa*); protibia ventrally without

2651 (†*Dicranomantispa*, †*Psilomantispa*) or with a row of flattened or angularly curved prostrate setae

2652 on well-developed and thickened keel; protarsus 5-segmented, tarsomere 1 not prolonged and not

2653 distally spinously produced, tarsomere 1-4 ventrally bearing conical setae (sometimes only present

2654 on tarsomeres 1-2); two simple pretarsal claws; arolium small, subtriangular, acutely tapering.

2655 Trichosors almost along entire wing margin (only one between each adjacent veinlets) or only

2656 present on wing apex; ScP fused with or separate from RA; hind wing 1rp-m upright, CuP stem

2657 well-developed (long and deep), reduced or absent, distally shortly creeping or not. Male

2658 gonocoxites 9 short or long, slender or broad, distally simple or bifurcated; gonapophyses 10 long,

2659 slender or broad, distally acute; gonostyli 10 (pseudopenis) whip-shaped, short to very long,

2660 basally enlarged and thickened (†*Doratomantispa*, †*Paradoxomantispa*). Female tergum 9 not
2661 fused with ectoprocts; pseudohypocaudae absent; gonocoxites 9 short, not elongated to a long
2662 ovipositor; ectoprocts rounded (†*Paradoxomantispa*) or ventrally slightly (†*Doratomantispa*) or
2663 strongly produced (†*Acanthomantispa*).

2664 **Remarks.** This revised diagnosis is mainly based on Li et al. (2022), combined with some
2665 characters summarized from †*Acanthomantispa*, †*Dicranomantispa*, †*Pectispina* and
2666 †*Psilomantispa*, all of which have been ousted from Drepanicinae and assigned into
2667 Doratomantiapinae in the present study. Eight possible synapomorphies were identified to
2668 supported the monophyly of †Doratomantispinae: (i-ii) branched (65:1) and very long (over 1/2
2669 length of profemur, 67:4, homologous) major process, (iii) protibia medially straight (82:0), (iv-vi)
2670 protarsal ventral specialized setae conical (100:3, 104:3, 106:3, homologous), (vii) protarsal
2671 arolium small, triangular and acutely tapering distad (109:1, homologous) and (viii) forewing
2672 proximal scp-r distad the original point of RP (139:1). These characters of foreleg are somewhat
2673 reduced or lost in derived doratomantispines. Twelve possible synapomorphies were identified to
2674 support the monophyly of derived doratomantispines: (i) flattened vertex (14:1), (ii) indistinct
2675 coronal suture (17:1), (iii) barely expanded of the area of procoxal insertion (29:0), (iv)
2676 prothoracic setae shortened (34:1) and (v) inserted on a smooth base (35:0), (vi) profemoral
2677 anteroventral row highly reduced to only one process (61:2), (vii) profemoral posteroventral row
2678 highly reduced to only one process (72:2, homologous), (viii) wing trichosors reduced, only
2679 distributed along wing apex (116:2), (ix) wing margin hair shortened (121:1), (x) ScP distally
2680 separated from RA (125:1), (xi) forewing costal crossveins proximad pterostigma or the same
2681 position simple (136: 1) and (xii) hind wing lrp-m distad the primary branching point of M

2682 (173:1). Except (iii) and (vii), these characters also independently evolved in the DCM clade.

2683

2684 **Genus** †*Acanthomantispa* Lu et al., 2020

2685 Supplementary Figs. S1j, S2s-v, S13j-m, S19o, p, S20a, S26m-o, r, S39d, e, S45h, i, S54k-n.

2686 Lu et al., 2020: 5. **Type species:** *Acanthomantispa immaculata* Lu et al., 2020, by original
2687 designation.

2688 **Revised diagnosis.** Vertex flattened. Profemoral ISs rows: anteroventral row with only major
2689 process remained, primarily branched near its 1/5-1/4 length, with three branches (all branches
2690 saber-shaped), located near middle of profemur; posteroventral row reduced to only one saber-
2691 shaped process slightly distal to level of major process; protibia with a row of angularly curved
2692 prostrate setae; protarsomeres 1-4 ventrally bearing conical setae. Trichosors only present on wing
2693 apex; ScP separate from RA with one crossvein connecting them; forewing proximal scp-r present;
2694 hind wing CuP stem well-developed, long and deep, distally shortly creeping or only bifurcate.
2695 Male sternum 9 plate-like, tapering apically to an obtuse point, ectoprocts elongated. Female
2696 gonocoxites 9 rounded, not produced; ectoprocts ventrally strongly produced.

2697 **Material examined.** †*Acanthomantispa grandis* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, 1ex, NIGP 173085,
2698 amber piece polished in the form of a subrectangular transparent cabochon, with length× width
2699 about 18.76× 4.84 mm, height about 12.81 mm (NIGP).

2700 †*Acanthomantispa immaculata* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♂ EMTG BU001408, amber piece
2701 also preserving a hemipteran; it is polished in the form of an elliptical transparent cabochon, with
2702 length× width about 43.42× 28.80 mm, height about 7.66 mm (CAU).

2703 †*Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU002131, amber piece

2704 also preserving a beetle; it is polished in the form of a semicircular transparent cabochon, with
2705 length× width about 28.46× 15.23 mm, height about 11.45 mm (CAU). Paratype, 1♀, EMTG
2706 BU002136, amber piece also preserving two dipterans; it is polished in the form of a subtriangular
2707 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 33.32× 14.26 mm, height about 7.38 mm (CAU).
2708 Paratype, 1♀, EMTG BU002270, amber piece polished in the form of a nearly quadrangular
2709 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 23.34× 21.26 mm, height about 9.11 mm (CAU).
2710 1♂, BXAM BA-NEU-034, amber piece also preserving a dipteran; it is polished in the form of a
2711 round transparent cabochon, with length× width about 22.91× 22.76 mm, height about 8.82 mm
2712 (CAU). 1ex, EMTG BU002302, amber piece also preserving a snakefly larva, a cockroach, two
2713 beetles, four ants and many dipterans; it is polished in the form of an elliptical transparent
2714 cabochon, with length× width about 58.46× 41.27 mm, height about 24.36 mm (CAU).

2715 †*Acanthomantispa* sp.: 1♀, NIGP171834, amber piece polished in the form of an elliptical
2716 transparent cabochon, with length× width about 34.72× 19.91 mm, height about 4.31 mm (NIGP).

2717 **Locality.** Hukwang Valley in Tanai Township, Myitkyina District of Kachin State, Myanmar,
2718 Lowermost Cenomanian.

2719 **Remarks.** Type specimens of †*Acanthomantispa maculata* identified as males in Lu et al. (2020)
2720 are females (Supplementary Figs. S54k-n).

2721

2722 **Genus** †*Dicranomantispa* Lu et al., 2020

2723 Supplementary Figs. S2w-x, S39f, S45j, k.

2724 Lu et al., 2020: 5. **Type species:** *Dicranomantispa zhouae* Lu et al., 2020, by original designation
2725 and monotypy.

2726 **Revised diagnosis.** Vertex flattened. Profemoral ISs rows: anteroventral row with only major
2727 process remained, primarily branched near its middle, with two branches (all branches saber-
2728 shaped), located near 1/3 length of profemur; posteroventral row reduced to only one saber-shaped
2729 process slightly distal to level of major process; protibia without specialized setae; protarsomeres
2730 1-2 ventrally bearing conical setae. Trichosors only present on wing apex; ScP separate from RA
2731 with one crossvein connecting them; forewing proximal scp-r absent; hind wing CuP stem well-
2732 developed, long and deep, distally simply bifurcate. Male ectoprocts elongated.

2733 **Material examined.** †*Dicranomantispa zhouae* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-ZM-
2734 19003, amber piece polished in the form of a raindrop-like transparent cabochon, with length×
2735 width about 30.93× 23.28 mm, height about 7.78 mm (CAU).

2736 **Locality.** Hukwang Valley in Tanai Township, Myitkyina District of Kachin State, Myanmar,
2737 Lowermost Cenomanian.

2738

2739 **Genus** †*Psilomantispa* Lu et al., 2020

2740 Supplementary Figs. S2y, z, S13n, o, S20b, c, S26s, S45l.

2741 Lu et al., 2020: 5. Type species: *Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al., 2020, by original designation
2742 and monotypy.

2743 **Revised diagnosis.** Vertex flattened. Profemoral ISs absent; protibial specialized setae absent;
2744 only protarsomere 1 ventrally bearing conical setae (possibly only one, sometimes absent).
2745 Trichosors only present on wing apex; ScP separate from RA with one crossvein connecting them;
2746 forewing proximal scp-r present; hind wing CuP stem well-developed, long and deep, distally
2747 shortly creeping only with three simple branches. Male sternum 9 plate-like, tapering apically to

2748 an obtuse point, ectoprocts elongated.

2749 **Material examined.** †*Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al., 2020: Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-LX-19004,

2750 amber piece polished in the form of an ovoid transparent cabochon, with length× width about

2751 26.70× 15.21 mm, height about 5.17 mm (CAU). 1ex, NIGP171734, amber piece polished in the

2752 form of an ovoid transparent cabochon, with length× width about 55.33× 37.04 mm, height about

2753 19.11 mm (NIGP).

2754 **Locality.** Hukwang Valley in Tanai Township, Myitkyina District of Kachin State, Myanmar,

2755 Lowermost Cenomanian.

2756

2757 **Supplementary Appendix 5. Additional results and discussion**

2758

2759

Divergence time estimation

2760 In the unpartitioned time calibration analysis, the 95% highest posterior density (HPD)
2761 intervals for the root and nodes closer to it were estimated to be much wider (less precise
2762 divergence time estimates) than those of the shallower nodes in general. This is highly likely due
2763 to the insufficient information in the dataset, such as a higher proportion of missing data and
2764 limited morphological characters, particularly of the basal lineages. Besides, the deviations of
2765 evolutionary rates from the clock model and the underpartitioning may have also contributed to
2766 this result (Angelis et al. 2018, Tao et al. 2020).

2767 Although the partitioned analysis fixes the root time to be the same as the unpartitioned
2768 analysis, which causes significant narrow 95% HPD intervals of deeper nodes, still estimated the
2769 older ages of deeper nodes and slightly younger age of some shallower nodes, which may be
2770 attributed to the limited data in partitions for inference or to the models of tip-dating analysis.
2771 Ideally, different partitions in a phylogenetic analysis should share the same tree topology and
2772 geological time duration, despite having their own independent evolutionary history (Zhang and
2773 Wang 2019). Future research that incorporates additional materials, extracts more morphological
2774 information, utilizes larger molecular datasets, and conducts comprehensive methodological
2775 evaluations may help to resolve these issues. (Supplementary Figs. S65, S66, Supplementary
2776 Tables S2, S3).

2777

2778

Ancestral state reconstruction

2779 Our analyses reveal that the raptorial lifestyle in Mantispoidea originated with a series of
2780 morphological innovations present in the foreleg, including the procoxa elongated, profemur
2781 incrassated and broadened near its proximal 1/3-1/2 length, the presence of profemoral
2782 integumentary specializations fully developed and protibia curved near the joint with profemur, all
2783 of which formed the groundplan of the ancestral raptorial foreleg. The modified structures of the
2784 protibia, including ventral keel and ventral specialized setae, medially curved protibia and the
2785 shortened protibia length appeared later, in the most recent common ancestor of the three raptorial
2786 families, while the modifications on the protarsus in raptorial Mantispoidea occurred the most
2787 recently and independently evolved in †Paraberothinae and Mantispidae. (Supplementary Figs.
2788 S6a, S86-S90, S97, S99).

2789 The subsequent evolutionary attempts of raptorial forelegs were mainly built upon these
2790 fundamental novelties above, singly or multiply undergoing complexification, further
2791 specialization, reduction, loss or even reversal (Supplementary Figs. S6a, S91-S96, S98, S100-
2792 S109). For example, the broadened position of profemur changed to the base independently in
2793 certain lineages respectively of the three raptorial families; middle curvature has been the typical
2794 state of the protibia in raptorial Mantispoidea since its origin, but in some paraberothines and
2795 †Doratomantispinae, a reversal from a curved to a straight state is observed; protibia is shortened
2796 variously, while the protibia-tarsus system is commonly as long as the ancestral state (longer than
2797 profemur), except Symphrasinae (equal), Calomantispinae and Mantispidae (shorter); Profemoral
2798 ISs, protibial and protarsal specialized setae complicatedly evolved into multiple types, varying in
2799 length, inclination, branching patterns (only present in ISs) and curvatures, but within an
2800 individual, the former one always exhibits complex combinations and the latter two are generally

2801 consistent. Among all known profemoral ISs types, tubercle- and saber-shaped ISs might be the
2802 earliest to appear, representing the ISs types during the early evolution of raptorial Mantispoidea.
2803 Meanwhile, other ISs types are likely to have evolved independently across various lineages
2804 within the raptorial Mantispoidea.

2805 The raptorial foreleg of deep lineages may be characterized by short, tubercle-, saber-, thorn-
2806 and stinger-shaped profemoral ISs, which are tiny, movable, and thickened setae with or without a
2807 slightly prominent base, arranged in two full rows. They may mainly function as
2808 mechanoreceptors for prothoracic tibial flexion reflex (Loxton and Nicholls 1979, Copeland and
2809 Carlson 1997, Hartenstein 1997) or to increase the friction coefficient on the profemoral ventral
2810 surface, lacking significant lethality. The trend of enlargement and strengthening of profemoral ISs
2811 is convergent both in Rhachiberothidae and Mantispidae, which can introduce or enhance puncture
2812 ability, decrease the angle between tibia and femur, and restrict protibial flexibility (Caldwell and
2813 Dingle 1975, Loxton and Nicholls 1979, deVries et al. 2012, Büsse et al. 2021). However, the
2814 enlarged ISs patterns differ significantly between the two families: Mantispidae focused on
2815 enlarging the integumentary process while specialized setae continuously contracted until being
2816 tiny Stitz organs, whereas Rhachiberothidae might enlarge both portions or even just the
2817 specialized setae. The rigidity of enlarged ISs in Mantispidae are undoubtedly higher than in
2818 Rhachiberothidae, reducing breakage risk caused by the movability of long specialized setae when
2819 holding prey, which is also well-supported by the preservation state that the broken long ISs are
2820 easily found in the specimens of Rhachiberothidae (Supplementary Figs. S21r, S22n, q, S23i, l, n),
2821 but very rare in Mantispidae. The protibial ventral specialized setae in Rhachiberothidae are
2822 generally erected, large, and diverse, collaborating with ISs to minimize the angle between the

2823 femur and tibia, increasing lethality (Loxton and Nicholls 1979). In contrast, †Dipteromantispidae
2824 and Mantispidae features flattened, small setae with limited diversity, likely functioning primarily
2825 as mechanoreceptors. In Rhachiberothidae, Symphrasinae, and basal mantispids, the curvature of
2826 protarsal specialized setae corresponds to that of protibia (ably flattened as in protibia in the latter
2827 two), but in TPM clade, it continuously curves towards a more angled direction. Notably,
2828 angularly curved protibial and conical protarsal ventral specialized setae in †Doratomantispinae
2829 are disparate from all other raptorial mantispoids, suggesting a more unique and exceptional
2830 function.

2831 The reduction of profemoral ISs may have emerged continuously throughout the entire
2832 raptorial evolution and reached the utmost degree within derived doratomantispines (even
2833 completely lost in †*Psilomantispa*). On the other hand, the reduction or loss of protibial and
2834 protarsal specialized setae independently evolved in Rhachiberothidae and Mantispidae
2835 (concentrating on the derived clades in the latter), such as †*Paradoxoberothesa*, †*Astioberothesa*,
2836 †*Microberothesa*, †*Stygioberothesa*, †*Dicranomantispa*, †*Psilomantispa* and Mantispinae. Despite the
2837 presence of plesiomorphic characters, such as the absence of enlarged ISs and protarsal ventral
2838 specialized setae, the raptorial foreleg of †Dipteromantispidae should also represent the simplified
2839 form, with profemoral ventral ISs sparse and reduced. These foreleg transformations, which
2840 appear to be coevolved with an enlargement of body size (Supplementary Figs. S114, S115,
2841 Supplementary Table S11), may reflect certain morphological optimization or even a shift of
2842 feeding habits (e.g., in derived doratomantispines, see later) in response to a predator-prey arms
2843 race and environmental changes. The concerted changes may promote functional specialization
2844 and improvement of predation efficiency, or represent expansion into novel ecological niches of

2845 the time (Romer 1966, Coates and Clack 1990, Wainwright et al. 2005, Adamowicz and Purvis
2846 2006, Clapham and Karr 2012, Futuyma 2013, Vermeij 2016).

2847 Prothorax may have also contributed to the early raptorial specialization, with the presence of
2848 the novelty—postfurcasternum possibly (near 50% likelihood) in the most recent common
2849 ancestor of raptorial mantispoids or the three raptorial families (100% likelihood) (Supplementary
2850 Fig. S82). The other novelties highly associated with raptorial lifestyles in HP emerged until the
2851 origin of Mantispidae. The prothorax which elongated posteriad procoxal insertion is a unique
2852 synapomorphy of Mantispidae, initially evolved in the most recent common ancestor of this
2853 family (Supplementary Fig. S81). The precoxal bridge occurred in the most recent common
2854 ancestor of †*Mesomantispoides* and TPM clade (Supplementary Fig. S84). All remaining HP
2855 specializations are mainly restricted and actively evolved in the TPM clade, including the eye
2856 specialization with ocular plane anteriorly, flattened vertex, prothorax strongly elongated in
2857 various degrees, tubular pronotum (also independently evolved in †*Archaeodrepanicus acutus*),
2858 the expanded area of procoxal insertion and maculae in DCM clade (Supplementary Figs. S6a,
2859 S77-S80, S83, S85). In raptorial Mantipoidea, the elongated wing only evolved in the TPM clade,
2860 and further enhanced independently in derived doratomantispines and Mantispinae
2861 (Supplementary Fig. S110). According to correlation tests (Supplementary Table 11), this
2862 specialization may result from the positive morphological integration with HP, namely more
2863 specialized HP promoting more specialized PW mainly through increasing its apomorphies.
2864 Additionally, the specialization of the raptorial foreleg could also facilitate the specialization of
2865 HP by increasing its apomorphies, which in turn could indirectly impact the evolution of PW,
2866 despite the weak correlation in both rates and morphological state changes between the foreleg

2867 and PW. The elongation of the forewing together with the elongated abdomen may serve a
2868 biomechanical purpose, potentially assisting in maintaining balance and stability due to the
2869 changes in body proportions caused by the elongated prothorax and enlarged raptorial forelegs.
2870 Further empirical research is required to provide comprehensive evidence and better understand
2871 the functional implications of these morphological changes.

2872 Raptorial Mantispoidea had more significant deviation in the HP region but less in the PW
2873 region during their early evolution (Supplementary Fig. S113). Mantispidae had negatively
2874 deviated HP and PW morphology from their initial ancestral states since its origin, and it had most
2875 apomorphic changes in the HP region and more changes in the PW region than the other lineages
2876 except †Dipteromantispidae with the most PW changes (Supplementary Figs. S6b, c, S111, S113;
2877 Supplementary Table S8). Rhachiberothidae displayed temporal HP and PW changes distinct
2878 from other raptorial mantispoids (mainly in the negative direction), but similar to berothids
2879 (mainly in the positive direction and closer to IASM). †Dipteromantispidae showed distinctly
2880 negatively deviating PW from its initial ancestral state, while having minimal HP and foreleg
2881 changes. The prothorax might also have been involved in the early raptorial specialization due to
2882 the presence of the postfurcasternum in the most recent common ancestor of raptorial mantispoids
2883 as well as the three raptorial families (Supplementary Fig. S82).

2884 †Doratomantispinae displays a course of significant gradual reduction of the regions directly
2885 associated with the raptorial lifestyle (head, prothorax and foreleg), far greater than any other
2886 lineages and very unique in raptorial Mantispoidea: (i) vertex domed, prothorax long and apically
2887 strongly expanded, profemur stout, strongly broadened near base, profemoral ventral ISs dense
2888 and large, intermingled with small ISs, anteroventral row moderately developed, major process

2889 basally five- or four-branched, protibia ventral specialized setae flattened and smoothly curved,
2890 protarsal ventral specialized setae cone-like, pretarsal arolium small and subtriangular
2891 (*†Paradoxomantispa*) — (ii) vertex domed, prothorax long and apically strongly expanded,
2892 profemur stout, strongly broadened near base, profemoral ventral ISs sparse, large and gradually
2893 shortened small ISs less and concentrating on the apex of profemur, anteroventral row reduced,
2894 major process basally bifurcated, protibia ventral specialized setae erected and angularly curved,
2895 protarsal ventral specialized setae cone-like, pretarsal arolium small and subtriangular
2896 (*†Doratomantispa*) — (iii) vertex flattened, prothorax long or shortened and apically barely
2897 expanded, profemur slender, slightly broadened near middle, only two profemoral ISs retained
2898 (major process and a posteroventral IS), major process trifurcated or four-branched near its 1/5
2899 length, protibia ventral specialized setae erected and angularly curved, protarsal ventral
2900 specialized setae cone-like, pretarsal arolium tiny and subtriangular (*†Acanthomantispa* and
2901 *†Pectispina*) — (iv) vertex flattened, prothorax long or shortened and apically barely expanded,
2902 profemur slender, slightly broadened near middle, only two profemoral ISs retained (major
2903 process and a posteroventral IS), major process trifurcated or four-branched near its 1/5 length,
2904 protibia ventral specialized setae erected and angularly curved, protarsal ventral specialized setae
2905 cone-like, pretarsal arolium tiny and subtriangular (*†Acanthomantispa* and *†Pectispina*) — (v)
2906 vertex flattened, prothorax shortened and apically barely expanded, profemur slender, slightly
2907 broadened near middle, only two profemoral ISs retained (major process and a posteroventral IS),
2908 major process nearly medially bifurcated, protibia ventral specialized setae absent, protarsal
2909 ventral specialized setae cone-like and reduced, pretarsal arolium tiny and subtriangular
2910 (*†Dicranomantispa*) — (vi) vertex flattened, prothorax shortened and apically barely expanded,

2911 profemur slender, profemoral ISs absent, protibia ventral specialized setae absent, protarsal ventral
2912 specialized setae almost all reduced, pretarsal arolium tiny and subtriangular (†*Psilomantispa*).
2913 These alternations evidently contributed to the prosperity of this subfamily, which boasts the
2914 highest number of species (18 species) among fossil mantispids, as well as a greater
2915 morphological rates and disparity (Supplementary Figs. S6, S7a, S64, S70a, b, S71-S74) and
2916 larger body size (Supplementary Figs. S114, S115).

2917 The states from (i) to (ii) may be the process of morphological optimization to improve the
2918 predation efficiency by reducing of superfluous small ISs and concentrating functions on the very
2919 long stout ISs, enhancing the puncture ability, further decreasing the angle between tibia and
2920 femur (more elongated ISs and erected angularly curved protibial ventral specialized setae) and
2921 restricting the flexibility of protibia (Caldwell and Dingle 1975, Poivre 1978, Loxton and Nicholls
2922 1979, Copeland and Carlson 1997, Hartenstein 1997, deVries et al. 2012, Pérez-de la Fuente and
2923 Peñalver 2019b). The branched specialization in the raptorial foreleg, also independently evolved
2924 in †*Dicranoberothesa*, is very unique in Mantispopidea, even insecta, which only occurs when there
2925 is highly reduction of profemoral ISs, usually accompanied by ISs length gradually shortened
2926 towards the apex of profemur (Supplementary Figs. S6a, S23i, S26g, j). The function and
2927 evolutionary significance of this branched structure remain elusive, yet it may confer a range of
2928 potential benefits, for example, every branch of major process bearing sensory specialized setae
2929 could increase the number of mechanoreceptors, enhancing the sensory perception of prey by this
2930 portion (Poivre 1978, Copeland and Carlson 1997, Hartenstein 1997); the long branch curves
2931 towards protibia can further decrease the angle between tibia and femur (Loxton and Nicholls
2932 1979); this structure may also increase the contact points for force application and help distribute

2933 forces more evenly to reduce the risk of damage or failure under stress. Future rigorous
2934 biomechanic and ethological investigations, together with computational simulation experiments,
2935 will contribute to a more comprehensive elucidation of the genuine functions and implications of
2936 these branched structures.

2937 In contrast, nearly all features closely associated with the raptorial lifestyle (from states (iii)
2938 to (vi)) are reduced or completely lost in derived doratomantispines (especially in †*Psilomantispa*,
2939 whose foreleg is highly closed to the cursorial form), which may indicate the change in feeding
2940 behaviors or even dietary shift from mainly carnivorous to mainly nectarivorous and palynivorous
2941 feeding habits. Morphospace analyses also suggest that derived doratomantispines extended the
2942 new morphospace far away from †*Paradoxomantispa* and †*Doratomantispa*, possibly leading to
2943 the ecological niche partitioning. This high reduction of raptorial systems may be driven by the
2944 selection pressure from the lineage competition caused by ecological niche saturation, and the
2945 angiosperm terrestrial revolution. The substantial competitive pressure had likely persisted for an
2946 extended duration, with the declining evolutionary and net diversification rates since the
2947 beginning of Cretaceous (Supplementary Figs. S69a, S118f). Additionally, the fossil records
2948 uncover high paleofauna diversity of †*Paradoxomantispa* and †*Doratomantispa*, with 14 species
2949 in total all from mid-Cretaceous Myanmar amber. These species share similar morphology and are
2950 mainly characterized by limited characters of their developed and optimized raptorial forelegs, as
2951 well as genitalia, which indicates that they might share similar ecological requirement and
2952 compete for the same prey and other resources, which may lead to more or less ecological niche
2953 overlap (Schluter 2000, Losos 2008, Violle et al. 2012, Godoy et al. 2014, Hembry and Weber
2954 2020). To reduce competition, niche partitioning is required to introduced differences in habitat

2955 use, diet, or other aspects of their ecology (Schoener 1974, Violle et al. 2012, Adler et al. 2013,
2956 Kraft et al. 2015).

2957 The rise of derived doratomantispines coincided with the period when the initial significant
2958 angiosperm diversity emerged (ca. 125-85 Ma), which led to the significant changes in terrestrial
2959 vegetation (competing for and replacing niches that were occupied by early gymnosperms and
2960 ferns), and promoted evolution and diversification of animals and other plant communities by
2961 providing new resources and habitats, as well as establishing complex interactions (Lloyd et al.
2962 2008, Barba-Montoya et al. 2018, Benton et al. 2022). This terrestrial flora revolution increased
2963 the source of both animal-based (e.g., the diversification of several insect lineages, such as ants
2964 (Moreau et al. 2006), assassin bugs (Hwang and Weirauch 2012), bees (Cardinal and Danforth
2965 2013), butterflies and moths (Wahlberg et al. 2013), orthopterans (Song et al. 2015), some dipteran
2966 groups (Condamine et al. 2016), and some beetle groups (Hunt et al. 2007, McKenna et al. 2015)
2967 and plant-based food (e.g., nectar and pollen). Recent extensive studies of mid-Cretaceous
2968 Myanmar amber have unveiled the remarkable diversity of insect paleofauna and well-preserved
2969 angiosperm fossils, serving as a microcosm reflecting this crucial Cretaceous ecological transition
2970 (Liu et al. 2018, Bao et al. 2019, Lu and Liu 2021, Ross 2021). It is worth noting that mantispids
2971 may not be strictly carnivorous, as some members have been observed visiting flowers during
2972 daytime, such as *Climaciella brunnea* (Say), *Necyla shirozui* (Nakahara), *Necyla flavonotata*
2973 Tjeder (Nakahara 1961, Tjeder 1963, Hoffman 1992). *Climaciella brunnea* has been documented
2974 to consume plant exudates at extrafloral nectaries (Batra 1972, Opler 1981), and the gut contents
2975 of *Necyla flavonotata* were found to contain pollen grains (Tjeder 1963). Therefore, the abundance
2976 and easy accessibility of food resources during this period, leading to the less feeding pressure,

2977 may also represent a crucial factor to drive the reduction of raptorial structures in derived
2978 doratomantispines.

2979 Notably, the specialized head (e.g., flattened vertex leading to a high proportion of compound
2980 eyes in head) and wings (e.g., elongation, reduced trichosors and venation) in derived
2981 doratomantispines exhibit convergent evolution with certain extant drepanicines, such as
2982 *Gerstaeckerella* and *Theristria*, as well as Mantispinae. However, the raptorial foreleg and
2983 prothorax in these extant taxa remain highly developed or further optimized, such as apically
2984 expanded and strongly elongated prothorax, a high diversity of developed raptorial foreleg
2985 morphologies in *Theristria* (Lambkin 1986a), the presence of a profemoral posteroventral carina
2986 in Calomantispinae and Mantispinae, and the trochanter being almost entirely fused with the
2987 femur, resulting in a characteristic trochanter-femur complex in Mantispinae. These morphological
2988 differences from derived doratomantispines imply that raptorial structures continue to serve a
2989 crucial function in these extant derived lineages, which is also supported by numerous previous
2990 biological and taxonomic studies (Devetak and Klokocovnik 2016, Snyman et al. 2021). Therefore,
2991 the convergent evolution observed in the head and wings of derived doratomantispines may
2992 originally evolved in conjunction with the highly developed raptorial forelegs to serve the
2993 raptorial lifestyle, but the rate of reduction and simplification was much slower for the former than
2994 the latter in the subsequent evolution. Alternatively, these specializations might also had occurred
2995 simultaneously with or following the reduction of the raptorial forelegs, irrelevant to the
2996 specialization of the raptorial lifestyle. Even in the context of ample food availability and reduced
2997 foraging pressure, enhanced visual acuity and flight capabilities may provide derived

2998 doratomantispines with a competitive advantage in food detection and habitat expansion,
2999 ultimately facilitating access to a greater range of resources.

3000

3001 *Correlation Test*

3002 We found correlations among evolutionary rates, morphological disparity, and state changes
3003 in different levels among anatomical regions (Supplementary Table S11). The foreleg rates
3004 moderately or strongly correlate with that of HP or PW in overall raptorial mantispoids (positive),
3005 †Dipteromantispidae (positive) and Rhachiberothidae (negative). Weak correlations among all
3006 phenotypic rates were detected in Mantispidae. Strong positive correlation was observed between
3007 foreleg and HP or PW disparity in Rhachiberothidae and Mantispidae. Strong correlations were
3008 also found between state changes of foreleg and other regions in Rhachiberothidae (positive) and
3009 †Dipteromantispidae (negative), while in Mantispidae strong negative correlation between state
3010 changes of foreleg and HP and weak correlation between state changes of foreleg and PW were
3011 observed.

3012

3013 REFERENCES

3014 Acker T.S. 1960. The comparative morphology of the male terminalia of Neuroptera (Insecta).

3015 *Microentomology*, 24:25–83.

3016 Adamowicz S.J., Purvis A. 2006. From more to fewer? Testing an allegedly pervasive trend in the

3017 evolution of morphological structure. *Evolution*, 60:1402–1416.

3018 Adams P.A. 1989. A new genus of Berothidae from tropical America, with two new species. *Psyche*,

3019 96:187–193.

3020 Adler P.B., Fajardo A., Kleinhesselink A.R., Kraft N.J.B. 2013. Trait-based tests of coexistence
3021 mechanisms. *Ecology Letters*, 16:1294–1306.

3022 Allio R., Nabholz B., Wanke S., Chomicki G., Pérez-Escobar O.A., Cotton A.M., Clamens A.L.,
3023 Kergoat G.J., Sperling F.A.H., Condamine F.L. 2021. Genome-wide macroevolutionary
3024 signatures of key innovations in butterflies colonizing new host plants. *Nature*
3025 *Communications*, 12:354.

3026 Angelis K., Álvarez-Carretero S., Dos Reis M., Yang Z.H. 2018. An evaluation of different partitioning
3027 strategies for Bayesian estimation of species divergence times. *Systematic Biology*, 67:61–77.

3028 Ansorge J., Schlüter T. 1990. The earliest Chrysopid: *Liassochrysa stigmatica* n. g. et n. sp. from the
3029 Lower Jurassic of Dobbertin, Germany. *Neuroptera International*, 6:87–93.

3030 Ardila-Camacho A., Califre-Martins C., Aspöck U., Contreras-Ramos A. 2021. Comparative
3031 morphology of extant raptorial Mantispodea (Neuroptera: Mantispidae, Rhachiberothidae)
3032 suggests a non-monophyletic Mantispidae and a single origin of the raptorial condition within
3033 the superfamily. *Zootaxa*, 4992:1–89.

3034 Ashra H., Nair S. 2022. Review: Trait plasticity during plant-insect interactions: From molecular
3035 mechanisms to impact on community dynamics. *Plant Science*, 317:111188.

3036 Aspöck U. 1983. Das Genus *Berotha* Walker (Neuropteroidea: Planipennia: Berothidae). *Annalen Des*
3037 *Naturhistorischen Museums in Wien. Serie B Für Botanik Und Zoologie*, 84:463–478.

3038 Aspöck U. 1989. *Nyrma kervillea* Navás – eine Berothide! (Neuropteroidea: Planipennia). *Zeitschrift*
3039 *der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Österreichischer Entomologen*, 41:19–24.

3040 Aspöck U., Aspöck H. 1979. *Nyrma kervillea* Navás - Wiederentdeckung einer systematisch isolierten
3041 Hemerobiiden-Spezies in Kleinasien. *Zeitschrift der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Österreichischer*

- 3042 Entomologen, 31:92-96.
- 3043 Aspöck U., Aspöck H. 1982. Das genus *Nosybus* Navás, 1910 (Neuropteroidea: Planipennia:
3044 Berothidae). Zeitschrift der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Österreichischer Entomologen, 34:91–105.
- 3045 Aspöck U., Aspöck H. 1984. Die Berothiden Australiens (und Neuseelands) II: Die Genera *Trichoma*,
3046 Tillyard, *Trichoberotha* Handschin, *Protobiella* Tillyard und *Austroberothella* n. g.
3047 (Neuropteroidea: Planipennia: Berothidae). Zeitschrift der Arbeitsgemeinschaft
3048 Österreichischer Entomologen, 36:65–85.
- 3049 Aspöck U., Aspöck H. 1985. Das Genus *Lekrugeria* Navás (Neuropteroidea: Planipennia: Berothidae:
3050 Berothinae). Zeitschrift der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Österreichischer Entomologen, 37:85–98.
- 3051 Aspöck U., Aspöck H. 1996. Revision des Genus *Podallea* Navás, 1936 (Neuroptera: Berothidae:
3052 Berothinae). Mitteilungen der Münchener Entomologischen Gesellschaft, 86:99–144.
- 3053 Aspöck U., Aspöck H. 1997. Studies on new and poorly-known Rhachiberothidae (Insecta: Neuroptera)
3054 from subsaharan Africa. Annalen des Naturhistorischen Museums in Wien, 99B:1–20.
- 3055 Aspöck U., Aspöck H. 2008. Phylogenetic relevance of the genital sclerites of Neuroptera (Insecta:
3056 Holometabola). Systematic Entomology, 33:97–127.
- 3057 Aspöck U., Aspöck H., Johnson J.B., Donga T.K., Duelli P. 2020. *Rhachiella malawica* gen. nov., spec.
3058 nov. from Malawi-another beauty of the Afrotropics (Neuroptera: Rhachiberothidae). Zootaxa,
3059 4808:131–140.
- 3060 Aspöck U., Hynd W.R.B. 1995. A new genus and species of Nosybinae (Neuropt., Berothidae) from
3061 eastern Africa. Entomologist's Monthly Magazine, 131:107–113.
- 3062 Aspöck U., Mansell M.W. 1994. A revision of the family Rhachiberothidae Tjeder, 1959, stat. n.
3063 (Neuroptera). Systematic Entomology, 19:181–206.

3064 Aspöck U., Nemeschkal H.L. 1998. A cladistic analysis of the Berothidae (Neuroptera).
3065 Neuropterology 1997. Proceedings of the Sixth International Symposium on Neuropterology
3066 (13-16 July 1997, Helsinki, Finland), 209:45–63.

3067 Aspöck U., Randolph S. 2014. Beaded lacewings - a pictorial identification key to the genera, their
3068 biogeographics and a phylogentic analysis (Insecta: Neuroptera: Berothidae). Deutsche
3069 Entomologische Zeitschrift, Berlin (N.F.), 61:155–172.

3070 Azar D., Maksoud S., Huang D.Y. 2020. A new dipteromantispid from the mid-Cretaceous Burmese
3071 amber (Neuroptera: Dipteromantispidae). Palaeoentomology, 3:407–414.

3072 Bale J.S., Masters G.J., Hodkinson I.D., Awmack C., Bezemer T.M., Brown V.K., Butterfield J., Buse
3073 A., Coulson J.C., Farrar J., Good J.E.G., Harrington R., Hartley S., Jones T.H., Lindroth R.L.,
3074 Press M.C., Symrnioudis I., Watt A.D., Whittaker J.B. 2002. Herbivory in global climate
3075 change research: direct effects of rising temperature on insect herbivores. Global Change
3076 Biology, 8:1–16.

3077 Bao T., Wang B., Li J.G., Dilcher D. 2019. Pollination of Cretaceous flowers. Proceedings of the
3078 National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America, 116:24707–24711.

3079 Barba-Montoya J., dos Reis M., Schneider H., Donoghue P.C.J., Yang Z. 2018. Constraining
3080 uncertainty in the timescale of angiosperm evolution and the veracity of a Cretaceous
3081 Terrestrial Revolution. New Phytologist, 218:819–834.

3082 Batra S.W.T. 1972. Notes on the behavior and ecology of the mantispid, *Climaciella brunnea*
3083 *occidentalis*. Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society, 45:334–340.

3084 Benton M.J., Twitchett R.J. 2003. How to kill (almost) all life: the end-Permian extinction event.
3085 Trends in Ecology & Evolution, 18:358-365.

3086 Benton M.J., Wilf P., Sauquet H. 2022. The Angiosperm Terrestrial Revolution and the origins of
3087 modern biodiversity. *New Phytologist*, 233:2017–2035.

3088 Berner R.A. 2009. Phanerozoic atmospheric oxygen: new results using the geocarbsulf model.
3089 *American Journal of Science*, 309:603–606.

3090 Berner R.A., Kothavala Z. 2001. Geocarb III: A revised model of atmospheric CO₂ over phanerozoic
3091 time. *American Journal of Science*, 301:182–204.

3092 Bond D.P.G., Wignall P.B. 2013. Large igneous provinces and mass extinctions: An update.
3093 International Conference on Volcanism, Impacts, and Mass Extinctions - Causes and Effects.
3094 Nat Hist Museum, London, ENGLAND, p. 29-55.

3095 Breitkreuz L.C.V., Winterton S.L., Engel M.S. 2017. Wing tracheation in Chrysopidae and other
3096 Neuropterida (Insecta): a resolution of the confusion about vein fusion. *American Museum*
3097 *Novitates*, 3890:1–44.

3098 Brink H.-J. 2015. Periodic signals of the milky way concealed in terrestrial sedimentary basin fills and
3099 in planetary magmatism? *International Journal of Geosciences*, 6:831–845.

3100 Büsse S., Bäuml F., Gorb S.N. 2021. Functional morphology of the raptorial forelegs in *Mantispa*
3101 *styriaca* (Insecta: Neuroptera). *Zoomorphologie*, 140:231–241.

3102 Caldwell R.L., Dingle H. 1975. Ecology and evolution of agonistic behavior in stomatopods.
3103 *Naturwissenschaften*, 62:214–222.

3104 Cardinal S., Danforth B.N. 2013. Bees diversified in the age of eudicots. *Proceedings of the Royal*
3105 *Society B: Biological Sciences*, 280:20122686.

3106 Clapham M.E., Karr J.A. 2012. Environmental and biotic controls on the evolutionary history of insect
3107 body size. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*,

3108 109:10927–10930.

3109 Coates M.I., Clack J.A. 1990. Polydactyly in the earliest known tetrapod limbs. *Nature*, 347:66–69.

3110 Cogné J.P., Humler E. 2008. Global scale patterns of continental fragmentation: Wilson's cycles as a
3111 constraint for long-term sea-level changes. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 273:251–259.

3112 Condamine F.L., Clapham M.E., Kergoat G.J. 2016. Global patterns of insect diversification: Towards
3113 a reconciliation of fossil and molecular evidence? *Scientific Reports*, 6:19208.

3114 Condamine F.L., Silvestro D., Koppelhus E.B., Antonelli A. 2020. The rise of angiosperms pushed
3115 conifers to decline during global cooling. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of
3116 the United States of America*, 117:28867–28875.

3117 Copeland J., Carlson A.D. 1997. Prey capture in mantids: Prothoracic tibial flexion reflex. *Journal of
3118 Insect Physiology*, 23:1151–1156.

3119 Crampton G.C. 1928. A comparison of the neck and prothoracic sclerites throughout the orders of
3120 insects from the standpoint of phylogeny. *Transactions of the American Entomological Society*,
3121 52:199–248.

3122 Devetak D., Klokokovnik V. 2016. The feeding biology of adult lacewings (Neuroptera): A review.
3123 *Trends in Entomology*, 12:29–42.

3124 deVries M.S., Murphy E.A.K., Patek S.N. 2012. Strike mechanics of an ambush predator: The spearing
3125 mantis shrimp. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 215:4374–4384.

3126 Dorey J.B., Merritt D.J. 2017. First observations on the life cycle and mass eclosion events in a mantis
3127 fly (Family Mantispididae) in the subfamily Drepanicinae. *Biodiversity Data Journal*, 5:e21206.

3128 dos Santos E.B., Adami-Rodrigues K., de Lima F.J., Bantim R.A.M., Wappler T., Saraiva A.A.F. 2019.
3129 Evidence of plant-insect interaction in the Early Cretaceous Flora from the Crato Formation,

- 3130 Araripe Basin, Northeast Brazil. *Historical Biology*, 31:926–937.
- 3131 Dudley R. 1998. Atmospheric oxygen, giant Paleozoic insects and the evolution of aerial locomotor
3132 performance. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 201:1043–1050.
- 3133 Eltringham H. 1932. On an extrusible glandular structure in the abdomen of *Mantispa styriaca* Poda
3134 (Neuroptera). *Transactions of the [Royal] Entomological Society of London*, 80:103–105.
- 3135 Engel M.S., Grimaldi D.A. 2008. Grimaldi, D. A. 2008. Diverse Neuropterida in Cretaceous amber,
3136 with particular reference to the paleofauna of Myanmar (Insecta). *Nova Supplementa*
3137 *Entomologica*, 20:1–86.
- 3138 Engel M.S., Winterton S.L., Breitkreuz L.C.V. 2018. Phylogeny and evolution of Neuropterida: Where
3139 have wings of lace taken us? *Annual Review of Entomology*, 63:531–551.
- 3140 Erwin D.H. 1994. The Permo-Triassic extinction. *Nature*, 367:231–236.
- 3141 Faulkner D.K. 1992. A revision of the genus *Lomamyia* Banks (Planipennia: Berothidae) with an
3142 emphasis on the western United States species. Long Beach, California, USA, California State
3143 University, p. 119.
- 3144 Ferris G.F. 1940. The morphology of *Plega signata* (Hagen) (Neuroptera: Mantispidae).
3145 *Microentomology*, 5:33–56.
- 3146 Fikáček M., Beutel R.G., Cai C., Lawrence J.F., Newton A.F., Solodovnikov A., Ślipiński A., Thayer
3147 M.K., Yamamoto S. 2020. Reliable placement of beetle fossils via phylogenetic analyses -
3148 Triassic *Leehermania* as a case study (Staphylinidae or Myxophaga?). *Systematic Entomology*,
3149 45:175–187.
- 3150 Futuyma D.J. 2013. *Evolution*. Third ed. Oxford University Press.
- 3151 Gastil G. 1960. The distribution of mineral dates in time and space. *American Journal of Science*,

3152 258:1–35.

3153 Godoy O., Kraft N.J.B., Levine J.M. 2014. Phylogenetic relatedness and the determinants of
3154 competitive outcomes. *Ecology Letters*, 17:836–844.

3155 Goloboff P.A., Catalano S.A. 2016. TNT version 1.5, including a full implementation of phylogenetic
3156 morphometrics. *Cladistics*, 32:221–238.

3157 Gorden N.L.S., Adler L.S. 2018. Consequences of multiple flower-insect interactions for subsequent
3158 plant-insect interactions and plant reproduction. *American Journal of Botany*, 105:1835–1846.

3159 Graham J.B., Dudley R., Aguilar N.M., Gans C. 1995. Implications of the late Palaeozoic oxygen pulse
3160 for physiology and evolution. *Nature*, 375:117–120.

3161 Grimaldi D. 2000. A diverse fauna of Neuropterodea in amber from the Cretaceous of New Jersey.
3162 Leiden (The Netherlands): Backhuys Publishers, *The Quarterly Review of Biology*.

3163 Halsch C.A., Shapiro A.M., Fordyce J.A., Nice C.C., Thorne J.H., Waetjen D.P., Forister M.L. 2021.
3164 Insects and recent climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the*
3165 *United States of America*, 118.

3166 Haq B.U., Hardenbol J., Vail P.R. 1987. Chronology of fluctuating sea levels since the Triassic. *Science*,
3167 235:1156–1167.

3168 Hartenstein V. 1997. Introduction to insect sensory organs as a model system in sensory physiology and
3169 developmental biology. *Microscopy Research and Technique*, 39:467–469.

3170 Hautmann M. 2012. Extinction: End-Triassic Mass Extinction. *Encyclopedia of Life Sciences*:1–10.

3171 Hembry D.H., Weber M.G. 2020. Ecological interactions and macroevolution: a new field with old
3172 roots. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution and Systematics*, 51:215–243.

3173 Hoffman K.M. 1992. Systematics of the Mantispinae (Neuroptera: Mantispidae) of North, Central and

- 3174 South America. Clemson, South Carolina, USA, Clemson University, p. 501.
- 3175 Huang S., Ren D., Wang Y.J. 2019. A new basal beaded lacewing (Neuroptera: Berothidae) from mid-
3176 Cretaceous Myanmar amber. *Cretaceous Research*, 95:1–7.
- 3177 Hunt G., Slater G. 2016. Integrating paleontological and phylogenetic approaches to macroevolution.
3178 *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 47:189–213.
- 3179 Hunt T., Bergsten J., Levkanicova Z., Papadopoulou A., John O.S., Wild R., Hammond P.M., Ahrens D.,
3180 Balke M., Caterino M.S., Gomez-Zurita J., Ribera I., Barraclough T.G., Bocakova M., Bocak
3181 L., Vogler A.P. 2007. A comprehensive phylogeny of beetles reveals the evolutionary origins
3182 of a superradiation. *Science*, 318:1913–1916.
- 3183 Hwang W.S., Weirauch C. 2012. Evolutionary history of assassin bugs (Insecta: Hemiptera:
3184 Reduviidae): insights from divergence dating and ancestral state reconstruction. *Plos One*,
3185 7:e45523.
- 3186 Jepson J.E. 2015. A review of the current state of knowledge of fossil Mantispidae (Insecta:
3187 Neuroptera). *Zootaxa*, 3964:419–432.
- 3188 Jepson J.E., Heads S.W., Makarkin V.N., Ren D. 2013. New fossil mantidflies (Insecta: Neuroptera:
3189 Mantispidae) from the Mesozoic of north-eastern China. *Palaeontology*, 56:603–613.
- 3190 Jepson J.E., Khramov A.V., Ohl M. 2018. New Mesomantispinae (Insecta: Neuroptera: Mantispidae)
3191 from the Jurassic of Karatau, Kazakhstan. *Zootaxa*, 4402:563–574.
- 3192 Jouault C., Nel A., Legendre F., Condamine F.L. 2022a. Estimating the drivers of diversification of
3193 stoneflies through time and the limits of their fossil record. *Insect Systematics and Diversity*,
3194 6:4.
- 3195 Jouault C., Nel A., Perrichot V., Legendre F., Condamine F.L. 2022b. Multiple drivers and lineage-

3196 specific insect extinctions during the Permo-Triassic. *Nature Communications*, 13.

3197 Khramov A.V. 2013. New mantidflies (Neuroptera: Mantispidae) from the Upper Jurassic of
3198 Kazakhstan. *Insect Systematics & Evolution*, 44:221–230.

3199 Khramov A.V. 2023. The first Triassic beaded lacewing (Neuroptera: Berothidae) from Central Asia,
3200 with redescription of *Mesoberothen superba* (Riek, 1955). *Zootaxa*, 5330:287–294.

3201 Klein C.G., Pisani D., Field D.J., Lakin R., Wills M.A., Longrich N.R. 2021. Evolution and dispersal of
3202 snakes across the Cretaceous-Paleogene mass extinction. *nature Communications*, 12:5335.

3203 Koch N.M., Garwood R.J., Parry L.A. 2021. Fossils improve phylogenetic analyses of morphological
3204 characters. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 288:2021004.

3205 Kopylov D., Rasnitsyn A., Aristov D., Bashkuev A., Bazhenova N., Dmitriev V., Gorochov A., Ignatov
3206 M., Ivanov V., Khramov A., Legalov A., Lukashevich E., Mamontov Y., Melnitsky S., Ogłaza
3207 B., Ponomarenko A., Prokin A., Ryzhkova O., Shmakov A., Zmarzły M. 2021. The Khasurty
3208 fossil insect Lagerstätte. *Paleontological Journal*, 54:1221–1394.

3209 Kraft N.J.B., Godoy O., Levine J.M. 2015. Plant functional traits and the multidimensional nature of
3210 species coexistence. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of*
3211 *America*, 112:797–802.

3212 Labandeira C.C. 1998. Early history of arthropod and vascular plant associations. *Annual Review of*
3213 *Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 26:329–377.

3214 Lafarge T., Pateiro-Lopez B. 2017. alphashape3d: Implementation of the 3D alpha-shape for the
3215 reconstruction of 3D sets from a point cloud. R package version 1.3.:1–11.

3216 Lambeck K., Chappell J. 2001. Sea level change through the last glacial cycle. *Science*, 292:679-686.

3217 Lambkin K.J. 1986a. A revision of the Australian Mantispidae (Insecta: Neuroptera) with a contribution

- 3218 to the classification of the family. I. General and Drepanicinae. Australian Journal of Zoology,
3219 Supplementary Series, 116:1–142.
- 3220 Lambkin K.J. 1986b. A revision of the Australian Mantispidae (Insecta: Neuroptera) with a
3221 contribution to the classification of the family. II. Calomantispinae and Mantispinae.
3222 Australian Journal of Zoology, Supplementary Series, 117:1–113.
- 3223 Lehtonen S., Silvestro D., Karger D.N., Scotese C., Tuomisto H., Kessler M., Pena C., Wahlberg N.,
3224 Antonelli A. 2017. Environmentally driven extinction and opportunistic origination explain
3225 fern diversification patterns. Scientific Reports, 7:4831.
- 3226 Li D., Aspöck H., Aspöck U., Liu X.Y. 2018. A review of the beaded lacewings (Neuroptera:
3227 Berothidae) from China. Zootaxa, 4500:235–257.
- 3228 Li D., Aspöck H., Aspöck U., Liu X.Y. 2020a. New beaded lacewings (Insecta: Neuroptera: Berothidae)
3229 from Indochina. Zootaxa, 4890:509–520.
- 3230 Li H.Y., Wu C., Ohl M., Liu X.Y. 2020b. A new sexually dimorphic mantidfly species of *Allomantispa*
3231 Liu et al., 2015 from China (Neuroptera: Mantispidae). Journal of Asia-Pacific Entomology,
3232 23:988–1002.
- 3233 Li H.Y., Zhuo D., Cao L.R., Wang B., Poinar G., Ohl M., Liu X.Y. 2022. New cretaceous fossil
3234 mantispids highlight the palaeodiversity of the extinct subfamily Doratomantispinae
3235 (Neuroptera: Mantispidae) Organisms Diversity & Evolution, 22:731–731.
- 3236 Li H.Y., Zhuo D., Wang B., Liu X.Y. 2020c. New dipteromantispids (Insecta: Neuroptera:
3237 Dipteromantispidae) from mid-Cretaceous Myanmar amber. Cretaceous Research, 116:1–10.
- 3238 Liu X.Y., Aspöck H., Winterton S.L., Zhang W.W., Aspöck U. 2017. Phylogeny of pleasing lacewings
3239 (Neuroptera: Dilaridae) with a revised generic classification and description of a new

- 3240 subfamily. *Systematic Entomology*, 42:448–471.
- 3241 Liu X.Y., Lu X.M., Zhang W.W. 2016. *Halteriomantispa grimaldii* gen. et sp. nov.: A new genus and
3242 species of the family Dipteromantispidae (Insecta: Neuroptera) from the mid-Cretaceous
3243 amber of Myanmar. *Zoological Systematics*, 41:165–172.
- 3244 Liu X.Y., Winterton S.L., Wu C., Piper R., Ohl M. 2015. A new genus of mantidflies discovered in the
3245 Oriental region, with a higher-level phylogeny of Mantispidae (Neuroptera) using DNA
3246 sequences and morphology. *Systematic Entomology*, 40:183–206.
- 3247 Liu Z.J., Huang D.Y., Cai C.Y., Wang X. 2018. The core eudicot boom registered in Myanmar amber.
3248 *Scientific Reports*, 8:16765.
- 3249 Lloyd G., Ruta M., Tarver J., Benton M. 2008. Dinosaurs and the Cretaceous terrestrial revolution.
3250 *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 28:107A–107A.
- 3251 Losos J.B. 2008. Phylogenetic niche conservatism, phylogenetic signal and the relationship between
3252 phylogenetic relatedness and ecological similarity among species. *Ecology Letters*, 11:995–
3253 1003.
- 3254 Louca S., Pennell M.W. 2020. Extant timetrees are consistent with a myriad of diversification histories.
3255 *Nature*, 580:502–505.
- 3256 Loxton R.G., Nicholls I. 1979. Functional-morphology of the praying mantis forelimb (Dictyoptera,
3257 Mantodea). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 66:185–203.
- 3258 Lu X.M., Liu X.Y. 2021. The Neuropterida from the mid-Cretaceous of Myanmar: A spectacular
3259 palaeodiversity bridging the Mesozoic and present faunas. *Cretaceous Research*, 121:1–15.
- 3260 Lu X.M., Wang B., Zhang W.W., Ohl M., Engel M.S., Liu X.Y. 2020. Cretaceous diversity and
3261 disparity in a lacewing lineage of predators (Neuroptera: Mantispidae). *Proceedings of the*

- 3262 Royal Society of London (B), 287:20200629.
- 3263 Machado R.J.P., Krolow T.K. 2016. A new species of *Spiroberotha* Adams 1989 (Neuroptera:
3264 Berothidae) and the first record of the genus in Brazil. *Zootaxa*, 4093:127–134.
- 3265 Machado R.J.P., Martins C., Aspöck H., Tavares L., Aspöck U. 2022. The first cave associated genus of
3266 Berothidae (Insecta: Neuroptera), and the biogeographical history of Cyrenoberothinae.
3267 *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 195:1422–1444.
- 3268 Machado R.J.P., Rafael J.A. 2010. Taxonomy of the Brazilian species previously placed in *Mantispa*
3269 Illiger, 1798 (Neuroptera: Mantispidae), with the description of three new species. *Zootaxa*,
3270 2454:1–61.
- 3271 MacLeod E.G., Adams P.A. 1967. A review of the taxonomy and morphology of the Berothidae, with
3272 the description of a new subfamily from Chile (Neuroptera). *Psyche*, 74:237–265.
- 3273 Makarkin V., Yang Q., Dong R. 2013. A new Cretaceous family of enigmatic two-winged lacewings
3274 (Neuroptera). *Fossil Record*, 16:67–75.
- 3275 Makarkin V.N. 2017. An interesting new genus of Berothinae (Neuroptera: Berothidae) from the early
3276 Eocene Green River Formation, Colorado. *Zootaxa*, 4226:594–600.
- 3277 Makarkin V.N. 2018. A new species of *Haploberotha* (Neuroptera: Berothidae) from mid-Cretaceous
3278 Burmese amber. *Cretaceous Research*, 90:375–381.
- 3279 Makarkin V.N., Kupryjanowicz J. 2010. A new mantispid-like species of Rhachiberothinae (Neuroptera:
3280 Berothidae) from Baltic Amber, with a critical review of the fossil record of the subfamily.
3281 *Acta Geologica Sinica-English Edition*, 84:655–664.
- 3282 Makarkin V.N., Ohl M. 2015. An important new fossil genus of Berothinae (Neuroptera: Berothidae)
3283 from Baltic amber. *Zootaxa*, 3946:401–415.

3284 Makarkin V.N., Yang Q., Peng Y., Ren D. 2012. A comparative overview of the neuropteran
3285 assemblage of the Lower Cretaceous Yixian Formation (China), with description of a new
3286 genus of Psychopsidae (Insecta: Neuroptera). *Cretaceous Research*, 35:57–68.

3287 Makarkin V.N., Yang Q., Reng D. 2011. Two new species of *Sinosmylites* Hong (Neuroptera,
3288 Berothidae) from the Middle Jurassic of China, with notes on Mesoberothidae. *Zookeys*:199–
3289 215.

3290 McKenna D.D., Wild A.L., Kanda K., Bellamy C.L., Beutel R.G., Caterino M.S., Farnum C.W., Hawks
3291 D.C., Ivie M.A., Jameson M.L., Leschen R.A.B., Marvaldi A.E., McHugh J.V., Newton A.F.,
3292 Robertson J.A., Thayer M.K., Whiting M.F., Lawrence J.F., Slipinski A., Maddison D.R.,
3293 Farrell B.D. 2015. The beetle tree of life reveals that Coleoptera survived end-Permian mass
3294 extinction to diversify during the Cretaceous terrestrial revolution. *Systematic Entomology*,
3295 40:835–880.

3296 Meinander M. 1972. Coniopterygidae from Mongolia III (Neuroptera). *Notulae Entomologicae*,
3297 52:127–138.

3298 Monserrat V.J. 2006. Nuevos datos sobre algunas especies de la familia Berothidae (Insecta:
3299 Neuroptera). *Heteropterus: Revista de Entomología*, 6:173–207.

3300 Moreau C.S., Bell C.D., Vila R., Archibald S.B., Pierce N.E. 2006. Phylogeny of the ants:
3301 diversification in the age of angiosperms. *Science*, 312:101-104.

3302 Murdoch D., Adler D. 2021. rgl: 3D Visualization using OpenGL. R package version 0.10 8.3.

3303 Nakahara W. 1961. A new species of the Mantispidae from Japan (Neuroptera). *Mushi*, 35:63–66.

3304 Nakamine H., Yamamoto S., Takahashi Y. 2020. Hidden diversity of small predators: new thorny
3305 lacewings from mid-Cretaceous amber from northern Myanmar (Neuroptera:

- 3306 Rhachiberothidae: Paraberotherinae). *Geological Magazine*, 157:1149–1175.
- 3307 Nakamine H., Yamamoto S., Takahashi Y., Li H.Y., Liu X.Y. 2022. A remarkable new thorny lacewing
3308 from mid-Cretaceous amber from northern Myanmar (Neuroptera: Rhachiberothidae). *PalZ*,
3309 96:207–217.
- 3310 Nel A., Delclòs X., Hutin A. 2005. Mesozoic chrysopid-like Planipennia: a phylogenetic approach
3311 (Insecta : Neuroptera). *Annales De La Societe Entomologique De France*, 41:29–68.
- 3312 New T.R. 1989. Planipennia, Lacewings. *Handbuch der Zoologie*. Vol. 4 (Arthropoda: Insecta), Part 30.
3313 Berlin, Walter de Gruyter.
- 3314 Opler P.A. 1981. Polymorphic mimicry of polistine wasps by a neotropical Neuropteran. *Biotropica*,
3315 13:165–176.
- 3316 Oswald J.D. 2022. Neuropterida species of the world. *Lacewing Digital Library*. Research Publication
3317 No. 1.
- 3318 Panfilov D.V. 1980. Novye predstaviteli setcharokrylykh (Neuroptera) iz yury Karatau [=New
3319 representatives of lacewings (Neuroptera) from the Jurassic of Karatau]. Pp. 82–111. In: Dolin,
3320 V. G.; Panfilov, D. V.; Ponomarenko, A. G.; Pritykina, L. N. *Iskopaemye nasekomye*
3321 *mezozoya* [=Fossil insects of the Mesozoic].
- 3322 Parmesan C., Yohe G. 2003. A globally coherent fingerprint of climate change impacts across natural
3323 systems. *Nature*, 421:37–42.
- 3324 Pearce M.A., Jarvis I., Tocher B.A. 2009. The Cenomanian–Turonian boundary event, OAE2 and
3325 palaeoenvironmental change in epicontinental seas: New insights from the dinocyst and
3326 geochemical records. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 280: 207–234.
- 3327 Pérez-de la Fuente R., Peñalver E. 2019a. A mantidfly in Cretaceous Spanish amber provides insights

- 3328 into the evolution of integumentary specialisations on the raptorial foreleg. *Scientific Reports*,
- 3329 9:1–16.
- 3330 Pérez-de la Fuente R., Peñalver E. 2019b. A mantidfly in Cretaceous Spanish amber provides insights
- 3331 into the evolution of integumentary specialisations on the raptorial foreleg. *Scientific Reports*,
- 3332 9:1–16.
- 3333 Peris D., Condamine F.L. 2024. The angiosperm radiation played a dual role in the diversification of
- 3334 insects and insect pollinators. *Nature Communications*, 15.
- 3335 Poivre C. 1978. Morphologie externe comparée de *Gerstaeckerella gigantea* Enderlein [Planipennia,
- 3336 Mantispidae]. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France (N.S.)*, 14:191–206.
- 3337 Present T.M., Adkins J.F., Fischer W.W. 2020. Variability in Sulfur Isotope Records of Phanerozoic
- 3338 Seawater Sulfate. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 47.
- 3339 Quental T.B., Marshall C.R. 2010. Diversity dynamics: Molecular phylogenies need the fossil record.
- 3340 *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 25:434–441.
- 3341 Rabosky D.L., Santini F., Eastman J., Smith S.A., Sidlauskas B., Chang J., Alfaro M.E. 2013. Rates of
- 3342 speciation and morphological evolution are correlated across the largest vertebrate radiation.
- 3343 *Nature Communications*, 4:1958.
- 3344 Reynoso-Velasco D., Contreras-Ramose A. 2019. Taxonomic review of the mantidfly genus *Nolima*
- 3345 Navas (Neuroptera, Mantispidae, Calomantispinae). *Zookeys*:131–158.
- 3346 Romer A.S. 1966. *Vertebrate paleontology*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- 3347 Ross A. 2021. Supplement to the Burmese (Myanmar) amber checklist and bibliography, 2020.
- 3348 *Palaeoentomology*, 4:057–076.
- 3349 Saputra D.D., Sari R.R., Hairiah K., Widiyanto, Suprayogo D., van Noordwijk M. 2022. Recovery after

3350 volcanic ash deposition: vegetation effects on soil organic carbon, soil structure and
3351 infiltration rates. *Plant and Soil*, 474:163–179.

3352 Schluter D. 2000. Ecological character displacement in adaptive radiation. *American Naturalist*,
3353 156:S4-S16.

3354 Schoener T.W. 1974. Resource partitioning in ecological communities. *Science*, 185:27–39.

3355 Scotese C. 2016. Some thoughts on global climate change: The transition for Icehouse to hothouse
3356 conditions. GSA Annual Meeting in Denver.

3357 Shi C.F., Yang Q., Shi C.K., Labandeira C.C., Pang H., Ren D. 2020. Cretaceous mantid lacewings
3358 with specialized raptorial forelegs illuminate modification of prey capture (Insecta:
3359 Neuroptera). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 190:1054–1070.

3360 Sigurdsson H. 1988. Assessment of the atmospheric impact of volcanic eruptions. *Conf on Global
3361 Catastrophes in Earth History : An Interdisciplinary Conference on Impacts, Volcanism, and
3362 Mass Mortality*. Snowbird, Ut, p. 99–110.

3363 Silvestro D., Antonelli A., Salamin N., Quental T.B. 2015a. The role of clade competition in the
3364 diversification of North American canids. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences
3365 of the United States of America*, 112:8684–8689.

3366 Silvestro D., Cascales-Minana B., Bacon C.D., Antonelli A. 2015b. Revisiting the origin and
3367 diversification of vascular plants through a comprehensive Bayesian analysis of the fossil
3368 record. *New Phytologist*, 207:425–436.

3369 Snedden J.W., Liu C. 2010. A compilation of Phanerozoic sea-level change, coastal onlaps and
3370 recommended sequence designations. *Search and Discovery Article*:40594.

3371 Snedden J.W., Liu C.J. 2011. Recommendations for a uniform chronostratigraphic designation system

- 3372 for Phanerozoic depositional sequences. *Aapg Bulletin*, 95:1095–1122.
- 3373 Snyman L.P., Ohl M., Pirk C.W.W., Sole C.L. 2021. A review of the biology and biogeography of
3374 Mantispidae (Neuroptera). *Insect Systematics & Evolution*, 52:125–166.
- 3375 Snyman L.P., Sole C.L., Ohl M. 2017. A revision of and keys to the genera of the Mantispinae of the
3376 Oriental and Palearctic regions (Neuroptera: Mantispidae). *Zootaxa*, 4450:501–549.
- 3377 So K.-S., Won C.-G. 2022. A new fossil mantis fly (Insecta: Neuroptera: Mantispidae) from the Lower
3378 Cretaceous of the Democratic People's Republic of Korea. *Cretaceous Research*, 135:105175.
- 3379 Song H.J., Amedegnato C., Cigliano M.M., Desutter-Grandcolas L., Heads S.W., Huang Y., Otte D.,
3380 Whiting M.F. 2015. 300 million years of diversification: elucidating the patterns of
3381 orthopteran evolution based on comprehensive taxon and gene sampling. *Cladistics*, 31:621–
3382 651.
- 3383 Tang C., Davis K.E., Delmer C., Yang D., Wills M.A. 2018. Elevated atmospheric CO₂
3384 promoted speciation in mosquitoes (Diptera, Culicidae). *Communications Biology*, 1.
- 3385 Tao Q.Q., Tamura K., Mello B., Kumar S. 2020. Reliable confidence intervals for RelTime estimates of
3386 evolutionary divergence times. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 37:280–290.
- 3387 Tauber C.A. 1969. Taxonomy and biology of the lacewing genus *Meleoma* (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae).
3388 University of California Publications in Entomology.
- 3389 Tauber C.A., Sosa F., Albuquerque G.S., Tauber M.J. 2017. Revision of the Neotropical green lacewing
3390 genus *Ungla* (Neuroptera, Chrysopidae). *ZooKeys*, 674:1–188.
- 3391 Tjeder B. 1959. Neuroptera-Planipennia. The lace-wings of southern Africa. 2. Family Berothidae.
3392 South African Animal Life, 6:256–314.
- 3393 Tjeder B. 1963. A new *Chrysopa* from Pakistan (Neur. Chrysopidae). *Entomologisk Tidskrift*, 84:125–

3394 128.

3395 Tjeder B. 1968. The genus *Mucroberotha* Tjed. and its systematic position (Neuroptera). Entomologisk
3396 Tidskrift, 89:3–18.

3397 Upchurch P., Hunn C.A., Norman D.B. 2002. An analysis of dinosaurian biogeography: evidence for
3398 the existence of vicariance and dispersal patterns caused by geological events. Proceedings of
3399 the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences, 269:613-621.

3400 Vermeij G.J. 2016. Gigantism and its implications for the history of life. Plos One, 11:e014609.

3401 Violle C., Enquist B.J., McGill B.J., Jiang L., Albert C.H., Hulshof C., Jung V., Messier J. 2012. The
3402 return of the variance: Intraspecific variability in community ecology. Trends in Ecology &
3403 Evolution, 27:244–252.

3404 Vitousek P.M., Chadwick O.A. 2013. Pedogenic Thresholds and Soil Process Domains in Basalt-
3405 Derived Soils. Ecosystems, 16:1379–1395.

3406 Wahlberg N., Wheat C.W., Pena C. 2013. Timing and patterns in the taxonomic diversification of
3407 Lepidoptera (butterflies and moths). Plos One, 8:e80875.

3408 Wainwright P.C., Alfaro M.E., Bolnick D.I., Hulsey C.D. 2005. Many-to-one mapping of form to
3409 function: A general principle in organismal design? Integrative and Comparative Biology,
3410 45:256–262.

3411 Wang J.L., Shi C.F., Liu X.Y., Shih C.K., Ren* D., Wang* Y.J. 2024. A new stem-group mantispoid
3412 lineage (Insecta: Neuroptera) equipped with unique raptorial structures from the Middle
3413 Jurassic of China. Journal of Systematics and Evolution.

3414 Wang K.J., Yan X.H., Chen L.F. 2011. Geometric double-entity model for recognizing far-near
3415 relations of clusters. Science China-Information Sciences, 54:2040–2050.

3416 Wedmann S., Makarkin V. 2007. A new genus of Mantispidae (Insecta: Neuroptera) from the Eocene of
3417 Germany, with a review of the fossil record and palaeobiogeography of the family. *Zoological*
3418 *Journal of the Linnean Society*, 149:701–716.

3419 Weigelt P., Steinbauer M.J., Cabral J.S., Krefl H. 2016. Late Quaternary climate change shapes island
3420 biodiversity. *Nature*, 532:99–+.

3421 Wickham H. 2009. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*.

3422 Willmann R. 1990. The phylogenetic position of the Rhachiberothinae and the basal sister-group
3423 relationships within the Mantispidae (Neuroptera). *Systematic Entomology*, 15:253–265.

3424 Winterton S.L., Lemmon A.R., Gillung J.P., Garzon I.J., Badano D., Bakkes D.K., Breitkreuz L.C.V.,
3425 Engel M.S., Lemmon E.M., Liu X.Y., Machado R.J.P., Skevington J.H., Oswald J.D. 2018.
3426 Evolution of lacewings and allied orders using anchored phylogenomics (Neuroptera,
3427 Megaloptera, Raphidioptera). *Systematic Entomology*, 43:330–354.

3428 Wise K.A.J. 1992. The New Zealand species of Berothidae (Insecta: Neuroptera). *Records of the*
3429 *Auckland Institute and Museum*, 29:167–177.

3430 Yang Y., Li H.Y., Wang B., Zhang W.W., Liu X.Y. 2020. New beaded lacewings (Neuroptera:
3431 Berothidae) from the mid-Cretaceous of Myanmar with specialized cephalic structures.
3432 *Cretaceous Research*, 108:104–348.

3433 Yin Z.W., Lu L., Yamamoto S., Thayer M.K., Newton A.F., Cai C.Y. 2021. Dasycerine rove beetles:
3434 Cretaceous diversification, phylogeny and historical biogeography (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae:
3435 Dasycerinae). *Cladistics*, 37:185–210.

3436 Yu G.C., Smith D.K., Zhu H.C., Guan Y., Lam T.T.Y. 2017. GGTREE: an R package for visualization
3437 and annotation of phylogenetic trees with their covariates and other associated data. *Methods*

- 3438 in Ecology and Evolution, 8:28–36.
- 3439 Yu Y.L., Zhang C., Xu X. 2021. Deep time diversity and the early radiations of birds. Proceedings of
3440 the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America, 118:e2019865118.
- 3441 Yu Y.L., Zhang C., Xu X. 2023. Complex macroevolution of pterosaurs. Current Biology, 33:770–779.
- 3442 Yuan D., Ren D., Wang Y. 2016. New beaded lacewings (Neuroptera: Berothidae) from Upper
3443 Cretaceous Myanmar amber. Cretaceous Research, 68:40 – 48.
- 3444 Zaffosa A., Finnegan S., Peters S.E. 2017. Plate tectonic regulation of global marine animal diversity.
3445 Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America, 114:5653-
3446 5658.
- 3447 Zhang C., Wang M. 2019. Bayesian tip dating reveals heterogeneous morphological clocks in
3448 Mesozoic birds. Royal Society Open Science, 6:182062.
- 3449
- 3450

3452

3453 **Figure S1. Habitus photos of representatives of Mantispoidea.** (a-b) Berothidae. a,
 3454 *Osmyloberotha magnimaculata* Li et al., ventral view (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19004). b,
 3455 *Ansoberotha jiewenae* Yang, Shi & Ren, lateral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-014). (c-d)
 3456 Rhachiberothidae. (c) *Creagroparaberotha* sp.1, lateral view (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-022). (d)
 3457 *Dicranoberotha zhangzhiqiae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, lateral view (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-027).
 3458 (e) *Kurtdipteromantispa relictata* Li et al., Dipteromantispidae, dorsal view (Holotype, ♂, CAU-
 3459 BA-GYH-19008). (f-j), Mantispidae. (f) *Mesomantispoides felixporcus* Li et al., dorsal view
 3460 (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171728). (g) *Parvosymphrasites aploneura* Li et al., lateral view (Holotype, ♂,
 3461 NIGP171730). (h) *Haplacantha robusta* Li et al., dorsal view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171731). (i)

3462 *Doratomantispa gaoyuhei* Li et al., lateral view (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19003). (j)

3463 *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al., lateral view (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-034). Scale bars in (a-h),

3464 1 mm, in (i-j), 2 mm.

3465

3466 **Figure S2. Raptorial foreleg photos of representatives in Mantispoidea from mid-Cretaceous**
3467 **Myanmar amber.** (a-f) Rhachiberothidae. (a-b) Raptorial foreleg of *Paraberothoides longispina*
3468 Li et al. (Holotype, ♂, EMTG BU001998). (a) Holistic view. (b) Protarsus. (c) Raptorial foreleg of
3469 *Dicranoberothena zhangzhiqiae* Zhuo, Li & Liu (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-027), holistic view.
3470 (d-f) Raptorial foreleg of *Dicranoberothena liumohanae* Zhuo, Li & Liu. (d) Profemoral ISs
3471 (Holotype, NIGP171723). (e) Protibia (Holotype, NIGP171723). (f) Protarsus (Paratype, ♀,
3472 NIGP171725). (g-z) Mantispididae. (g-i) Raptorial foreleg of *Mesomantispidoides felixoporcus* Li et
3473 al. (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171728). (g) Holistic view. (h) Major process, distal portion of protibia and
3474 protarsus. (i) Protibia. (j-k) Raptorial foreleg of *Parvoasymphrasites aploneurus* Li et al.
3475 (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171730). (j) Holistic view. (k) Profemoral ventral ISs and protibia. (l-o)
3476 Raptorial foreleg of *Haplacantha robusta* Li et al. (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171731). (l) Holistic view.
3477 (m) Median portion of protibia, showing the detail of its ventral specialized setae. (n-o) protarsus.
3478 (p-r) Raptorial foreleg of *Haplacantha tenuis* Li et al. (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171732). (p) Holistic
3479 view. (q) distal portion of protibia, showing the detail of its ventral specialized setae. (r) Protarsus.
3480 (s-v) Raptorial foreleg of *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al. (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-034). (s)
3481 Holistic view. (t) median portion of protibia, showing the detail of its ventral specialized setae. (u-
3482 v) protarsus. (w-x) Raptorial foreleg of *Dicranomantispa zhouae* Lu et al. (Holotype, ♂, CAU-
3483 BA-ZM-19003). (w) Holistic view. (x) protarsus. (y-z) Raptorial foreleg of *Psilomantispa*
3484 *abnormis* Lu et al.. (y) Holistic view (NIGP171734). (z) Protarsus (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-LX-
3485 19004). Scale bars in (g), (s) and (w), 1 mm, in others, 0.2 mm.

3486

3487 **Figure S3. Phylogenetic trees based on the morphological matrix of 146 taxa × 232**

3488 **characters, using maximum parsimony analysis (traditional search), maximum likelihood**

3489 **analysis and Bayesian inferences. (a) Strict consensus of 10 most parsimonious trees of length**

3490 **964 under equal weighting. Unambiguous morphological character states are shown on the tree**

3491 **with a black circle as the homologous state and a white circle as the homoplasious state. Bremer**

3492 **support values/Bootstrap values are shown at relevant nodes. Consistency index = 0.350, retention**

3493 **index = 0.856. (b-c) Results of statistical analyses using the mkv+ Γ model. (b) Maximum**

3494 **likelihood phylogram (MK+FQ+ASC+R3). Numbers at nodes are bootstrap frequencies from**

3495 **1000 replicates. (c) The maximum compatibility tree from Bayesian inference. Numbers at nodes**

3496 **are posterior probabilities. Scale bar units are expected number of substitutions per site.**

3497 **Abbreviations: BM1, The first major clade of Berothidae; BM2, The second major clade of**

3498 **Berothidae; R1, The first major clade of Rhachiberothidae; R2, The second major clade of**

3499 **Rhachiberothidae; R3, The third major clade of Rhachiberothidae; PD,**

3500 ***Paradoxoberothes*+*Dicranoberothes* clade; TPM, Tubular-pronotum mantispid clade; DCM,**

3501 ***Drepanicinae*+*Calomantispinae*+*Mantispinae* clade.**

3502

3503 **Figure S4. Phylogenetic trees based on the morphological matrix of 132 taxa × 232**

3504 **characters, using maximum parsimony analysis (traditional search), maximum likelihood**

3505 **analysis and Bayesian inferences. (a) Strict consensus of 10 most parsimonious trees of length**

3506 **941 under equal weighting. Unambiguous morphological character states are shown on the tree**

3507 **with a black circle as the homologous state and a white circle as the homoplasious state. Bremer**

3508 **support values/Bootstrap values are shown at relevant nodes. Consistency index = 0.358, retention**

3509 **index = 0.856. (b-c) Results of statistical analyses using the mkv+ Γ model. (b) Maximum**

3510 **likelihood phylogram (MK+FQ+ASC+R3). Numbers at nodes are bootstrap frequencies from**

3511 **1000 replicates. (c) The maximum compatibility tree from Bayesian inference. Numbers at nodes**

3512 **are posterior probabilities. Scale bar units are expected number of substitutions per site.**

3513 **Abbreviations: BM1, The first major clade of Berothidae; BM2, The second major clade of**

3514 **Berothidae; R1, The first major clade of Rhachiberothidae; R2, The second major clade of**

3515 **Rhachiberothidae; R3, The third major clade of Rhachiberothidae; PD,**

3516 ***Paradoxoberotha*+*Dicranoberotha* clade; TPM, Tubular-pronotum mantispid clade; DCM,**

3517 ***Drepanicinae*+*Calomantispinae*+*Mantispinae* clade.**

3518

3519 **Figure S5. Phylogenetic trees based on the morphological matrix of 143 taxa × 232**

3520 **characters, using maximum parsimony analysis (traditional search), maximum likelihood**

3521 **analysis and Bayesian inferences. (a) Strict consensus of 10 most parsimonious trees of length**

3522 **948 under equal weighting. Unambiguous morphological character states are shown on the tree**

3523 **with a black circle as the homologous state and a white circle as the homoplasious state. Bremer**

3524 **support values/Bootstrap values are shown at relevant nodes. Consistency index = 0.355, retention**

3525 **index = 0.859. (b-c) Results of statistical analyses using the mkv+ Γ model. (b) Maximum**

3526 **likelihood phylogram (MK+FQ+ASC+R3). Numbers at nodes are bootstrap frequencies from**

3527 **1000 replicates. (c) The maximum compatibility tree from Bayesian inference. Numbers at nodes**

3528 **are posterior probabilities. Scale bar units are expected number of substitutions per site.**

3529 **Abbreviations: BM1, The first major clade of Berothidae; BM2, The second major clade of**

3530 **Berothidae; R1, The first major clade of Rhachiberothidae; R2, The second major clade of**

3531 **Rhachiberothidae; R3, The third major clade of Rhachiberothidae; PD,**

3532 ***Paradoxoberotha*+*Dicranoberotha* clade; TPM, Tubular-pronotum mantispid clade; DCM,**

3533 ***Drepanicinae*+*Calomantispinae*+*Mantispinae* clade.**

3535

3536 **Figure S6. The summary covering phylogeny, morphological evolution of the prothorax and**

3537 **foreleg, as well as changes in HP and foreleg overall morphological states and body size over**

3538 **time in Mantispoidea. (a) The summary covering phylogeny, morphological evolution of the**

3539 **prothorax and foreleg. The number along the branch tip and below the node represent the**

3540 **comprehensive PCoA score of foreleg, summarized from the results of maximum likelihood**

3541 **reconstruction of ancestral states. The magnitude and direction of the value represents the**

3542 **morphological polarity measured by IASM (marked by star and dashed line) and the extent to the**

3543 **overall morphology of foreleg deviated from IASM. The higher difference between the score and**

3544 the IASM value the higher morphological deviation of the taxonomic group from IASM (i.e.,
3545 more apomorphic changes). 1-37, Representative phenotypes of the foreleg and i-xi,
3546 Representative phenotypes of the prothorax in Mantispoidea. Deviation in morphological states
3547 over time of (b) HP and (c) Foreleg respectively for overall Mantispoidea, Berthidae, raptorial
3548 Mantispoidea, Rhachiberthidae, Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae, using comprehensive
3549 PCoA scores as the proxy and the score of IASM serving as the origin dotted line, based on the
3550 maximum likelihood reconstruction of ancestral states. The direction and magnitude of the value
3551 represents the morphological polarity (measured by the value of IASM) and the extent to the
3552 overall morphology of anatomical regions deviated from IASM. The higher difference between
3553 the score and IASM indicates the higher morphological deviation (i.e., more apomorphic changes).
3554 (d) Deviation in body size across time respectively for overall Mantispoidea, Berthidae, raptorial
3555 Mantispoidea, Rhachiberthidae, Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae, using forewing length
3556 (MmF) as the proxy. Representative phenotypes of the foreleg in Mantispoidea: 1, *Osmyloberotha*
3557 *magnimaculata* Li et al.. 2, *Haploberotha persephone* Engel & Grimaldi. 3, *Podallea vasseana*
3558 (Navás), adapted from Tjeder (1959): Figure 301. 4, *Archarhachiberotha longitarsa* Wang, Ren &
3559 Wang, adapted from Wang et al. (2024). 5, *Rhachiella malawica* Aspöck et al., adapted from
3560 Aspöck et al. (2020): Figure 3. 6, *Hoelzeliella manselli* Aspöck & Aspöck, adapted from Aspöck
3561 & Aspöck (1997): Figure 35. 7, *Mucroberotha copeland* Aspöck & Aspöck, adapted from Aspöck
3562 & Aspöck (1997): Figure 25. 8, *Paradoxoberotha chimaera* Nakamine et al.. 9, *Dicranoberotha*
3563 *liumohanae* Zhuo, Li & Liu. 10, *Raptorapax terribilissima* Petrulevičius, Azar & Nel, adapted
3564 from Petrulevičius, Azar & Nel (2010): Figure Plate II3. 11, *Creagroparaberotha* sp.. 12,
3565 *Paraberthoides longispina* Li et al.. 13, *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al.. 14, *Acanthoberotha*

3566 *cuspis* Nakamine et al.. 15, *Astioberotha falcipes* Nakamine et al.. 16, *Paradipteromantispa*
3567 *polyneura* Li et al.. 17, *Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* Li et al.. 18, *Enigmadipteromantispa dilatata*
3568 Li et al.. 19, *Archaeodrepanicus nuddsi* Jepson et al.. 20, *Archaeodrepanicus* sp.. 21, *Trichoscelia*
3569 sp.. 22, *Plega dactylota* Rehn. 23, *Sinomesomantispa microdentata* Jepson et al.. 24,
3570 *Habrosymphrosis xiai* Shi et al., 2019. 25, *Mesomantispoides felixoporcus* Li et al.. 26,
3571 *Haplacantha robusta* Li et al.. 27, *Haplacantha tenuis* Li et al.. 28, *Paradoxomantispa jiaoxiaoae*
3572 Lu et al.. 29, *Doratomantispa zhuozhengmingi* Li et al.. 30, *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al..
3573 31, *Dicranomantispa zhouae* Lu et al.. 32, *Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al.. 33, *Aragomantispa*
3574 *lacerata* Pérez de la Fuente & Peñalver, adapted from Pérez de la Fuente & Peñalver (2019):
3575 Figure 5. 34, *Allomantispa coniprocesa* Li et al., 2020. 35, *Theristria delicatula* (Westwood). 36,
3576 *Calomantispa venusta* Lambkin. 37, *Eumantispa pseudoharmandi* Okamoto.

3577

3578 **Figure S7. Phylomorphospace comparisons for different taxonomic groups and**
 3579 **morphological disparity (sum of variances as the proxy) dynamics in Mantispoidea, based on**
 3580 **the results of the disparity analyses of MORD matrices.** The phylomorphospace comparisons
 3581 are based on (a) Whole body excluding genitalia (d) HP and (g) PW. The number on each 3D
 3582 convex hull is its volume value (see details in Supplementary Table S4). Morphological disparity
 3583 through time of (b) Whole body, (c) Whole body excluding genitalia, (e) HP, (f) Foreleg and (h)
 3584 PW respectively for overall Mantispoidea, Berothidae, raptorial Mantispoidea, Rhachiberothidae,

3585 Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae. The area around medians are 95% and 50% highest
3586 posterior density (HPD) intervals. (See the interactive 3D graphics in Data availability)

3587
3588 **Figure S8. Habitus photos of representatives in Berothidae.** (a) *Osmyloberotha dispersa* Li et
3589 al., lateral view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171721). (b) *Osmyloberotha magnimaculata*, dorsal view
3590 (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19004). (c) *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov, dorsal view (♀,
3591 BXAM BA-NEU-36). (d) *Osmyloberotha dispersa*, dorsal view (Paratype, ♂, CAM BA-0016). (e)
3592 *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov, dorsal view (♀, NIGP18068). (f) *Osmyloberotha simpla*
3593 Khramov, lateral view (♂, NIGP18067). (g) *Osmyloberotha* sp.1, dorsal view (NIGP18069). (h)
3594 *Osmyloberotha chenzuyini* Zhuo, Li & Liu, dorsal view (Holotype, ♂, BXAM-BA-NEU-38). (i)
3595 *Haploberotha persephone* Engel & Grimaldi, lateral view (BXAM BA-NEU-015). (j)

3596 *Haploberotha persephone* Engel & Grimaldi, ventral view (BXAM BA-NEU-015). (k)

3597 *Iceloberotha simulatrix* Engel & Grimaldi, ventral view (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-018). (l)

3598 *Jersiberotha tauberorum* Engel & Grimaldi (NIGP171720). Scale bars 1 mm.

3599

3600

3601 **Figure S9. Habitus photos of representatives in Rhachiberothidae (Paraberothinae).** (a)

3602 *Acanthoberotha cuspis* Nakamine et al., lateral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-020). (b)

3603 *Acanthoberotha cuspis* Nakamine et al., lateral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-019). (c)

3604 *Acanthoberotha cuspis* Nakamine et al., ventral view (♂, EMTG BU001992). (d) *Astioberotha*

3605 *falcipes* Nakamine et al., lateral view (♀, EMTG BU001993). (e) *Creagroparaberotha cuneata*

3606 Nakamine et al., dorsal view (♀, EMTG BU001995). (f) *Creagroparaberotha cuneata* Nakamine
 3607 et al., lateral view (EMTG BU002204). (g) *Creagroparaberotha* sp.2, lateral view (NIGP171722).
 3608 (h) *Creagroparaberotha* sp.1, lateral view (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-021). (i) *Micromantispa cristata*
 3609 Shi et al., lateral view (♀, EMTG BU002121). (j) *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al., dorsal view
 3610 (♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19006). (k) *Micromantispa galeata* Nakamine et al., ventral view (♀, BXAM
 3611 BA-NEU-023). (l) *Micromantispa* sp., lateral view (♀, EMTG BU002143). Scale bars 1 mm.

3612
 3613 **Figure S10. Habitus photos of representatives in Rhachiberothidae.** (a) *Paraberothoides*
 3614 *longispina* Li et al., Paraberothinae, dorsal view (Holotype, ♂, EMTG BU001998). (b-i)
 3615 *Dicranoberothesa liumohanae* Zhuo, Li & Liu. (b) Ventral view (Paratype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-
 3616 026). (c) Lateral view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171723). (d) Ventral view (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171724).

3617 (e) Lateral view (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171725). (f) Dorsal view (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171726). (g)
 3618 Dorsal view (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171727). (h) Ventral view (Paratype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-025). (i)
 3619 Lateral view (Paratype, ♀, CAU-BA-NH-20002). (j-m) Dipteromantispidae. (j)
 3620 *Kurtodipteromantispa* sp., lateral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-029). (k) *Kurtodipteromantispa* sp.,
 3621 lateral view (♀, NIGP003). (l) *Enigmadipteromantispa dilatata* Li et al., lateral view (Holotype, ♂,
 3622 CAU-BA-GYH-19007). (m) *Kurtodipteromantispa zhuodei*, Li & Liu, lateral view (♂, BXAM-
 3623 NEU031). Scale bars 1 mm.

3624

3625 **Figure S11. Habitus photos of representatives in Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae. (a-f)**
3626 Dipteromantispidae. (a) *Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* Li et al., ventral view (Holotype, ♂, CAU-
3627 BA-GYH-19008). (b) *Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* Li et al., dorsal view (Paratype, ♂, CAU-BA-
3628 GYH-19009). (c) *Kurtodipteromantispa univenula* Li et al., dorsal view (Holotype, ♂,
3629 NIGP173316). (d) *Mantisdiptera enigmatica* Grimaldi, dorsal view (Holotype, NJ-154). (e)
3630 *Halteriomantispa grimaldii* Liu, Lu & Zhang, lateral view (Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU001924). (f)
3631 *Paradipteromantispa polyneura* Li et al., lateral view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP173215). (g-i)
3632 Mantispidae. (g) *Mesomantispoides felixporcus* Li et al., ventral view (Holotype, ♀,
3633 NIGP171728). (h-k) Symphrasinae. (h) *Habrosymphra xiai* Shi et al., 2019, lateral view (♀,
3634 NIGP171729). (i) *Proplega evelynae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, dorsal view (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-
3635 NEU-032). (j) *Proplega evelynae*, dorsal view (Paratype, ♀, NIGP172730). (k)
3636 *Haplosymphrasites zouae* Lu et al., dorsal view (♀, NIGP171831). (l) *Haplacantha tenuis* Li et al.,
3637 lateral view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171732). Scale bars 1 mm.

3638

3639 **Figure S12. Habitus photos of representatives in Mantispidae, lateral view.** (a-g)

3640 Mesomantispinae. (a) *Archaeodrepanicus acutus* Jepson et al. (Holotype, CNU-NEU-LB2011004).

3641 (b) *Archaeodrepanicus* sp1. (a paratype of *Archaeodrepanicus nuddsi* Jepson et al., ♂, CNU-NEU-

3642 LB2011002). (c) *Archaeodrepanicus nuddsi* Jepson et al. (Paratype, CNU-NEU-LB2011003). (d),

3643 (g), *Archaeodrepanicus nuddsi* Jepson et al. (Holotype, CNU-NEU-LB2011001P/C). (e)

3644 *Clavifemora rotundata* Jepson et al. (Holotype, CNU-NEU-NN2011001). (f) *Karataumantispia*

3645 *carnaria* (Khramov), (Holotype, PIN 2239/1725). (h) *Sinomesomantispia microdentata* Jepson et

3646 al., Symphrasinae (Holotype, CNU-NEU-2011006P/C). (i-k) Mesomantispinae. (i) *Longipronotum*

3647 *benmaddoxi* (Jepson, Khramov & Ohl) (Holotype, PIN 2784 1056). (j) *Ovalofemora monstrosa*

3648 (Khramov) (Holotype, PIN 2066/1119). (k) *Ovalofemora abbottae* Jepson, Khramov & Ohl

3649 (Holotype, PIN 2239 1727). Scale bars in (a-b), (d-e), (g), (h), (j), 5 mm, in (c), (k), 2 mm, in (f),
 3650 (i), 1 mm.

3651
 3652 **Figure S13. Habitus photos of representatives in Mantispidae, lateral view.** (a) *Haplacantha*
 3653 *tenuis* Li et al., dorsal view (Paratype, ♂, NIGP171733). (b) *Doratomantispa arcimaculata* Li et
 3654 al., lateral view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP 177985). (c) *Doratomantispa zhuozhengmingi* Zhuo, Li &
 3655 Liu (Holotype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-002). (d) *Doratomantispa* sp.1, dorsal view (♂, NIGP18115).
 3656 (e) *Doratomantispa yumeiyingae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, ventral view (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-

3657 007). (f) *Doratomantispa* sp.2, ventral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-40). (g) *Doratomantispa* sp.3,
3658 lateral view (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-41). (h) *Doratomantispa ares* Li et al., dorsal view (Holotype,
3659 ♂, NIGP 173084). (i) *Paradoxomantispa jiaxiaoe* Lu et al., lateral view (Holotype, ♀, CAM BA-
3660 0015). (j) *Acanthomantispa* sp., ventral view (♀, NIGP171834). (k-l) *Acanthomantispa maculata*
3661 Lu et al.. (k) ventral view (EMTG BU002302). (l) lateral view (Paratype, ♀, EMTG BU002136).
3662 (m) *Acanthomantispa grandis* Lu et al. (Holotype, NIGP 173085). (n) *Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu
3663 et al., ventral view (NIGP171734). (o) *Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al., dorsal view (Holotype,
3664 ♂, CAU-BA-LX-19004). Scale bars in (a-e), (g), (i), 1 mm, in (f), (h), (j-o), 2 mm.

3665

3666 **Figure S14. Head and prothorax photos and drawings of representatives in Berothidae. (a-b)**

3667 Head and prothorax photos of *Osmyloberotha dispersa* Li et al. (a) Lateral view (Holotype, ♂,

3668 NIGP171721). (b) Dorsal view (Paratype, ♂, CAM BA-0016). (c-d) Head & prothorax photos of
3669 *Osmyloberotha magnimaculata* Li et al. (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19004). (c) Head and
3670 prothorax, dorsal view. (d) Head, frontal view. (e) Head photos of *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov,
3671 frontal view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP18068). (f-g) Head photos of *Nyrma kervillea* Navás, ♀. (f)
3672 Frontal view. (g) Ventral view. (h) Head photos of *Nosybus* sp., frontal view, ♂. (i) Head photos of
3673 *Berothera bannana* Yang & Liu, frontal view, ♀. (j-k), (o), Prothorax photos of *Nyrma kervillea*
3674 Navás, ♀. (j) Dorsal view. (k) Ventral view. (o), Lateral view. (l-n), (p), (s), Head and Prothorax of
3675 *Lomamyia flavicornis* (Walker), ♀. (l) Prothorax photo, ventral view. (m) Prothorax drawing,
3676 ventral view. (n) Head photo, ventral view. (s) Prothorax drawing, lateral view. (q), (u), (t), Head
3677 and prothorax photos of *Haploberotha persephone* Engel & Grimaldi. (q) Dorsal view (♀, BXAM
3678 BA-NEU-016). (u) Lateral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-015). (t) Frontal view (♀, BXAM BA-
3679 NEU-015). (r), (v), (w), Prothorax of *Iceloberotha simulatrix* Engel & Grimaldi, ventral view (♂,
3680 BXAM BA-NEU-018). (r-v) Photos. (w) Drawing. Abbreviations: bs, Basisternum; cg, Anterior
3681 cervical sclerite; em, Epimeron; es, Episternum; fs, furcasternum; lc, Posterior cervical sclerite; trt,
3682 trochantin; tu, tubercle. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

3683

3684 **Figure S15. Head and prothorax photos and drawings of representatives in Berothidae and**
 3685 **Rhachiberothidae (Paraberothinae).** (a-m) Berothidae. (a-b) Head and prothorax photos of
 3686 *Ansoberotha jiewenae* Yang, Shi & Ren. (a) Head photo, frontal view (♀, NIGP171715). (b) Head
 3687 and Prothorax photo, lateral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-014). (c-d) *Cornoberotha anomala* Yang
 3688 et al. (Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU001249). (c) Head photo, frontal view, arrow indicating the frontal
 3689 horn. (d) antenna. (e-f) Head and prothorax photos of *Cornoberotha aspoeckae* Yang et al.
 3690 (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171707). (e) Head and prothorax, ventral view. (f) antenna. (g) Head photo of

3691 *Cornoberotha monogona* Yang et al. (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171708), frontal view. (h-m) Head and
3692 prothorax of *Dolichoberotha bifurcata* Yang et al. (h-j) Photo (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171709). (h)
3693 Frontal view. (j) Dorsal view. (k) Photo, ventral view (Paratype, ♀, EMTG BU001991). (l-m)
3694 Lateral view (Paratype, ♂, EMTG BU002117). (l) Photo. (m) Drawing. (n-t) Rhachiberothidae. (n)
3695 Head photo of *Acanthoberotha cuspis* Nakamine et al., lateral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-019).
3696 (o-p) Head and prothorax photos of *Astioberotha falcipes* Nakamine et al., lateral view (♀, EMTG
3697 BU001993). (q), (t), Head photos of *Creagroparaberotha* sp.2, lateral view (NIGP171722). (q)
3698 antenna. (t) Lateral view. (r) Head and prothorax photo of *Creagroparaberotha cuneata* Nakamine
3699 et al., lateral view (♀, EMTG BU001995). (s) Head and prothorax photo of *Creagroparaberotha*
3700 sp.1, lateral view (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-021). Abbreviations: cg, Anterior cervical sclerite; es,
3701 Episternum; fs, furcasternum; lc, Posterior cervical sclerite. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

3702

3703 **Figure S16. Head and thorax photos and drawings of representatives in Berothidae and**

3704 **Rhachiberothidae. (a-k), Paraberothinae. (a) Head and prothorax photo of *Creagroparaberotha***

3705 **sp.1, lateral view (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-022). (b) Head photo of *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al.,**

3706 **frontal view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-025). (c-f) Head and prothorax of *Micromantispa cristata* Shi**

3707 **et al. (♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19006). (c) Photo, dorsal view. (d-e) Photo, ventral view. (f) Drawing,**

3708 **ventral view. (g-h) Head and prothorax of *Micromantispa* sp., lateral view (♀, EMTG BU002143).**

3709 (g) Photo. (h) Drawing. (i) Head photo of *Micromantispa* sp., lateral view (♀, EMTG
3710 BU001224).(j-k) Head and prothorax of *Paraberothoides longispina*, lateral view (Holotype, ♂,
3711 EMTG BU001998). (j) Photo. (k) Drawing. (l-s) *Dicranoberotha*. (l-n), (q-s), Head and thorax
3712 photos of *Dicranoberotha liumohanae*. (l) Head, frontal view (Paratype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-
3713 026). (m-n) Head, lateral view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171723). (q) (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171727), (r-s)
3714 (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171725), arrows showing the fluffy membranous sac anterior to the mesothorax.
3715 (o-p) Head and prothorax photos of *Dicranoberotha zhangzhiqiae*, (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-
3716 NEU-027). (o) Dorsal view. (p) Antenna. Abbreviations: bs, Basisternum; cg, Anterior cervical
3717 sclerite; em, Epimeron; es, Episternum; fs, furcasternum; lc, Posterior cervical sclerite; trt,
3718 trochantin; tu, tubercle. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

3719

3720 **Figure S17. Head and prothorax photos and drawings of representatives in**

3721 **Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae. (a) Head photo of *Kurtodipteromantispa* sp., dorsal view**

3722 **(♀, BXAM BA-NEU-029). (b-c) Head and prothorax of *Halteriomantispa grimaldii* Liu, Lu &**

3723 **Zhang, lateral view (Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU001924). (b) Photo. (c) Drawing. (d) Head and**

3724 prothorax photo of *Kurtodipteromantispa* sp., lateral view (♀, NIGP003). (e) Head photo of
3725 *Enigmadipteromantispa dilatata* Li et al., lateral view (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-GYH-19007). (f),
3726 (k), Head and prothorax of *Kurtodipteromantispa xiai* Li et al., lateral view (Holotype, ♂, LPAM
3727 BA-NEU-001). (f), Photo. (k), Drawing. (g) Head photo of *Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* Li et al.,
3728 dorsal view (Paratype, ♂, CAU-BA-GYH-19009). (h) Head photo of *Paradipteromantispa*
3729 *polyneura* Li et al., lateral view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP173215). (i) Head and thorax photo of
3730 *Kurtodipteromantispa univenula* Li et al. dorsal view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP173316). (j) Head photo
3731 of *Kurtodipteromantispa zhuodei*, Li & Liu, frontal view (Paratype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-002). (l-
3732 q) Mantispidae. (l) Head and prothorax photo of *Archaeodrepanicus acutu* Jepson et al., lateral
3733 view (Holotype, CNU-NEU-LB2011004). (m-q) Head and prothorax photo of *Mesomantispoides*
3734 *felixoporcus* Li et al., (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171728). (m) Lateral view. (n-q) Ventral view. (q) Head
3735 and prothorax photo of *Habrosymphysis xiai* Shi et al., 2019, lateral view (♀, NIGP171729).
3736 Abbreviations: cg, Anterior cervical sclerite; em, Epimeron; es, Episternum; fs, furcasternum; lc,
3737 Posterior cervical sclerite; pfs, postfurcasternum; trt, trochantin. Scale bars in (a-k), (m-q), 0.2 mm,
3738 1 in 1.0 mm.

3739

3740 **Figure S18. Head and prothorax photos and drawings of representatives in Mantispidae**

3741 **(Symphrasinae).** (a) Head and prothorax photo of *Parvosymphrasites aploneura* Li et al., lateral

3742 view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171730). (b-d) Head and prothorax photos of *Proplega evelynae* Zhuo,

3743 Li & Liu (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-032). (b) Prothorax, lateral view. (c) Head, ventral view.
3744 (d) Head ventral view. (e-f), Prothorax of *Parasymphrasites electrinus* Lu et al., lateral view
3745 (Holotype, EMTG BU002162). (e) Photo. (f) Drawing. (g) Head and prothorax of *Proplega*
3746 *evelynae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, dorsal view (Paratype, ♀, NIGP172730). (h-k) Prothorax of *Trichoscelia*
3747 sp.. (h-i) Lateral view. (J-K) Ventral view. (h), (j) Photos. (i), (k) Drawings. (l-o) Prothorax of
3748 *Plega* spp. (l-m) Lateral view. (n-o) Ventral view. (l), (n-o), Photo. (m) Drawing. Abbreviations: bs,
3749 Basisternum; cg, Anterior cervical sclerite; em, Epimeron; es, Episternum; fs, furcasternum; lc,
3750 Posterior cervical sclerite; pfs, postfurcasternum; trt, trochantin. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

3751

3752

Figure S19. Head and prothorax photos and drawings of representatives in Mantispidae. (A-

3753

I) *Haplacantha* Li et al.. (a-e) Head and prothorax of *Haplacantha robusta* Li et al. (Holotype, ♂,

3754 NIGP171731). (a-d) Photos. (a), (d), Head and Prothorax, lateral view. (b) Prothorax, lateral view.
3755 (c) Head, lateral view. (e) Drawing, lateral view. (f-h) Head and prothorax of *Haplacantha tenuis*
3756 Li et al. (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171732). (f) Head and prothorax, lateral view. (g) Head, dorsal view.
3757 (h) Prothorax, lateral view. (i) Prothorax of *Haplacantha tenuis*, dorsal view (Paratype, ♂,
3758 NIGP171733). (j-p) Doratomantispinae. (j-l) *Doratomantispa yumeiyingae* Zhuo, Li & Liu
3759 (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-007). (j) Head and prothorax, lateral view. (k) Apical expanded
3760 area of prothorax, ventral view. (l) Head, frontal view. (m) Head and prothorax photo of
3761 *Doratomantispa zhangzhiqiae* Zhuo, Li & Liu, dorsal view (Holotype, ♂, BXAM BA-NEU-006).
3762 (n) Head photo of *Doratomantispa zhangwenjuni* Zhuo, Li & Liu, frontal view (Holotype, ♂,
3763 BXAM BA-NEU-005). (o-p) Head and prothorax of *Acanthomantispa maculata*, lateral view
3764 (Paratype, ♀, EMTG BU002136). (o) Photo. (q) Drawing. Abbreviations: bs, Basisternum; cg,
3765 Anterior cervical sclerite; em, Epimeron; es, Episternum; fs, furcasternum; lc, Posterior cervical
3766 sclerite; pfs, postfurcasternum; trt, trochantin, tu, tubercle. Scale bars in (j), (m), (o-p), 1 mm, in
3767 (a-i), (k-l), (n), 0.2 mm.
3768

3769

3770 **Figure S20. Head and prothorax photos and drawings of representatives in Mantispidae. (a-c)**

3771 Doratomantispinae. (a) Head photo of *Acanthomantispa maculata*, dorsal view (Paratype, ♀,

3772 EMTG BU002136). (b) Head and prothorax photo of *Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al., dorsal

3773 view (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-LX-19004). (c) Head photo of *Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al.,

3774 ventral view (NIGP171734). (d-m) DCM clade. (d-e) *Allomantispa coniprocessa* Li et al.
3775 (Drepanicininae), (d) Head, frontal view. (e) Apical expanded area of prothorax, ventral view. (f-g)
3776 *Calomantispa venusta* Lambkin (Calomantispinae), (f) Head, frontal view. (g) Apical expanded
3777 area of prothorax, ventral view. (h-m) *Campanacella javanica* (Westwood). (h) Head, frontal view.
3778 (i-j), (l) Apical expanded area of prothorax, (i-j) A photo and a drawing, ventral view. (k) Photo,
3779 lateral view. (m) Drawing of prothorax, lateral view. bs, Basisternum; cg, Anterior cervical sclerite;
3780 em, Epimeron; es, Episternum; fs, furcasternum; lc, Posterior cervical sclerite; pfs,
3781 postfurcasternum; trt, trochantin, tu, tubercle. Scale bars 0.5 mm.
3782

3783

3784 **Figure S21. Leg photos of representatives in Berothidae and Rhachiberothidae**

3785 **(Paraberothinae).** (a-k) Berothidae. (a-c) Mid and hind tarsi of *Osmyloberotha dispersa*,

3786 ventral view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171721). (c) fore and mid tarsi of *Osmyloberotha magnimaculata*,

3787 ventral view (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19004). (d) Foreleg of *Nyrma kervillea* Navás, lateral

3788 view ♀. (e) Foreleg of *Lomamyia flavicornis* (Walker), ventral view ♀. (f) Hind tarsi of

3789 *Iceloberothes simulatrix* Engel & Grimaldi, ventral view (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-018). (g) Hind tarsi
3790 of *Jersiberothes tauberorum* Engel & Grimaldi, lateral view (♀, NIGP171720). (h) Mid tarsus of
3791 *Cornoberothes aspoeckae* Yang et al., ventral view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171707). (i-k) Hind tarsi of
3792 *Dolichoberothes bifurcata* Yang et al. (i) Ventral view (Paratype, ♀, EMTG BU001991). (j) Ventral
3793 view (Paratype, ♂, EMTG BU002117). (k) Lateral view (Paratype, ♂, EMTG BU002117). (l-w)
3794 Rhachiberothidae. (l-q) Leg of *Acanthoberothes cuspis* Nakamine et al. (l-p) Raptorial foreleg. (l-n)
3795 ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-020. (l) Holistic view. (m) Profemur. n, protibia. (o) holistic view (♀, BXAM
3796 BA-NEU-019). (p) Holistic view (♂, EMTG BU001992). (q) Hind tarsus, ventral view (♂, EMTG
3797 BU001992). (R-T) Raptorial foreleg of *Astioberothes falcipes* Nakamine et al. (♀, EMTG
3798 BU001993). (r) Holistic view. (s) Profemur. (t) Protibia and protarsus. (u-w) Legs of
3799 *Creagroparaberothes cuneata* Nakamine et al. (♀, EMTG BU001995). (u-v) Raptorial foreleg. (u)
3800 Holistic view. (v) Protibia. (w) Mid tarsus, ventral view. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

3801

3802 **Figure S22. Leg photos of representatives in Rhachiberothidae (Paraberothinae).** (a-c)

3803 Raptorial foreleg of *Creagroparaberotha cuneata* Nakamine et al. (EMTG BU002204). (a)

3804 Profemur. (b) Holistic view. (c) Protibia and protarsus. (d-f) Raptorial foreleg of

3805 *Creagroparaberotha* sp.2 (NIGP171722). (d) Profemur. (e) Protibia and protarsus. (f) Protarsus.

3806 (g-j) Legs of *Creagroparaberotha* sp.1 (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-021). (g-i) Raptorial foreleg. (g)
3807 Profemur. (h) Protibia and protarsus. (i) Holistic view. (j) Mid tarsi, ventral view. (k) Raptorial
3808 foreleg of *Creagroparaberotha* sp.1 (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-022). (l) Raptorial foreleg of
3809 *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al. (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-025). (m) Raptorial foreleg of
3810 *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al. (♀, EMTG BU002121). (N-P) Raptorial foreleg of
3811 *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al. (♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19006). (n) Profemur. (o) Protibia. (p)
3812 Protarsus. (q-r) Raptorial foreleg of *Micromantispa galeata* Nakamine et al. (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-
3813 023). (q) Profemur. (r) Protibia. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

3814

3815

3816 **Figure S23. Leg photos of representatives in Rhachiberothidae and Dipteromantispidae. (A-**

3817 **N) Rhachiberothidae. (a-b) Raptorial foreleg of *Micromantispa* sp. (♀, EMTG BU002143). (a)**

3818 **Profemur. (b) Protibia. (c) Raptorial foreleg of *Paraberothoides longispina*, Paraberothinae**

3819 **(Holotype, ♂, EMTG BU001998). (d-k) Legs of *Dicranoberothesia liumohanae*. (d) Raptorial**

3820 **foreleg (Paratype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-026). (e-f) Raptorial foreleg (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171723).**

3821 (e) Profemur. (f) Protibia. (g) Hind tarsus, ventral view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171723). (H-J)
3822 Raptorial foreleg (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171725). (h) Holistic view. (f) Details of profemur and
3823 protibia. (j) Protarsus. (k) Mid tarsus, ventral view (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171725). (l-m)
3824 *Dicranoberotha zhangzhiqiae* (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-027). (l) Raptorial foreleg. (m) Mid
3825 tarsus, ventral view. (n) Raptorial foreleg of *Paradoxoberotha chimaera* Nakamine et al.
3826 (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-NH-20001). (o-s) Dipteromantispidae. (o-p) Raptorial foreleg of
3827 *Kurtodipteromantispa* sp. (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-029). (o) Holistic view. (p) Details of protibia. (q-
3828 s) Raptorial foreleg of *Halteriomantispa grimaldii* Liu, Lu & Zhang (Holotype, ♀, EMTG
3829 BU001924). (q-r) Holistic view. (s) Details of protibia. Scale bars in (h), 1 mm, in (a-g), (i-s), 0.2
3830 mm.

3831

3832 **Figure S24. Leg photos of representatives in Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae**

3833 **(Symphrasinae).** (a-n) Dipteromantispidae. (a-b) Raptorial foreleg of *Enigmadipteromantropa*

3834 *dilatata*, (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-GYH-19007). (a) Holistic view. (b) Details of protibia. (c-d)

3835 Raptorial foreleg of *Kurtodipteromantispa univenula* (Holotype, ♂, NIGP173316). (c) Holistic
3836 view. (d) Protibia. (e-g) Raptorial foreleg of *Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* (Holotype, ♂, CAU-
3837 BA-GYH-19008). (e) Holistic view. (f) Profemur. (g) Protibia. (h) Raptorial foreleg of
3838 *Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* (Paratype, ♂, CAU-BA-GYH-19009). (i-j) Raptorial foreleg of
3839 *Paradipteromantispa polyneura* Li et al. (Holotype, ♀, NIGP173215). Holistic view. (j) Protibia
3840 and protarsus. (k-l) Mid tarsus of *Kurtodipteromantispa* sp., ventral view (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-
3841 029). (m) Hind tarsus of *Enigmadipteromantispa dilatata*, dorsal view (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-
3842 GYH-19007). (n) Mid tarsus of *Paradipteromantispa polyneura* Li et al., ventral view (Holotype,
3843 ♀, NIGP173215). (o-s) Symphrasinae. (o-q) Raptorial foreleg of *Habrosymphra xiai* Shi et al.
3844 (♂, CAU-BA-WN-19002). (o) Profemur, lateral view. (p) Profemur, ventral view. (q) Protibia. (r-s)
3845 Raptorial foreleg of *Habrosymphra xiai* Shi et al. (♀, NIGP171729). (r) Holistic view. (s)
3846 Details of profemur and protibia. Scale bars 0.2 mm.
3847

3848

3849 **Figure S25. Leg photos of representatives in Mantispidae.** (a-r) Symphrasinae. (a-b) Raptorial
 3850 foreleg of *Proplega evelynae* (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-032) (a) Posterolateral view. (b)
 3851 Anterolateral view. (c-e) Raptorial foreleg of *Symphrasinae* sp. (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-033). (c)
 3852 Holistic view. (d) Protarsus. (e) Details of profemur and protibia. (f-g) Mid tarsi of

3853 *Parasymphrasites electrinus* Lu et al., ventral view (Holotype, ♀, EMTG BU002162). (h-i)

3854 Raptorial foreleg of *Plega dactylota* Rehn. (h) Lateral view. (i) Ventral view. (j) Details of protibia.

3855 (k-l) Protarsus. (m-n) Profemur of *Trichoscelia* sp.. (m) Lateral view. (n) Ventral view. (o) Hind

3856 tarsus of *Habrosymphrasis xiai* Shi et al. (♀, NIGP171729), lateral view. (p) Hind tarsus of

3857 *Parvoasymphrasites aploneurus*, ventral view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171730). (q) Hind tarsi of

3858 *Proplega evelynae*, ventral view (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-032). (r) Hind tarsus of *Plega*

3859 *dactylota* Rehn, ventral view. (s) Hind tarsus of *Trichoscelia* sp., ventral view. (t-u) Mid and hind

3860 tarsus of *Mesomantisoides felixporcus*, ventral view (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171728). (t) Mid tarsus.

3861 (u) Hind tarsus. (v-w) Raptorial foreleg of *Haplacantha tenuis*, (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171732). (v)

3862 Holistic view. (w) Details of profemur, protibia and protarsus. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

3863

3864

3865 **Figure S26. Leg photos of representatives in Mantispidae.** (a-c) Raptorial foreleg of

3866 *Haplacantha tenuis*, (Paratype, ♂, NIGP171733). (a) Holistic view. (b-c) Details of protasus. (d)

3867 Hind tarsi of *Haplacantha robusta*, ventral view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171731). (e) Mid tarsi of

3868 *Haplacantha robusta*, ventral view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171731). (f) Hind tarsi of *Haplacantha*

3869 *tenuis*, ventral view, (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171732). (g-s) Doratomantispinae. (g-i) Raptorial foreleg

3870 of *Paradoxomantispa jiaxiaoe* Lu et al. (Holotype, ♀, CAM BA-0015). (g) Holistic view. (h)

3871 Protarsus. (i) Protibia. (j-l) Raptorial foreleg of *Doratomantispa pubescens* Lu et al. (Holotype,
3872 EMTG BU001759). (j) Holistic view. (k) Protibia. (l) Protarsus. (m) Major process and protarsus
3873 and distal portion of protibia of *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al. (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-034).
3874 (n-o) Raptorial foreleg of *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al. (EMTG BU002302). (n) Holistic
3875 view. (o) Protibia and protarsus. (p) Hind tarsus of *Doratomantispa* sp.1, ventral view (♂,
3876 NIGP18115). (q) Hind tarsus of *Paradoxomantispa jiaxiaoe* Lu et al., ventral view (Holotype, ♀,
3877 CAM BA-0015). (r) Hind tarsus of *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al., ventral view (♂, BXAM
3878 BA-NEU-034). (s) Hind tarsus of *Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al., ventral view (NIGP171734).
3879 Scale bars in (a-m), (p-q), 0.2 mm, in (n), (o), (r-s), 1 mm.

3880

3881 **Figure S27. Raptorial foreleg photos of representatives in Mantispidae. (a-e), (g-l)**

3882 Mesomantispinae. (a) *Archaeodrepanicus acutu* Jepson et al. (Holotype, CNU-NEU-LB2011004).

3883 (b) *Archaeodrepanicus nudsi* Jepson et al. (Holotype, CNU-NEU-LB2011001P/C).

3884 *Archaeodrepanicus nudsi* Jepson et al. (Paratype, CNU-NEU-LB2011003).

3885 *Archaeodrepanicus* sp1. (a paratype of *Archaeodrepanicus nudsi* Jepson et al., ♂, CNU-NEU-

3886 LB2011002). (e) *Clavifemora rotundata* Jepson et al. (Holotype, CNU-NEU-NN2011001). (g)

3887 *Karataumantispa carnaria* (Khramov), (Holotype, PIN 2239/1725). (h) *Longipronotum*
 3888 *benmaddoxi* (Jepson, Khramov & Ohl) (Holotype, PIN 2784 1056). (i) *Ovalofemora abbottae*
 3889 Jepson, Khramov & Ohl (Holotype, PIN 2239 1727). (j-l) *Ovalofemora monstrosa* (Khramov)
 3890 (Holotype, PIN 2066/1119). (j) Holistic view. (k-l) Details of protibia and protarsus. (f)
 3891 *Sinomesomantispa microdentata* Jepson et al., Symphrasinae (Holotype, CNU-NEU-2011006P/C).
 3892 Scale bars 1 mm.
 3893

3894

3895 **Figure S28. Raptorial foreleg photos of representatives in Mantispidae (DCM clade). (A-F)**

3896 **Legs of *Allomantispa coniprocessa* Li et al.** (a-e) Raptorial foreleg. (a) Procoxa. (b)

3897 Posterolateral view. (c) Anterolateral view. (d) Details of protibia. (e) Protarsus, ventral view. (f)

3898 Hind tarsus, ventral view. (g-l) Legs of *Ditaxis biseriata* (Westwood). (g-k) Raptorial foreleg. (g)

3899 Procoxa. (h) Posterolateral view. (i) Anterolateral view. (j) Details of protibia. (k) Protarsus,

3900 ventral view. (l) Hind tarsus, ventral view. (g-l) Legs of *Drepanicus chrysopinus* Brauer. (m-r)

3901 Raptorial foreleg. (m) Procoxa. (n) Posterolateral view. (o) Anterolateral view. (p) Details of

3902 protibia. (q) Protarsus, ventral view. (r) Hind tarsus, ventral view. Scale bars in (a-c), (g-i), (m-o),

3903 1 mm, in (d-f), (j-l), (p-r), 0.2 mm.

3905 **Figure S29. Raptorial foreleg photos of representatives in Mantispidae (DCM clade).** (a-f)
3906 Legs of *Gerstaeckerella chilensis* (Hagen). (a-e) Raptorial foreleg. (a) Procoxa. (b) Posterolateral
3907 view. (c) Anterolateral view. (d) Details of protibia. (e) Protarsus, ventral view. (f) Hind tarsus,
3908 ventral view. (g-l) Legs of *Theristria delicatula* (Westwood). (g-k) Raptorial foreleg. (g) Procoxa.
3909 (h) Posterolateral view. (i) Anterolateral view. (j) Details of protibia. (k) Protarsus, ventral view. (l)
3910 Hind tarsus, ventral view. (M-R) Legs of *Calomantispa venusta* Lambkin. (m-q), Raptorial foreleg.
3911 (m) Procoxa. (n) Posterolateral view. (o) Anterolateral view. (p) Details of protibia. (q) Protarsus,
3912 ventral view. (r) Hind tarsus, ventral view. (s-x) Legs of *Euclimacia badia* Okamoto. (s-w)
3913 Raptorial foreleg. (s) Procoxa. (t) Posterolateral view. (u) Anterolateral view. (v) Details of
3914 protibia. (w) Protarsus, ventral view. (x) Hind tarsus, ventral view. Scale bars in (a-c), (g-i), (m-o),
3915 (s-u), 1 mm, in (d-f), (j-l), (p-r), (v-x), 0.2 mm.

3916

3917 **Figure S30. Wing drawings of representatives in Berothidae.** (a) Forewing of *Sinosmylites*
 3918 *rasnitsyni* Makarkin et al., adapted from Makarkin et al. (2011): Figure 3B. (b) Hind wing of
 3919 *Sinosmylites* sp., adapted from Makarkin et al. (2011): Figure 5B. (c) Forewing of *Epimesoberotha*
 3920 *parva* Jepson et al., adapted from Jepson et al. (2012): Figure 17A. (d) Left fore- and hind wings
 3921 of *Osmyloberotha dispersa*, (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171721). (e) Left fore- and hind wing of
 3922 *Osmyloberotha dispersa*, (Paratype, ♂, CAM BA-0016). (f-g) Fore- and hind wings of
 3923 *Osmyloberotha magnimaculata*, (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19004). (f) Right. (g) Left. (h) Left

- 3924 fore- and hind wings of *Osmyloberotha chenzuyini*, (Holotype, ♂, BXAM-BA-NEU-38). (i-j)
- 3925 Fore- and hind wings of *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-36). (i) Right. (j)
- 3926 Left. (k-l) Fore- and hind wings of *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov, (♀, NIGP18068). (k) Right.
- 3927 (l) Left. (m) Fore- and hind wings of *Xiaoberotha bipunctata* Shi et al., adapted from Shi et al.
- 3928 (2019): Figure 5B, D. Scale bars 1 mm.

3930

3931 **Figure S31. Wing drawings of representatives in Berothidae.** (a) Fore- and hind wings of
 3932 *Nyrma kervillea* Navás, adapted from Aspöck & Aspöck (1979): Figure 7. (b) Fore- and hind
 3933 wings of *Ormiscocerus nitidipennis* Blanchard in Gay, adapted from Penny & Winterton (2007):
 3934 Figure 4. (c) Fore- and hindwings of *Oloberotha sinica* Ren & Guo, adapted from Ren & Guo

3935 (1996): Figure 6b. (d) Fore- and hindwings of *Elektroberotha groehni* Makarkin & Ohl, adapted
 3936 from Makarkin & Ohl (2015): Figure 3. (e) Fore- and hind wings of *Protobiella zelandica* Tillyard,
 3937 adapted from Wise, 1992: Figure 2. (f) Fore- and hind wings of *Spermophorella* sp.. (g) Fore- and
 3938 hind wings of *Lomamyia flavicornis* (Walker). (h) Fore- and hind wings of *Isoscelipteron*
 3939 *acuticaudatum* Li et al.. Scale bars 1 mm.

3941 **Figure S32. Wing drawings of representatives in Berothidae.** (a) Fore- and hind wing of
3942 *Manselliberothera neuropterologorum* Aspöck & Aspöck, adapted from Aspöck & Aspöck (1998):
3943 Figure 9. (b) Fore- and hind wing of *Speleoberothera paloma* Machado et al., adapted from
3944 Machado et al. (2022): Figure 4B. (c) Fore- and hind wing of *Cantabroberothera soplaensis* Pérez-
3945 de la Fuente & Peñalver, adapted from Pérez-de la Fuente & Peñalver (2021): Figure 3D-E. (d)
3946 Fore- and hind wing of *Maculaberothera nervosa* Yuan, Ren & Wang, adapted from Yuan, Ren &
3947 Wang, 2016: Figure 3. (e) Fore- and hind wing of *Jersiberothera tauberorum* Engel & Grimaldi
3948 (NIGP171720). (f) Fore- and hind wing of *Ansoberothera jiewenae* Yang et al. (♀, BXAM BA-
3949 NEU-014). (g) Forewing of *Krokhathone parva* Khramov, adapted from Khramov (2015): Figure
3950 2a. Scale bars 1 mm.

3951

3952 **Figure S33. Wing drawings of representatives in *Archarhachiberotha longitarsa* Wang, Ren**
 3953 **& Wang, and Rhachiberothidae.** (a) Fore- and hind wings of *Archarhachiberotha longitarsa*
 3954 Wang, Ren & Wang. (b) Left fore- and hind wings of *Creagroparaberotha cuneata* Nakamine et al.
 3955 (♀, EMTG BU001995). (c) Left fore- and hind wings of *Creagroparaberotha* sp.2 (NIGP171722).
 3956 (d) Left fore- and hind wings and right hind wings of *Creagroparaberotha* sp.1 (♂, BXAM BA-
 3957 NEU-021). (e) Right fore- and hind wings and left hind wing of *Astioberotha falcipes* Nakamine
 3958 et al. (♀, EMTG BU001993). (f) Right fore- and hind wings of *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al.
 3959 (♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19006). (g) Right fore- and hind wings of *Micromantispa galeata* Nakamine
 3960 et al., 2020 (♀, BXAM BA-NEU-023). (h) Left fore- and hind wings and right hind wing of
 3961 *Micromantispa* sp. (♀, EMTG BU002143). Scale bars 1 mm.

3962

3963 **Figure S34. Wing drawings of representatives in Rhachiberothidae.** (a) Left fore- and hind
3964 wings of *Paraberotheroides longispina*, Paraberotherinae (Holotype, ♂, EMTG BU001998). (b-g)
3965 *Dicranoberotha liumohanae*. (b-c) Holotype, ♀, NIGP171723). (b) Right fore- and hind wings. (c)
3966 Left fore- and hind wings. (d) f, Paratype, ♀, NIGP171726. (d) Left fore- and hind wings. (f)
3967 Right fore- and hind wings. (e) Right fore- and hind wings (Paratype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-026).
3968 (g) Left fore- and hind wings (Paratype, ♀, NIGP171725). (h) Right fore- and left hind wings of
3969 *Dicranoberotha zhangzhiqiae* (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-027). (i) *Mucroberotha vesicaria*
3970 Tjeder, Rhachiberotherinae, adapted from Ardila-Camacho et al., 2021: Figure 30a. Scale bars 1 mm.

3971

3972 **Figure S35. Forewing drawings of representatives in Dipteromantispidae.** (a)

3973 *Paradipteromantispa polyneura* Li et al. (Holotype, ♀, NIGP173215), adapted from Li et al.

3974 (2020): Figure 2A. (b) *Halteriomantispa grimaldii* Liu, Lu & Zhang (Holotype, ♀, EMTG

3975 BU001924), adapted from Liu et al., 2016: Figure 5B. (c) *Mantispidipterella longissima* Liu et al.,

3976 adapted from Liu et al. (2017): Figure 5B. (d) Right forewing of *Kurtodipteromantispa univenula*

3977 (Holotype, ♂, NIGP173316). (e-f) *Enigmadipteromantispa dilatata* (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-

3978 GYH-19007). (e) Right forewing. (f) Left forewing. (g-j) *Kurtodipteromantispa relicta*. (g) Left

3979 forewing (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-GYH-19008). (h) Right forewing (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-

3980 GYH-19008). (i) Right forewing (Paratype, ♂, CAU-BA-GYH-19009). (j) Left forewing
 3981 (Paratype, ♂, CAU-BA-GYH-19009). Scale bars 1 mm.

3982

3983 **Figure S36. Wing drawings of representatives in Mantispidae.** (a) Forewing of *Berotherone*
 3984 *protea* (Panfilov in Dolin et al.), adapted from Khramov2015: Figure 1a. (b) Forewing of
 3985 *Mesithone maculata* Panfilov in Dolin et al., adapted from Panfilov in Dolin et al. (1980): Figure
 3986 86. (c) Forewing of *Mesithone magna* Panfilov in Dolin et al., adapted from Panfilov in Dolin et al.
 3987 (1980): Figure 87. (d) Fore- and hind wings of *Khasurtoberotha bellissima* Kopylov et al., adapted
 3988 from Kopylov et al., (2020): Figure 38. (e) Forewing of *Archaeodrepanicus nuddsi* Jepson et al.,
 3989 Mesomantispinae (Holotype, CNU-NEU-LB2011001P/C), adapted from Jepson et al. (2013):

3990 Figure 1C. (f) Forewing of *Archaeodrepanicus acutu* Jepson et al., Mesomantispinae (Holotype,
3991 CNU-NEU-LB2011004), adapted from Jepson et al. (2013): Figure 4B. (g-h) *Mesomantispoides*
3992 *felixoporcus*, (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171728). (g) Right forewing. (h) Left forewing. (i-k)
3993 Symphrasinae. (i) Forewing of *Archaeosymphrasis pennyi* Shi et al., adapted from Shi et al.
3994 (2019): Figure 1D, E. (j-k) *Proplega evelynae*, (Holotype, ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-032). (j) Right
3995 fore- and hind wings. (k) Left forewing. Scale bars 1 mm.

3996

3997 **Figure S37 Wing drawings of representatives in Mantispidae (Symphrasinae).** (a-b) *Proplega*

3998 *evelynae*, (Paratype, ♀, NIGP172730). (a) Left fore- and hind wings. (b) Right fore- and hind

3999 wings. (c-d) *Parvosymphrasites aploneura*, (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171730). (c) Left fore- and hind

4000 wings. (d) Right fore- and hind wings. (e) Left fore- and hind wings of *Habrosymphrasis xiai* Shi

4001 et al., 2019 (♀, NIGP171729). (f) Left fore- and hind wings of *Haplosymphrasites zouae* Lu et al.

4002 (♀, NIGP171831). Scale bars 1 mm.

4003

4004 **Figure S38. Wing drawings of representatives in Mantispidae.** (a-b) *Haplacantha robusta*

4005 (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171731). (a) Right forewing. (b) Left fore- and hind wings. (c-d) *Haplacantha*

4006 *tenuis*, (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171732). (c) Left fore- and hind wings. (d) Right fore- and hind wings.

4007 (e-f) *Haplacantha tenuis*, (Paratype, ♂, NIGP171733). (e) Right fore- and hind wings. (f) Left

4008 fore- and hind wings. Scale bars 1 mm.

4009

4010 **Figure S39. Wing drawings of representatives in Mantispidae (Doratomantispinae).** (a) Fore-
 4011 and hind wings of *Paradoxomantispa mahaiyingae* Zhuo, Li & Liu: (Holotype, ♀, CAM BA-
 4012 0015), adapted from Li et al., 2022: Figure 24g-h. (b) Fore- and hind wings of *Doratomantispa*
 4013 *arcimaculata* Li et al. (Holotype, ♂, NIGP 177985), adapted from Li et al. (2022): Figure 3a, c. (c)
 4014 Fore- and hind wings of *Doratomantispa zhangzhiqiae* Zhuo, Li & Liu (Holotype, ♂, BXAM BA-
 4015 NEU-006), adapted from Li et a. (2022): Figure 18a, c. (d-e) *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al.
 4016 (♂, BXAM BA-NEU-034). (d) Left fore- and hind wings. (e) Right fore- and hind wings. (f)

4017 *Dicranomantispa zhouae* Lu et al. (Holotype, ♂, CAU-BA-ZM-19003), adapted from Lu et al.

4018 (2022): Figure S10F, H. Scale bars 1 mm.

4019

4020 **Figure S40. Fore- and hind wing drawings of representatives in Mantispidae (DCM calde).** (a)

4021 Fore- and hind wings of *Drepanicus chrysopinus* Brauer, adapted from Ardila-Camacho et al.

4022 (2021): Figure 32f. (b) Fore- and hind wings of *Gerstaeckerella irrorata* (Erichson), adapted from

4023 Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): Figure 30c. (c) Fore- and hind wings of *Allomantispa coniprocessa*

4024 Li et al., adapted from Li et al. (2020): Figure 2B. (d) Fore- and hind wings of *Calomantispa*

4025 *spectabilis* Banks, adapted from Lambkin (1986b): Figure 404. (e) Fore- and hind wings of

4026 *Nolima victor* Navás, adapted from Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): Figure 30d. (f) Fore- and hind

4027 wings of *Eumantispa harmandi* Okamoto. (g) Fore- and hind wings of *Necyla flavacoxa* (Yang).

4028 Scale bars 1 mm.

4029

4030

4031 **Figure S41. Some details of wings.** (a-f) *Osmyloberotha*, showing the distal portion that ScP is
4032 fused with RA, arrows indicating the reduced trajectory of ScP which is finally fused with RA.. (a)
4033 Forewing of *Osmyloberotha dispersa* (Paratype, ♂, CAM BA-0016). (b) Hind wing of
4034 *Osmyloberotha magnimaculata* (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-GYH-19004). (c) Forewing of
4035 *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov (♀, NIGP18068). (d-e) Fore- and hind wings of *Osmyloberotha*
4036 sp.1 (NIGP18069). (g-i) *Osmyloberotha*, arrows indicating the sigmoid 1rp-m in the hind wing. (g)
4037 *Osmyloberotha* sp.1 (NIGP18069). (h) *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov, lateral view (♂,
4038 NIGP18067). (f) *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov (♀, NIGP18068). (j-k) Forewing pterostigmatic
4039 area of *Lomamyia flavicornis* (Walker), arrows showing the trachea in ScP running into RA, which
4040 indicates the two vein are fused together distally. (l-o) PD clade and *Mesomantispoides*
4041 *felixoporcus*, arrows indicating the sigmoid 1rp-m in the hind wing. (l) *Paradoxoberotha chimaera*
4042 Nakamine et al. (Holotype, ♀, CAU-BA-NH-20001). (m) *Dicranoberotha liumohanae*. (Paratype,
4043 ♀, BXAM BA-NEU-026). (n) *Dicranoberotha liumohanae* (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171723). (o)
4044 *Mesomantispoides felixoporcus* (Holotype, ♀, NIGP171728). Scale bars 0.2 mm.

4045

4046 **Figure S42. Male terminalia photos and drawings of Berothidae.** (a-d) *Osmyloberotha*

4047 *dispersa*, (a) Photo, lateral view (Holotype, ♂, NIGP171721). (b-d) Lateral view (CAM BA-0016).

4048 (b-c) Photos. (d) Drawing. (e) *Osmyloberotha chenzuyini*, photo, lateral view (Holotype, BXAM-

4049 BA-NEU-38). (f) *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khramov, photo, lateral view (NIGP18067). (g-h) *Nyrma*
4050 *kervillea* Navás, photo. (g) Lateral view. (h) Caudal view. (I-K) *Nosybus* sp., photo. (i) Lateral
4051 view, (j) Caudal view, k, Ventral view. (l-m) *Lomamyia flavicornis* (Walker), photo. (l) Lateral
4052 view. (m) Caudal view. (n-o) *Isoscelipteron acuticaudatum* Li et al., photo. (n) Lateral view. (o)
4053 Ventral view. (P-Q) *Berothera bannana* (Yang), photo. (p) Lateral view. (q) Ventral view. (r)
4054 *Haploberotha persephone* Engel & Grimaldi, ventral view (BXAM BA-NEU-015), photo, lateral
4055 view. Abbreviations: S, Sternum; T, Tergum; cc, Callus cerci; ect, Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses;
4056 gst, Gonostyli; gx, Gonocoxites. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

4057

4058 **Figure S43. Male terminalia photos and drawings of Berothidae and Rhachiberothidae**

4059 **(Paraberothinae).** (a-h) Berothidae. (a-b) *Haploberotha persephone* Engel & Grimaldi, ventral

4060 view (BXAM BA-NEU-015), photos, lateral view. (c) *Jersiberotha tauberorum* Engel & Grimaldi

4061 (NIGP171720), photo, lateral view. (d-e) *Iceloberotha simulatrix* Engel & Grimaldi, (BXAM BA-

4062 NEU-018), ventral view. (d) Photo. (e) Drawing. (f) *Dolichoberotha bifurcata* Yang et al.
4063 (Paratype, EMTG BU002117), photo, lateral view. (g-h) *Cornoberotha aspoeckae* Yang et al.
4064 (Paratype, EMTG BU001214), photos, ventral view. (i-j) *Acanthoberotha cuspis* Nakamine et al.,
4065 (EMTG BU001992), lateral view. (i) Photo. (j) Drawing. (k), (n), *Creagroparaberotha* sp.1, lateral
4066 view (BXAM BA-NEU-021), lateral view. (k) Photo. (n) Drawing. (l-m) *Creagroparaberotha* sp.1,
4067 lateral view (BXAM BA-NEU-022), lateral view. (l) Photo. (m) Drawing. Abbreviations: S,
4068 Sternum; T, Tergum; cc, Callus cerci; ect, Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses; gst, Gonostyli; gx,
4069 Gonocoxites. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

4070

4071 **Figure S44. Male terminalia photos and drawings of Rhachiberothidae (Paraberothinae)**

4072 **Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae. (a-b) *Paraberothoides longispina*, (Holotype, EMTG**

4073 **BU001998), lateral view. (a) Photo. (b) Drawing. (c-d) *Burmodipteromantispa jiaxiaoe* Liu, Lu**

4074 & Zhang (BXAM BA-NEU-003), ventral view. (c) Photo. (d) Drawing. (e-f)
4075 *Kurtodipteromantispa relictata*, (Holotype, CAU-BA-GYH-19008), ventral view. (e) Photo. (f)
4076 Drawing. g, *Kurtodipteromantispa relictata* (Paratype, CAU-BA-GYH-19009), photo, lateral view.
4077 (h-j) *Kurtodipteromantispa univenula* (Holotype, NIGP173316). (h) Photo, lateral view. (i)
4078 Drawing, lateral view. (j) Drawing, dorsal view. (k-l) *Parvoasymphrasites aploneurus* (Holotype,
4079 NIGP171730), lateral view. (k) Photo. (l) Drawing. (m-n) *Plega* sp., photo. (m) Lateral view. (n)
4080 Caudal view. (o-p) *Trichoscelia* sp., photo. (o) Lateral view. (p) Caudal view. (q-r) *Haplacantha*
4081 *tenuis* (Paratype, NIGP171733), caudal view. (q) Photo. (r) Drawing. Abbreviations: S, Sternum; T,
4082 Tergum; cc, Callus cerci; ect, Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses; gst, Gonostyli; gx, Gonocoxites.
4083 Scale bars 0.2 mm.

4084

4085 **Figure S45. Male terminalia photos and drawings of Mantispidae (Doratomantispinae).** (a)

4086 *Paradoxomantispa mahaiyingae* Zhuo, Li & Liu (Holotype, BXAM BA-NEU-008), photo, ventral

4087 view. (b-c) *Doratomantispa ares* Li et al. (Holotype, NIGP 173084), lateral view. (b) Photo. (c)

4088 Drawing. (d-e) *Doratomantispa arcimaculata* Li et al. (Holotype, NIGP 177985), lateral view. (d)

4089 Photo. (e) Drawing. (f-g) *Doratomantispa zhangwenjuni* Zhuo, Li & Liu, (Holotype, BXAM BA-

4090 NEU-005), lateral view. (f) Photo. (g) Drawing. (h-i), *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al.

4091 (BXAM BA-NEU-034). (h) Photo. (i) Drawing. (j-k) *Dicranomantispa zhouae* Lu et al. (Holotype,

4092 CAU-BA-ZM-19003), lateral view. (j) Photo. (k) Drawing. (l) *Psilomantispa abnormis* Lu et al.

4093 (Holotype, CAU-BA-LX-19004), photo, ventral view. Abbreviations: S, Sternum; T, Tergum; cc,
 4094 Callus cerci; ect, Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses; gst, Gonostyli; gx, Gonocoxites. Scale bars in (a-
 4095 f), (i), 0.2 mm, in (g-h), (j-l), 1 mm.

4097 **Figure S46. Male terminalia photos of Mantispidae (DCM clade).** (a) *Theristria discolor*
 4098 (Westwood), lateral view. (b-e) *Theristria irnperfecta* (Westwood). (b) Lateral view. (c) dorsal
 4099 view. (d) Ventral view. (e) Caudal view. (f-g) *Allomantispa coniprocesa* Li et al. (f) Lateral view.
 4100 (g) Ventral view. (h) Caudal view. (i-k) *Allomantispa tibetana* Liu et al., 2015. (i) Lateral view. (j)
 4101 Ventral view. (k) Caudal view. (l-m) *Necyla flavacoxa* (Yang). (l) Lateral view. (m) Ventral view.
 4102 Abbreviations: S, Sternum; T, Tergum; cc, Callus cerci; ect, Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses; gst,
 4103 Gonostyli; gx, Gonocoxites. Scale bars in (b-e), 0.2 mm, in (a), (f-m), 1 mm.

4105 **Figure S47. Male terminalia and homology hypotheses of genital sclerites in Berothidae.** (a)
4106 *Osmyloberotha dispersa*, lateral view. (b) *Osmyloberotha chenzuyini*, lateral view. (c-d) *Nyrma*
4107 *kervillea* Navás, adapted from Aspöck (1989): Figures 3, 5. (c) Lateral view. (d) Sclerites, ventral
4108 view. (E-F) *Protobiella zelandica* Tillyard, adapted from Wise (1992): Figures 4, 6. (e) Lateral
4109 view. (f) Ventral view. (g-h) *Nosybus* sp. (g) Lateral view. (h) Caudal view. (i-j) *Naizema*
4110 *mendozae* (Esben-Petersen), adapted from MacLeod & Adams, 1967: Figures 20-21. (i), Lateral
4111 view. (j) Ventral view. (k-l) *Trichorma gracilipenne* Tillyard, adapted from Aspöck & Aspöck
4112 (1985): Figures 2, 4. (k) Lateral view. (l) Ventral view. (m-n) *Spiroberotha sanctarosa* Adams,
4113 adapted from Adams (1989): Figures 4, 6. (m) lateral view. (n) Sclerites, ventral view. (o-p)
4114 *Lomamyia squamosa* Carpenter, adapted from MacLeod & Adams, 1967: Figures 10-11, 13. (o)
4115 Lateral view. (p) Sclerites, ventral view. Abbreviations: T, Tergum; ect, ectoprocts.

4116

4117 **Figure S48. Male terminalia and homology hypotheses of genital sclerites in Berothidae,**

4118 **Rhachiberothidae and Mantispidae.** (a-g) Berothidae. (a-b) *Berotha bannana* (Yang), adapted

4119 from Li et al. (2018): Figures 12-13. (a) Lateral view. (b) Sclerites, ventral view. (c) *Icelobero*

4120 *simulatrix* Engel & Grimaldi (BXAM BA-NEU-018), ventral view. (d) *Cornobero*

4121 *thero* Yang et al. (Paratype, EMTG BU001214), ventral view. (e) *Cyrenobero*

4122 *thero* Adams, adapted from MacLeod & Adams (1967): Figure 7, lateral view. (f-g) *Speleobero*

4123 *thero* mineira Machado et al., adapted from Machado et al. (2022): Figures 9D, 10D. (f) Lateral view. (g)

4124 Sclerites, dorsal view. (h-l) Rhachiberothidae. (h) *Mucrobero*

4125 Ardila-Camacho et al. (2022): Figure 33a, 34a, lateral view. (i-j) *Rhachiberothera sheilae* Aspöck &
4126 Mansell, adapted from Aspöck & Mansell (1994): Figures 7-8. (i) Lateral view. (j) Caudal view. (k)
4127 *Acanthoberothera cuspis* Nakamine et al. (EMTG BU001992), lateral view. (l) *Creagroparaberothera*
4128 sp.1 (BXAM BA-NEU-022), lateral view. (m) *Mantispidipterella longissima* Liu et al.,
4129 Dipteromantispidae, adapted from Liu et al. (2017): Figure 4D, ventral view. (n-p) Mantispidae. (n)
4130 *Parvoasymphrasites aploneurus* (Holotype, NIGP171730), lateral view. (o) *Plega* sp., lateral view.
4131 (p) *Plega dactylota* Rehn, adapted from Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): Figure15d, ventral view.
4132 Abbreviations: T, Tergum; ect, ectoprocts.

4133

4134 **Figure S49. Male terminalia and homology hypotheses of genital sclerites in Mantispidae.** (a)

4135 *Haplacantha tenuis* (Paratype, NIGP171733), caudal view. (b) *Paradoxomantispa mahaiyingae*

4136 Zhuo, Li & Liu (Holotype, BXAM BA-NEU-008), ventral view. (c) *Doratomantispa*

4137 *zhangwenjuni* Zhuo, Li & Liu, (Holotype, BXAM BA-NEU-005), lateral view. (d)

4138 *Doratomantispa ares* Li et al. (Holotype, NIGP 173084), lateral view. (e) *Doratomantispa*

4139 *zhuozhengmingi* Zhuo, Li & Liu (Holotype, BXAM BA-NEU-002), lateral view. (f)

4140 *Doratomantispa arcimaculata* Li et al. (Holotype, NIGP 177985), lateral view. (g)

4141 *Doratomantispa longa* (Shi et al.), adapted from Shi et al. (2020): Figure 5D, lateral view. (h)

4142 *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al. (BXAM BA-NEU-034), lateral view. (i-j) *Allomantispa*

4143 *coniprocessa* Li et al.. (i) Lateral view. (j) Sclerites, ventral view. (k-l) *Ditaxis*

4144 *biseriata* (Westwood), adapted from Lambkin (1986a): Figures 40, 45. (k) Lateral view. (l)

4145 Sclerites, ventral view. (m-n) *Drepanicus chrysopinus* Brauer, adapted from Liu et al. (2015):

4146 Figure 9A, C. (m) Lateral view. (n) Sclerites, ventral view. (o-p) *Gerstaeckerella chilensis* (Hagen),

4147 adapted from Liu et al. (2015): Figure 9E, G. (o) Lateral view. (p) Sclerites, ventral view.

4148 Abbreviations: T, Tergum; ect, ectoprocts.

4149

4150 **Figure S50. Male terminalia and homology hypotheses of genital sclerites in Mantispidae.** (a-
 4151 b) *Theristria discolor* (Westwood), adapted from Lambkin (1986a): Figures 83, 88. (a) Lateral
 4152 view. (b) Sclerites, ventral view. (c) *Nolima pinal* Rehn, adapted from Reynoso & Contreras
 4153 (2019): Figure 9E, I, lateral view. (d-e) *Calomantispa spectabili* Banks, adapted from Lambkin et
 4154 al. (1986b): Figures 410, 415. (d) Lateral view. (e) Sclerites, ventral view. (f-g) *Eumantispa*
 4155 *harmandi* Okamoto. (f) Lateral view. (g) Sclerites, ventral view. Abbreviations: T, Tergum; ect,
 4156 ectoprocts.

4157

4158 **Figure S51. Female terminalia photos and drawings of Berothidae and Rhachiberothidae.** (a-
4159 o) Berothidae. (a-b) *Osmyloberotha magnimaculata* (Holotype, CAU-BA-GYH-19004), lateral
4160 view. (a) Photo. (b) Drawing. (c-d) *Osmyloberotha simpla* Khrarov (NIGP18068), lateral view. (c)
4161 Photo. (d) Drawing. (e-f) *Lomamyia flavicornis* (Walker), photos. (e) Lateral view. (f) Ventral view.
4162 (g-h) *Ansoberotha jiewenae* Yang, Shi & Ren (NIGP171715), lateral view. (g) Photo. (h) Drawing.
4163 (i) *Cornoberotha monogona* Yang et al. (Holotype, NIGP171708), photo, ventral view. (j-k)
4164 *Cornoberotha aspoeckae* Yang et al. (Holotype, NIGP171707), lateral view. (j) Photo. (k)
4165 Drawing. (l-m) *Dolichoberotha bifurcata* Yang et al. (Paratype, EMTG BU001991), ventral view.
4166 (l) Photo. (m) Drawing. (n-o) *Haploberotha persephone* Engel & Grimaldi (BXAM BA-NEU-
4167 015), lateral view. (n) Photo. (o) Drawing. (p-q) *Astioberotha falcipes* Nakamine et al. (EMTG
4168 BU001993), lateral view. (p) Photo. (q) Drawing. Abbreviations: S, Sternum; T, Tergum; ect,
4169 Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses; gx, Gonocoxites; hc, Hypocauda; phc, Pseudohypocauda. Scale
4170 bars 0.2 mm.

4171

4172 **Figure S52. Female terminalia photos and drawings of Rhachiberothidae. (a-h)**

4173 Paraberothinae. (a) *Micromantispa* sp. (EMTG BU002143), lateral view. (b) *Creagroparaberotha*

4174 *cuneata* Nakamine et al., (EMTG BU001995), lateral view. (c-d) *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al.

4175 (EMTG BU002121), lateral view. (c) Photo. (d) Drawing. (e-f) *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al.

4176 (CAU-BA-GYH-19006). (e) Photo. (f) Drawing. (g-h) *Micromantispa galeata* Nakamine et al.

4177 (BXAM BA-NEU-023). (g) Photo. (h) Drawing. (i-n) *Dicranoberotha liumohanae*. (i) Caudal
4178 view (Paratype, BXAM BA-NEU-026). (j-k) Lateral view (Holotype, NIGP171723). (j) Photo. (k)
4179 Drawing. (l) Photo, caudal view (Paratype, CAU-BA-NH-20002). (m-n) Lateral view (Paratype,
4180 NIGP171727). (m) Photo. (n) Drawing. (o-p) *Dicranoberotha zhangzhiqiae*, (Holotype, BXAM
4181 BA-NEU-027), lateral view. (o) Photo. (p) Drawing. Abbreviations: S, Sternum; T, Tergum; ect,
4182 Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses; gx, Gonocoxites; hc, Hypocauda; phc, Pseudohypocauda. Scale
4183 bars 0.2 mm.

4185 **Figure S53. Female terminalia photos and drawings of Rhachiberothidae and Mantispidae**
4186 **(Symphrasinae).** (a-b) *Dicranoberotha zhangzhiqiae*, (Holotype, BXAM BA-NEU-027), caudal
4187 view. (a) Photo. (b) Drawing. (c-d) *Parasymphrasites electrinus* Lu et al. (Holotype, EMTG
4188 BU002162), lateral view. (c) Photo. (d) Drawing. (e-g) *Proplega evelynae* (Holotype, BXAM BA-
4189 NEU-032). (e) Photo, lateral view. (f) Photo, details of gonocoxites+ gonapophyses 8. (g)
4190 Drawing, lateral view. (h-i) *Habrosymphrasis xiai* Shi et al., lateral view (NIGP171729), lateral
4191 view. (h) Photo. (i) Drawing. (j-k) *Plega* sp., photo. (j) Ventral view. (k) Lateral view. (l-m)
4192 *Haplosymphrasites zouae* Lu et al. (NIGP171831), ventral view. (l) Photo. (m) Drawing.
4193 Abbreviations: S, Sternum; T, Tergum; ect, Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses; gx, Gonocoxites; hc,
4194 Hypocauda; phc, Pseudohypocauda. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

4195

4196 **Figure S54. Female terminalia photos and drawings of Mantispididae.** (a-f) *Mesomantisporus*

4197 *felixporcus* (Holotype, NIGP171728). (a) Ventral view, photo. (b) Ventral view, drawing. (c)

4198 Lateral view, photo. (d) Lateral view, drawing. (e) Caudal view, photo. (f) Caudal view, drawing.

4199 (g-h) *Haplacantha tenuis*, (Holotype, NIGP171732), lateral view. (g) Photo. (h) Drawing. (j-n)

4200 *Doratomantispa*. (i-j) *Doratomantispa gaoyuhei* Li et al. (Holotype, CAU-BA-GYH-19003),

4201 lateral view. (i) Photo. (j) Drawing. (k-l) *Acanthomantispa* sp. (NIGP171834), lateral view. (k)

4202 Photo. (l) Drawing. (m-n) *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et al. (Paratype, EMTG BU002270),

4203 lateral view. (m) Photo. (n) Drawing. Abbreviations: S, Sternum; T, Tergum; ect, Ectoprocts. gp,

4204 Gonapophyses; gx, Gonocoxites. Scale bars 0.2 mm.

4206 **Figure S55. Female terminalia photos of Mantispidae (DCM clade).** (a-b) *Gerstaeckerella*
 4207 *chilensis* (Hagen). (a) Lateral view. (b) Ventral view. (c-d) *Theristria storeyi* Lambkin. (c) Lateral
 4208 view. (d) Ventral view. (E-F) *Calomantispia venusta* Lambkin. (e) Lateral view. (f) Ventral view.
 4209 (g-h) *Tuberonotha insignis* (Navás). (g) Lateral view. (h) Ventral view. Abbreviations: S, Sternum;
 4210 T, Tergum; ect, Ectoprocts. gp, Gonapophyses; gx, Gonocoxites; phc, Pseudohypocauda. Scale
 4211 bars 1 mm.

4213 **Figure S56. Female terminalia and homology hypotheses of genital sclerites in Berothidae.** (a)
4214 *Osmyloberotha magnimaculata* (Holotype, CAU-BA-GYH-19004), lateral view. (b-c) *Nyrma*
4215 *kervillea* Navás, adapted from Aspöck & Aspöck (1989): Figures 8-9, Lateral view. (c) Ventral
4216 view. (d) *Elektroberotha groehni* Makarkin & Ohl, adapted from Makarkin & Ohl (2015): Figure
4217 7D, ventral view. (e-f) *Austroberothella reiki* Aspöck & Aspöck, adapted from Aspöck & Aspöck
4218 (1985): Figures 28-29. (e) Lateral view. (f) Ventral view. (g-h) *Trichoma gracilipenne* Tillyard,
4219 adapted from Aspöck & Aspöck (1985): Figures 6-7. (g) Lateral view. (h) Ventral view. (i-j)
4220 *Naizema mendozina* (Esben-Petersen), adapted from MacLeod & Adams (1967): Figures 23-24. (i)
4221 Lateral view. (j) Ventral view. (k) *Spiroberotha sanctarosa* Adams, adapted from Adams (1989):
4222 Figure 7, lateral view. (l) *Nosybus nobilis* Navás, adapted from Aspöck & Aspöck (1982): Figure 5,
4223 lateral view. (m-n) *Lomnmyia flawcornis* (Walker), adapted from MacLeod & Adams (1967):
4224 Figures 18-19. (m) Lateral view. (n) Ventral view. (o-p) *Berothera bannana* (Yang), adapted from Li
4225 et al. (2018): Figures 15-16. (o) Lateral view. (p) Ventral view. T, Tergum; ect, Ectoprocts.

4226

4227 **Figure S57. Female terminalia and homology hypotheses of genital sclerites in Berothidae**

4228 **and Rhachiberothidae.** (a) *Protoberotha mimuta* Huang et al., adapted from Huang et al. (2019):

4229 Figure 3B, lateral view. (b-c) *Speleoberotha mineira* Machado et al., adapted from Machado et al.

4230 (2022): Figures A-B. (b) Lateral view. (c) Ventral view. (d) *Aggregataberoth punctata* Wang,

4231 Huang & Wang, adapted from Wang et al. (2022): Figure 3B, lateral view. (e-f) *Cyrcnoberoth*

4232 *penai* MacLeod & Adams (1967): Figures 15-16. (e) Lateral view. (f) Ventral view. (g)

4233 *Haploberotha persephone* Engel & Grimaldi (BXAM BA-NEU-015), lateral view. (h) Berothidae

4234 indeterminate adapted from Pérez-de la Fuente & Peñalver (2021): Figure 5B. (i) *Cornoberotha*
4235 *aspoeckae* Yang et al. (Holotype, NIGP171707), lateral view. (j) *Dolichoberotha bifurcata* Yang et
4236 al. (Paratype, EMTG BU001991), ventral view. (k) *Ansoberotha jiewenae* Yang, Shi & Ren
4237 (NIGP171715), lateral view. (l) *Micromantispa cristata* Shi et al. (EMTG BU002121),
4238 Paraberothinae, lateral view. (m-p) Rhachiberothinae. (m-n) *Rhachiberotha sheilae* Aspöck &
4239 Mansell, adapted from Aspöck & Mansell (1994): Figures 13-14. (m) Lateral view. (n) Ventral
4240 view. (o-p) *Mucroberotha vesicaria* Tjeder, adapted from Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): Figure
4241 35a-b. (o) Lateral view. (p) Ventral view. T, Tergum; ect, Ectoprocts.

4242

4243 **Figure S58. Female terminalia and homology hypotheses of genital sclerites in**

4244 **Rhachiberothidae, Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae.** (a-b) *Dicranoberotha*,

4245 Rhachiberothidae. (a) *Dicranoberotha liumohanae* (Holotype, NIGP171723), lateral view. (b)

4246 *Dicranoberotha zhangzhiqiae*, (Holotype, BXAM BA-NEU-027), lateral view. (c-d)

4247 Dipteromantispidae. (c) *Halteriomantispa grimaldii* Liu, Lu & Zhang (Holotype, EMTG

4248 BU001924), lateral view. (d) *Kurtodipteromantispa zhuodei* Li & Liu (Holotype, BXAM BA-

4249 NEU-001), lateral view. (e-o) Mantispidae. (e-f) *Mesomantispoides felixporcus* (Holotype,
4250 NIGP171728). (e) Ventral view. (f) Caudal view. (g) *Habrosymphrosis xiai* Shi et al.
4251 (NIGP171729), lateral view. (h) *Proplega evelynae* (Holotype, BXAM BA-NEU-032), lateral
4252 view. (i-j) *Anchieta* sp., adapted from Ardila-Camacho et al. (2021): Figure 35c-d. (i) Lateral view.
4253 (j) Ventral view. (k) *Doratomantispa gaoyuhei* Li et al. (Holotype, CAU-BA-GYH-19003), lateral
4254 view. (l) *Acanthomantispa* sp. (NIGP171834), lateral view. (m) *Acanthomantispa maculata* Lu et
4255 al. (Paratype, EMTG BU002270), lateral view. (n-o) *Allomantispa coniprocessa* Li et al.. (n)
4256 Lateral view. (o) Ventral view. T, Tergum; ect, Ectoprocts.

4257

4258 **Figure S59. Female terminalia and homology hypotheses of genital sclerites in Mantispidae.**

4259 **(A-B) *Ditaxis biseriata* (Westwood), adapted from Lambkin (1986a):** Figures 35-36. (a)

4260 Lateral view. (b) Ventral view. (c-d) *Drepanicus chrysopinus* Brauer, adapted from Liu et al.

4261 (2015): Figure 10A-B. (c) Lateral view. (d) Ventral view. (e-f) *Gerstaeckerella chilensis* (Hagen),

4262 adapted from Liu et al. (2015): Figure 10D-E. (e) Lateral view. (f) Ventral view. (g-h) *Theristria*

4263 *discolor* (Westwood), adapted from Lambkin (1986a): Figure 80. (g) Lateral view. (h) Ventral
 4264 view. (i-j) *Theristria delicatula* (Westwood), adapted from Lambkin (1986a): Figures 237-238. (i)
 4265 Lateral view. (j) Ventral view. (k-l) *Calomantispa venusta* Lambkin (1986b): Figures 436-437. (k)
 4266 Lateral view. (l) Ventral view. (m-n) *Eumantispa harmandi* Okamoto. (m) Lateral view. (n) Ventral
 4267 view. Abbreviations: T, Tergum; ect, ectoprocts.

4268
 4269 **Figure S60. Phylogenetic trees based on maximum parsimony analysis, using new technology**
 4270 **search.** (a) Strict consensus of 10 most parsimonious trees of length 964 under equal weighting,
 4271 based on the morphological matrix of 146×232. Consistency index = 0.350, retention index =
 4272 0.856. (b) Strict consensus of 10 most parsimonious trees of length 941 under equal weighting,
 4273 based on the morphological matrix of 132×232. Consistency index = 0.358, retention index =
 4274 0.856. (c) Strict consensus of 10 most parsimonious trees of length 948 under equal weighting,
 4275 based on the morphological matrix of 143×232. Consistency index = 0.355, retention index =
 4276 0.859. Abbreviations: BM1, The first major clade of Berothidae; BM2, The second major clade of
 4277 Berothidae; R1, The first major clade of Rhachiberothidae; R2, The second major clade of

4278 Rhachiberothidae; R3, The third major clade of Rhachiberothidae; PD,
 4279 *Paradoxoberotha*+*Dicranoberotha* clade; TPM, Tubular-pronotum mantispid clade; DCM,
 4280 Drepanicinae+Calomantispinae+Mantispinae clade.

4281

4282 **Figure S61. Phylogenetic trees based on maximum likelihood analysis (MK+FQ+ASC+G4).**

4283 (a) Phylogram based on the morphological matrix of 146×232. (b) Phylogram based on the

4284 morphological matrix of 132×232. (c) Phylogram based on the morphological matrix of 143×232.

4285 Numbers at nodes are bootstrap frequencies from 1000 replicates. Abbreviations: BM1, The first

4286 major clade of Berothidae; BM2, The second major clade of Berothidae; R1, The first major clade

4287 of Rhachiberothidae; R2, The second major clade of Rhachiberothidae; R3, The third major clade

4288 of Rhachiberothidae; PD, *Paradoxoberotha*+*Dicranoberotha* clade; TPM, Tubular-pronotum

4289 mantispid clade; DCM, Drepanicinae+Calomantispinae+Mantispinae clade.

4291 **Figure S62. Maximum compatible tree based on unpartitioned Bayesian inference. Node**
4292 **values represent median divergence times and node bars the 95%HPD of age distribution.**

4293

4294

Figure S63. Maximum compatible tree based on partitioned Bayesian inference. Node values

4295

represent median divergence times and node bars the 95%HPD of age distribution.

4296

4297 **Figure S64. Maximum compatible tree based on unpartitioned Bayesian inference. with**
 4298 **DRA correction. Node values and branch colours represent clade mean morphological**
 4299 **evolutionary rates.**

4304

4305 **Figure S66. Maximum compatible tree based on partitioned Bayesian inference. with DRA**
 4306 **correction. Node values and branch colours represent clade mean morphological**
 4307 **evolutionary rates of foreleg.**

4308

4309 **Figure S67. Maximum compatible tree based on partitioned Bayesian inference. with DRA**

4310 **correction. Node values and branch colours represent clade mean morphological**

4311 **evolutionary rates of pterothorax & wings.**

4312

4313 **Figure S68. Maximum compatible tree based on partitioned Bayesian inference. with DRA**
 4314 **correction. Node values and branch colours represent clade mean morphological**
 4315 **evolutionary rates of genitalia.**

4316

4317

4318 **Figure S69. Morphological evolutionary rates through time and rate comparisons for**

4319 **different partitions. (a-f) Morphological evolutionary rates estimated through time, respectively**

4320 for overall Mantispoidea, Berothidae, raptorial Mantispoidea, Rhachiberothidae,

4321 Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae. (a) Overall (w) morphological evolutionary rates, estimated

4322 by Bayesian inference under a single partition. (b) Head & prothorax morphological evolutionary

4323 rates, estimated by Bayesian inference under four partitions. (c) Head & prothorax (HP)

4324 morphological evolutionary rates, estimated by Bayesian inference under four partitions. (d)

4325 Foreleg (f) morphological evolutionary rates, estimated by Bayesian inference under four
4326 partitions. (e) Pterothorax & wings (PW) morphological evolutionary rates, estimated by Bayesian
4327 inference under four partitions. (f) Genitalia (g) morphological evolutionary rates, estimated by
4328 Bayesian inference under four partitions. Abbreviations: g, Morphological evolutionary rate
4329 comparisons for overall body, head & prothorax, foreleg, pterothorax & wings and genitalia.
4330

4331

4332 **Figure S70. Morphospace 3D-plot for different taxonomic groups based on the results of the**

4333 **disparity analyses of MORD matrices. (a) Whole body (see the interactive 3D graphic: [whole](#)**

4334 **[body morphospace.html](#)), (b) Whole body excluding genitalia (see the interactive 3D graphic:**

4335 **[whole body \(excluding genitalia\) morphospace.html](#)) (c) HP (see the interactive 3D graphic: [head](#)**

4336 [& prothorax morphospace.html](#)) and (d) Foreleg (see the interactive 3D graphic: [foreleg](#)
4337 [morphospace.html](#)). (e) PW (see the interactive 3D graphic: [pterothorax & wings](#)
4338 [morphospace.html](#)). The number on each 3D convex hull is its volume value (see details in
4339 Supplementary Table S4).
4340

4341

4342 **Figure S71. Phylomorphospace comparisons of different partitions for different taxonomic**

4343 **groups in Mantispoidea, based on disparity analyses of MORD matrices, proxy by sov. (a)**

4344 **Whole body. (b) Whole body excluding genitalia, (c) HP. (d) Foreleg. (e) PW. Abbreviations: B,**

4345 **Berothidae; rM, Raptorial Mantispoidea; R, Rhachiberothidae; P, Paraberothinae; Rh,**

4346 Rhachiberothinae; D, Dipteromantispidae; M, Mantispidae; Me, Mesomantispinae; S,
 4347 Symphrasinae; Do, Doratomantispinae; Dre, Drepanicinae; C, Calomantispinae; Ma, Mantispinae.
 4348

4349
 4350 **Figure S72. Morphospace comparisons of different partitions for different taxonomic groups**
 4351 **in Mantispoidea, based on disparity analyses of MORD matrices, proxy by sov. (a) Whole**
 4352 **body. (b) Whole body excluding genitalia, (c) HP. (d) Foreleg. (e) PW. Abbreviations: B,**
 4353 **Berothidae; rM, Raptorial Mantispoidea; R, Rhachiberothidae; P, Paraberothinae; Rh,**

4354 Rhachiberothinae; D, Dipteromantispidae; M, Mantispidae; Me, Mesomantispinae; S,
 4355 Symphrasinae; Do, Doratomantispinae; Dre, Drepanicinae; C, Calomantispinae; Ma, Mantispinae.

4356
 4357 **Figure S73. Permutation tests with sample size corrected (Phylomorphospace) of different**
 4358 **partitions for different taxonomic groups, proxy by sov. (a) Whole body. (b) Whole body**
 4359 **excluding genitalia, (c) HP. (d) Foreleg. (e) PW. Each box represents a distribution of the**
 4360 **proportion greater than the observed value of the test statistic in the null distribution. Grey line**
 4361 **highlights the value of 0.025 or 0.975. Difference lower than 0.025 represents the disparity of the**
 4362 **former lower than the latter significantly, and the condition of the difference higher than 0.975 was**

4363 inverse. Abbreviations: B, Berothidae; rM, Raptorial Mantispoidea; R, Rhachiberothidae; P,
 4364 Paraberothinae; Rh, Rhachiberothinae; D, Dipteromantispidae; M, Mantispidae; Me,
 4365 Mesomantispinae; S, Symphrasinae; Do, Doratomantispinae; Dre, Drepanicinae; C,
 4366 Calomantispinae; Ma, Mantispinae.

4367
 4368 **Figure S74. Permutation tests with sample size corrected (Morphospace) of different**
 4369 **partitions for different taxonomic groups, proxy by sov. (a) Whole body. (b) Whole body**
 4370 **excluding genitalia, (c) HP. (d) Foreleg. (e) PW. Each box represents a distribution of the**
 4371 **proportion greater than the observed value of the test statistic in the null distribution. Grey line**

4372 highlights the value of 0.025 or 0.975. Difference lower than 0.025 represents the disparity of the
4373 former lower than the latter significantly, and the condition of the difference higher than 0.975 was
4374 inverse. Abbreviations: B, Berothidae; rM, Raptorial Mantispoidea; R, Rhachiberothidae; P,
4375 Paraberothinae; Rh, Rhachiberothinae; D, Dipteromantispidae; M, Mantispidae; Me,
4376 Mesomantispinae; S, Symphrasinae; Do, Doratomantispinae; Dre, Drepanicinae; C,
4377 Calomantispinae; Ma, Mantispinae.

4379 **Figure S75. Phylomorphospace comparisons of different partitions for different time bins of**
4380 **overall Mantispoidea, Berothidae, raptorial Mantispoidea, Rhachiberothidae,**
4381 **Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae, based on disparity analyses of MORD matrices, proxy**
4382 **by sov. (a) Whole body. (b) Whole body excluding genitalia, (c) HP. (d) Foreleg. (e) PW. (f)**
4383 **Comparison of morphospace of HP (h), foreleg (f) and PW (p) respectively for overall**
4384 **Mantispoidea, Berothidae, raptorial Mantispoidea, Rhachiberothidae, Dipteromantispidae and**
4385 **Mantispidae. Abbreviations: M, Mantispoidea; B, Berothidae; rM, Raptorial Mantispoidea; R,**
4386 **Rhachiberothidae; D, Dipteromantispidae; Ma, Mantispidae; T, Triassic; J, Jurassic, K, Cretaceous;**
4387 **KE, Early Cretaceous; KL, Late Cretaceous; Pg & N, Paleogene & Neogene; Q, Quaternary.**

4389 **Figure S76. Permutation tests with sample size corrected (Phylomorphospace) of different**
4390 **partitions for different time bins of overall Mantispoidea, Berothidae, raptorial**
4391 **Mantispoidea, Rhachiberothidae, Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae, proxy by sov. (a)**
4392 Whole body. (b) Whole body excluding genitalia, (c) HP. (d) Foreleg. (e) PW. Each box represents
4393 a distribution of the proportion greater than the observed value of the test statistic in the null
4394 distribution. Grey line highlights the value of 0.025 or 0.975. Difference lower than 0.025
4395 represents the disparity of the former lower than the latter significantly, and the condition of the
4396 difference higher than 0.975 was inverse. Abbreviations: M, Mantispoidea; B, Berothidae; rM,
4397 Raptorial Mantispoidea; R, Rhachiberothidae; D, Dipteromantispidae; Ma, Mantispidae; T,
4398 Triassic; J, Jurassic, K, Cretaceous; KE, Early Cretaceous; KL, Late Cretaceous; Pg & N,
4399 Paleogene & Neogene; Q, Quaternary.

4400

1. Ocular plane in frontal view

- not anteriorly curved inwards
- not anteriorly curved inwards

2. Vertex

- domed
- flattened

3. Pronotum shape

■ shield-shaped, posteroventrally not fused

■ tubular, posteroventrally fused

4. Maculae

absent
present

5. Prothorax

■ not elongated posteriad insertion of procoxa

■ slightly elongated posteriad insertion of procoxa, making procoxa insert near middle of prothorax

■ strongly elongated posteriad, making procoxa insert at anterior apex of prothorax

6. Postfurcasternum

absent

present

7. Area_of_procoxal_insertion

- barely_expanded
- distinctly_expanded

8. Precoxal_bridge

absent
 present

9. Ratio length/width of prothorax (pronotum)

- short, at most twice as long as wide
- compressed, nearly two times as long as wide
- 2-2.5 times as long as wide
- 2-2.5 times as long as wide & 3-4 times as long as wide
- 3-4 times as long as wide
- over 4.5 times as long as wide

10. Foreleg

■ cursorial
■ raptorial

11. Procoxa

not elongated
 elongated

12. Pofremur

■ not incrassate
■ incrassate

13. Inccrassate_profemur_in_lateral_view

14. Profemoral ventral integumentary specializations (ISs)

absent
present

15. Stinger-shaped ISs

absent
 present

16. Thorn-shaped ISs (ARD model)

absent
 present

16. Thorn-shaped ISs (ER model)

absent
 present

17. Saber-shaped ISs

absent
 present

18. Tubercle-shaped ISs

absent

present

19. Large pedicellate, thickened ISs

absent
 present

20. Spine-shaped ISs

- absent
- present

21. Profemoral_ventral_ISs

- absent
- fully_developed_and_complete
- reduced_and_incomplete
- only_two_processes_remained

22. Major process

- absent
- simple
- branched

23. Protibia near joint with profemur

not curved
 curved

24. Protibia medially

straight
 curved

25. Closed proibia

longer_to_slightly_shorter_than_profemur

about 4/5× length of profemur

3/4-2/3× length of profemur

1/2× length of profemur

□□ 26. Protibia_plus_protarsus

- longer_than_femur
- as_long_as_femur
- shorter_than_femur

28. Protibial specialized setae

absent
 present

29. Protibial specialized setae

-
- erected
- flattened
- erected & flattened

30. Curving degree of protibial specialized setae

-
- not curved
- smoothly curved
- angularly curved
- not curved & smoothly curved

31. Protarsal_ventral_specialized_setae

absent
 present

32. Male distodorsal specialized setae of probasitarsus

absent

long

minute, present as "Stitz organ"

33. Female distodorsal specialized setae of probasitarsus

- absent
- long
- minute, present as "Stitz organ"

34. Forewing length/width ratio

4401 **Figures S77-S110. Summary of maximum likelihood ancestral state reconstructions, using**
4402 **equal rate (ER) model for representative discrete characters of head (Supplementary**
4403 **Figures 77-78), prothorax (Supplementary Figures 79-85), foreleg (Supplementary Figures**
4404 **86-109) and wings (Supplementary Figures 110), onto the partitioned time-calibrated tree.**
4405 **The pie charts at key nodes illustrate the probabilities for ancestral state.**
4406

Fig. S111

Head & prothorax
-0.243 comprehensive PCoA value 0.133
length=128.234

4407 **Figure S111. Summary of maximum likelihood ancestral state reconstructions for**
4408 **comprehensive PCoA scores of HP onto the partitioned time-calibrated tree.**
4409

Fig. S112

Foreleg comprehensive PCoA value

-0.191 0.247

length=128.234

4410 **Figure S112. Summary of maximum likelihood ancestral state reconstructions for**
4411 **comprehensive PCoA scores of the foreleg onto the partitioned time-calibrated tree.**
4412

Fig. S113

a

b

- Mantispoidea
- Berothidae
- raptorial Mantispoidea
- Mantispidae
- Rhachiberothidae
- Dipteromantispidae
- ★ Ancestral state of Mantispoidea

Pterothorax & wings

-0.137 comprehensive PCoA value 0.063

length=128.234

4413 **Figure S113. Summary of maximum likelihood ancestral state reconstructions for (a)**
4414 **comprehensive PCoA scores of PW onto the partitioned time-calibrated tree, and (b)**
4415 **comprehensive PCoA scores dynamics over time respectively for overall Mantispoidea,**
4416 **Berothidae, raptorial Mantispoidea, Rhachiberothidae, Dipteromantispidae and**
4417 **Mantispidae.** The score of IASM serving as the origin dotted line, based on the maximum
4418 likelihood reconstruction of ancestral states. The magnitude and direction of the value represents
4419 the morphological polarity (measured by the line of the initial ancestral state (LI)) and the extent
4420 to the overall morphology of anatomical regions deviated from the LI. The higher difference
4421 between the score and the LI indicates the higher morphological deviation of the taxonomic group
4422 from IASM (i.e., more apomorphic changes).
4423

Fig. S114

4424 **Figure S114. Summary of maximum likelihood ancestral state reconstructions for body size**
4425 **onto the partitioned time-calibrated tree, using amber maximum plus compressed fossil and**
4426 **extant minimum forewing length as the proxy (MmF).**
4427

Fig. S115

4428 **Figure S115. Summary of maximum likelihood ancestral state reconstructions for (a) body**
4429 **size onto the partitioned time-calibrated tree, and (b) the body size dynamics over time**
4430 **respectively for overall Mantispoidea (Ⓐ excluding samples from mid-Cretaceous Myanmar**
4431 **amber, Ⓑ including samples from mid-Cretaceous Myanmar amber), Berothidae, raptorial**
4432 **Mantispoidea, Rhachiberothidae, Dipteromantispidae and Mantispidae, using forewing**
4433 **length (MF) as the proxy, excluding samples from Myanmar amber.**

4434

4435 **Figure S116. Set of distinct speciation rate-shift configurations sampled by fossil-BAMM**

4436 **during simulation of the posterior probabilities. The nine most commonly sampled**

4437 **configurations are shown. Grey dots indicate diversification rate shifts. Larger dots indicate**

4438 larger diversification rate shifts. The sampling frequency of each diversification scheme is
4439 shown above each plot.

4440

4441 **Figure S117. Set of distinct extinction rate-shift configurations sampled by fossil-BAMM**

4442 **during simulation of the posterior probabilities. The nine most commonly sampled**

4443 configurations are shown. Grey dots indicate diversification rate shifts. Larger dots indicate
4444 larger diversification rate shifts. The sampling frequency of each diversification scheme is
4445 shown above each plot.

4446

4447 **Figure S118. Set of distinct net diversification rate-shift configurations sampled by fossil-**
 4448 **BAMM during simulation of the posterior probabilities. The nine most commonly sampled**
 4449 **configurations are shown. Grey dots indicate diversification rate shifts. Larger dots indicate**
 4450 **larger diversification rate shifts. The sampling frequency of each diversification scheme is**
 4451 **shown above each plot.**

4452 **Figure S119. Speciation, extinction and net diversification of different taxonomic groups**
 4453 **through time in Mantispoidea. based on fossil-BAMM model, using binary partitioned time**
 4454 **through time in Mantispoidea. based on fossil-BAMM model, using binary partitioned time**

4455 **tree as input.** (a) Overall Mantispoidea. (b) Berothidae. (c) Raptorial Mantispoidea. (d)
 4456 Rhachiberothidae. (e) Dipteromantispidae. (f) Mantispidae. The area around medians are 95%
 4457 highest posterior density (HPD) intervals.

4458

4459 **Figure S120. (a) Speciation, (b) extinction and (c) net diversification through time of overall**
4460 **Mantispoidea, as well as Bayesian inferences for paleoenvironmental and intrinsic**
4461 **correlation parameters on speciation and extinction respectively for (d) Rhachiberothidae**
4462 **and (e) Mantispidae, under MBD with the exponential model (-m 0 option). The area around**
4463 **medians are 95% and 50% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals.**

4464

4465 **Figure S121. Speciation rate through time of (a) overall Mantispoidea, (b) Berothidae, (c)**

4466 **raptorial Mantispoidea, (d) Rhachiberothidae, (e) Dipteromantispidae and (f) Mantispidae,**

4467 **using MBD with the linear model (-m 1 option), based on the speciation and extinction**

4468 **information from the partitioned tip-dating Bayesian inference.** The area around medians are
4469 95% and 50% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals.

4470

4471 **Figure S122. Extinction rate through time of (a) overall Mantispoidea, (b) Berothidae, (c)**
4472 **raptorial Mantispoidea, (d) Rhachiberothidae, (e) Dipteromantispidae and (f) Mantispidae,**
4473 **using MBD with the linear model (-m 1 option), based on the speciation and extinction**
4474 **information from the partitioned tip-dating Bayesian inference. The area around medians are**
4475 **95% and 50% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals.**

4476

4477 **Figure S123. Net diversification rate through time of (a) overall Mantispoidea, (b)**

4478 **Berothidae, (c) raptorial Mantispoidea, (d) Rhachiberothidae, (e) Dipteromantispidae and (f)**

4479 **Mantispidae, using MBD with the linear model (-m 1 option), based on the speciation and**

4485 **Raptorial Mantispoidea, (d) Rhachiberothidae, (e) Dipteromantispidae and (f) Mantispidae,**
4486 **using MBD with the linear model (-m1 option).** One asterisk (*) indicates a weak support ($\omega <$
4487 0.5) for a potential strong effect (95% HPD different from 0) or a strong support ($\omega > 0.5$) for a
4488 potential small effect (95% HPD crossing 0). Two asterisk (**) indicates a strong support for a
4489 potential strong effect (95% HPD different from 0).
4490

4491

4492 **Figure S125. Overall morphological disparity through time of (a) overall Mantispoidea, (b)**

4493 **Berothidae, (c) Raptorial Mantispoidea, (d) Rhachiberothidae and (e) Mantispidae,**

4494 **excluding samples from mid-Cretaceous Myanmar amber. The area around medians are 95%**

4495 **and 50% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals.**

4496

4497 **Figure S126. Diversification dynamics among major mantispoid lineages through time,**

4498 **based on fossil-BAMM analysis, excluding the samples from mid-Cretaceous Myanmar**

4499 **amber.** (a) Speciation rates, (c) Extinction rates and (e) Net diversification rates in partitioned
4500 time-calibrated trees, with corresponding rate density images. Red dots indicate the 95% credible
4501 rate shifts. (b) Speciation, (d) Extinction and (f) Net diversification rates through time of overall
4502 Mantispoidea. The area around medians are 95% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals.

4503

4504 **Figure S127. Speciation rate through time of (a) overall Mantispoidea, (b) Berothidae, (c)**

4505 **raptorial Mantispoidea, (d) Rhachiberothidae, (e) Dipteromantispidae and (f) Mantispidae,**

4506 **using MBD with the exponential model (-m 0 option), based on the speciation and extinction**

4507 information from the partitioned tip-dating Bayesian inference, excluding the samples from
4508 mid-Cretaceous Myanmar amber. The area around medians are 95% and 50% highest posterior
4509 density (HPD) intervals.

4510

4511 **Figure S128. Extinction rate through time of (a) overall Mantispoidea, (b) Berothidae, (c)**
4512 **raptorial Mantispoidea, (d) Rhachiberothidae, (e) Dipteromantispidae and (f) Mantispidae,**
4513 **using MBD with the exponential model (-m 0 option), based on the speciation and extinction**
4514 **information from the partitioned tip-dating Bayesian inference, excluding the samples from**
4515 **mid-Cretaceous Myanmar amber. The area around medians are 95% and 50% highest posterior**
4516 **density (HPD) intervals.**

4517

4518 **Figure S129. Net diversification rate through time of (a) overall Mantispoidea, (b)**

4519 **Berothidae, (c) raptorial Mantispoidea, (d) Rhachiberothidae, (e) Dipteromantispidae and (f)**

4520 **Mantispidae, using MBD with the exponential model (-m 0 option), based on the speciation**

4521 and extinction information from the partitioned tip-dating Bayesian inference, excluding the
4522 samples from mid-Cretaceous Myanmar amber. The area around medians are 95% and 50%
4523 highest posterior density (HPD) intervals.

4524
4525 **Figure S130. Ecological reconstruction of the mid-Cretaceous species in raptorial**
4526 **Mantispoidea.** Top and left middle: *Halteriomantispa grimaldii* Liu, Lu & Zhang
4527 (Dipteromantispidae). Left bottom: *Mesomantispoides felixporcus* Li et al. (Mantispidae). Middle:
4528 *Dicranoberotha liumohanae* Zhuo, Li & Liu (Rhachiberothidae). Right top: *Doratomantispa*
4529 *gaoyuhei* Li et al. (Mantispidae). Background vegetation is the reconstruction of *Tropidogyne*
4530 *pentaptera* Poinar & Chambers.